

ETHICAL LEADERSHIP IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR: A STUDY OF NIGERIA

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Student Declaration

I declare that this thesis has not been submitted for another comparable academic award

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ABSTRACT

The challenges and the growing issues of ethical scandals in respect to leadership in diverse organisations (public, private and hybrid sectors) has driven the growing demand for ethics as a core pillar of leadership. This has driven the necessity for critical research works in the field of ethical leadership as a solution to these ethical challenges. The adoption of the concept of ethical leadership in recent years as a countermeasure towards the surge of ethical scandals involving leaders in organisations. Ethical leadership is not a relatively new paradigm within the leadership construct. Research studies have shown progress in understanding the constituent of ethics as a core component of leadership within the last three decades. While achieving a nascent state with regards to understanding and inculcating it within the field, there exists a fragmentation about the conceptualisation of ethical leadership and gaps in knowledge within the field especially with regards to skills.

This research study explored the concept of ethical leadership within the Nigeria public sector, with a core emphasis on the ethic-based challenges and the development of a skills framework to foster ethical leadership in the sector to improve their effectiveness and performance. Whilst there are studies on the development and behaviours of ethical leaders, this study contributes to the literature by providing a skills-based understanding of ethical leadership. This study addressed the gap through the exploration of Nigerian public sector leaders.

An interpretivist philosophy underpinned this study, which utilised an inductive approach to provide a medium for understanding and drawing information to garner a better picture of the phenomenon. Qualitative semi-structured interviews were adopted to acquire rich data and insight into public sector leader's perspective. A thematic analysis was adopted to identify themes of ethical leadership in the Nigerian public sector.

Findings from this study allowed for several contributions to the body of knowledge in the field of ethical leadership. An adoption of a systematic review process was done to critic current literature of ethical leadership and implements a series of set questions to explore and provide a basis for future study. An empirical skills-based framework of ethical leadership was constructed from the findings of this study's field research. This framework identifies the ethic-based challenges and the skills essential for an ethical leader. Furthermore, future avenues for research were derived.

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

The growing number of public related scandals and the frequent media reports on issues related to lack and loss in trust from several organisations in recent times has fuelled the need for a reassessment and critical research into the growing problems facing the lack of leadership and the abilities of leaders to curb these problems. Organisations are faced with the challenges of instilling ethical frameworks and code of conducts to proffer solutions to this growing problem. A perfect example in recent times is the diesel car scandal of Volkswagen and the case of disregarding moral and ethical code of conduct. A critical aspect in this situation is the pinpointing of the leadership as one of the reasons for breaking the moral code. With the prevalence of ethical related scandals such as the type in the Volkswagen situation, critical and extensive research has been carried out in the investigation of ethical leadership as a major solution since the mid-2000s (Quade et al., 2017). The growing challenges faced with lack of ethical values and code of conduct in recent times has sparked the necessity of critical research works and investigation into ethically led leadership. Toor & Ofori, (2009) reiterate the toxic, dangerous and destructive nature of a leadership without high ethical and moral value. The lack of ethical balance and strong moral values in honing the affairs of leadership in organisations has led to both direct and indirect harm of thousands of employees within organisations, invoked sanctions from governmental agencies and crippled consumer trust in several institutions (Eisenbeiss, 2012; Green & Odom, 2003; Thompson et al., 2010).

The growing conception and the surge in the necessity for an effective and efficient form of leadership has over the years become a concern for various organisational bodies in public, private and hybrid industries. In essence, the concept of leadership plays a key driving force in terms of organisational effectiveness, employee motivation and overall long-term sustainability and growth (Yukl, 2008; Xiaomeng & Barto, 2010; Louise & Benn, 2013). The lack of

effective, efficient and morally sound leaders with principles of strong ethical core beliefs have driven several industries, institutions into disrepute (Knights & Majella, 2005; Thompson et al., 2010). The necessity for ethics as a core value plays a critical role in the establishment and a general understanding of leadership (Cuilla, 2004). There is an increasing realization today that organisational leaders need to be subtler to their moral obligations to the larger society, which includes all their stakeholders such as consumers, employees, suppliers, governments and local communities (Mendonca, 2001).

Copeland (2015) posits the call for a growing need and resurgence of an ethic-based form of leadership within organisations is as a result of challenges facing people within the spectrum of power in adhering to the ethical structures and guidelines set to provide an ethical climate with organisations. In recent times, individuals in top management positions who are seen to be ethical and law abiding are at the fore front of carrying out unethical behaviours within organisations (Copeland, 2015; Ciulla, 2004). Furthermore, a lack of ethical behaviour within organisations and the absence of ethical climate to foster core ethical values and drive employee effectiveness, employee's voice and ethical behaviours has led to a clarion call for the need for ethical leadership within the leadership field (Combo, 2009; Ciulla, 2004; Copeland, 2015; Derr, 2012).

Ethical leadership is not relatively new within the field of leadership. The earliest identified conceptualisation of ethical leadership can be attributed to Enderle (1987). Several scholarly works over the last 30 years in literature have advanced the field of ethical leadership to various perspectives such as the attributes of an ethical leader and the behaviours. Furthermore, it has been stated that the concept of ethical leadership consists of two pillars, namely, the moral person and moral management (Trevino et al., 2003; Brown et al., 2005). Some scholarly works in the field have examined ethical leadership from the entrepreneurial perspective (Eisenbeiss, 2012). However, despite studies on ethical leadership, empirical research on the definition

remains limited (Toor & Ofori, 2009). A conceptualisation and definition of ethical leadership have been provided in recent years (Brown et al. 2005). Scholars over the years have called for a clearer conceptualisation of ethical leadership due to its ambiguous nature (Price, 2017; Eisenbeiss, 2012; Voegtlin, 2016). Whilst there are several advancements in the field of ethical leadership in six major perspectives, namely, the identity, followers, performance, sectors behavioural and demographic perspective, there exist avenues for development and further exploration due to the nascent state within literature.

This thesis aims to contribute to the further development of ethical leadership by exploring the Nigerian perspective and identifying the skills perspective of ethical leaders in the Nigerian public sector. Leadership challenges facing Nigeria is not relatively new. Several studies within the body of literature have asserted the issue facing Nigeria can be ascribed to a downward spiral in effective ethical frameworks, structures and the problem within the Nigerian context traced to the pre-independence era (Amakom, 2008; Enweremadu & Okafor, 2009). Furthermore, some school of thought have described leadership issue as an African problem with most stemming from lack of systems, skills, knowledge or developmental infrastructure to foster effective ethical leadership development within the continent. Due to these shortcomings in fostering and implementing effective leadership structures mostly in public sector organisation, several major scandals have affected major organisations within the Nigeria perspective most especially from the leadership standpoint. A good example in recent years within the Nigerian public sector can be seen within the Nigeria National petroleum corporation (NNPC) where a former group managing director (GMD) was involved in corrupt practices such as embezzlement. Furthermore, there exists a growing problem facing leadership in various institutions in Nigeria in the aspect of accountability, integrity and avenue for ethical culture development.

There exists limited empirical research on the skills perspective of ethical leadership. Although, studies have focused on ethical leadership conceptualisation and operationalisation from the private and hybrid settings, there appears to be limited empirical research focused on the skills perspective and influence on ethical leadership antecedents and outcomes regarding employee and organisational performance. From the demographical aspect of studies conducted in the field of ethical leadership, strong focus has been placed specifically from the Western and Eastern perspective of ethical values, norms, culture, and its impact on leadership. There exists a vast gap within the research community and scarcity of empirical studies in relation to ethical leadership from the Sub-Saharan region. **The sub-Saharan region can be classified as the most populous black demography in the world. Whilst several studies have explored the concept of ethical leadership from various demographical perspective, there is a shortage of empirical studies from this demography. Sub-Saharan region proffer a basis for understanding ethical leadership and proffer a platform for future study to understand leadership development. Several literature studies have examined the understanding of leadership from this sector (Ogunfowora et al., 2014; Harrison et al., 2018). While these studies have provided some understanding on some aspect of leadership, there exist limited literature addressing the ethical challenges facing operationalisation of leadership in every facet of life within the sub-Saharan context.**

1.2. Scope

This study explores the skills perspective of ethical leadership required within the Nigerian public sector, which is a developing world context. While there exists extensive works within the body of ethical leadership literature, studies have majorly focused on one demographical aspect (Eisenbeiss, 2012). Empirical works carried out have focused solely on the western aspect of an ethical leader (Eisenbeiss, 2012; Khuntia, et al., 2004). Furthermore, there exists a vast gap within the research community and scarcity of empirical studies in relation to ethical

leadership from the developing world perspective. While the scope of empirical research is centred around understanding ethical leadership from a western orientation, there are limited literature exploring the influence of ethical leadership from the African perspective. Furthermore, the centrality of works in literature have provided empirical findings from the private sector perspective, with limited works exploring the public sector. The research aims to examine the concept of ethical leadership from the context of the Nigerian public sector.

The Nigeria public sector can be described as one of the key sectors in the growth and development of the country as a whole. Furthermore as a driver of employment, cohesion and a great source for revenue generation, the importance of this sector plays a key role very aspect of the economy.

In Nigeria, the public sector can be described as one of the major drivers for Nigeria's economic growth and development. It provides the major contribution to the economy in terms of employment opportunities and avenues for development (Edo & Ikelegbe, 2014; Orukpe & Omoruyi, 2017). This sector functions as a medium for public services that include revenue generation, management, political and social service delivery to the people and monitoring and implementation of policies (Eliogu-Anenih, 2017; Imhonopi & Ugochukwu, 2013). While the sector provides an avenue for development, it has faced a downward spiral because of corruption and mainly due to ineffective leadership. This can be ascribed to the absence of ethics and accountability (Fatile, 2013). Which is attributed mainly due to lack of ethical leaders within the public sector to foster ethical behaviours, employee commitment and performance. There exists a shortage of leadership skills within the public sector to drive ethicality in the Nigerian public sector (Iheduru, 2016; Opara, 2014; Ogbewere, 2015). Some school of thought attribute this shortages to some core factors within the Nigerian public sector ranging from lack of infrastructures to foster ethic-based leadership development and culture of corruption in leadership stemming back to the pre-independence era of the country

(Akanmidu, 2014; Amakom, 2008; Edo & Ikelegbe, 2014). Fatile (2013) asserts a growing challenge facing the public sector consist of a plethora public sector leaders disregarding ethic-based framework for leadership, leadership development and a lack of accountability from both people in power and surbordinates. This study aims to provide an ethical leadership skills framework for the Nigerian public sector.

1.3. Research Aim

The aim of this study is to examine the concept of ethical leadership and to explore the skills perspective in ethical leadership development for improving performance within the Nigeran public sector.

1.4. Research Objectives

To accomplish the aim of this study, the following objectives provided guided the course of this research. These are:

- To examine the current conceptualisation of ethical leadership.
- To identify the ethic-based challenges facing leaders within the Nigerian public sector.
- To provide a skill-based ethical leadership framework within the Nigerian public sector.
- To investigate the influence of ethical leadership skills on performance in the Nigerian public sector.

1.5. Research Questions

To ensure the purpose and the objectives of this study were actualised, key questions were provided to guide the research study and to provide quality findings and answers to the problem definition. These questions are:

- **What is ethical leadership?**
- What are the required skills necessary for an effective ethical leader?
- What are the perspectives adopted in literature in examination of ethical leadership?

- What are the hinderances and limitations to the implementation of an ethical leadership framework?
- How does ethical leadership influence performance within an organisation?

1.6. Research Methodology

The research methodology of this study was justified and informed by its aim, objectives, and questions as the most suitable method to achieve the goals of the study. The researcher was guided by an interpretivist philosophy which provides a deeper understanding and investigates the personal views, opinions and ideas of participants, which cannot be attained from other forms of research philosophy. This philosophy and research paradigm is concerned with the exclusivity of a specific situation, contributing to the underlying pursuit of contextual depth. (Myers, 1999; Chowdhury, 2014). An inductive approach to research was adopted for this study, as this provides the avenue for the researcher to garner quality information from the human context. This approach draws from the acquired information to garner a better picture of the phenomenon of the role of skills and its influence on performance. The inductive approach to research can be elucidated as the process for providing qualitative analysis in which the analysis of the data acquired is guided by specific evaluation criteria (Thomas, 2006). A qualitative method of research was utilised in this study. This was informed by the research aim and the interpretivist standpoint. Which provides better insight into the world of leaders in the public sector and acquires rich information that cannot be obtained through the quantitative method. The data was collected through semi-structured interviews. 25 interviews were conducted. A thematic analysis was adopted to analyse the data collected through the interviews.

1.7. Originality and Contribution to Knowledge

1.7.1. Originality

Before the commencement of this research study, consideration and emphasis should be placed on the values and its contribution to the body of knowledge. Several scholars within literature have asserted this aspect to originality as a form of contribution (Phillips & Pugh, 1994; Guetzkow et al., 2004). Guetzkow et al. (2004) provides different variations to the definition and assessment of originality from various disciplinary clusters within literature. The authors assert the ideas of originality types in literature in the form of approach, data, theory, topic, method, outcome and understudied areas. Phillips & Pugh (1994) provides 15 different aspects to originality that can be exemplified.

This research proposes an original contribution which satisfies Philip & Pugh (1994) and Guetzkow et al. (2004) justification on the concept of originality. Adopting Philip & Pugh (1994) criteria for justification, this research contributes to literature satisfying (7) carrying out empirical work that hasn't been done before, (11) taking a particular technique and applying it in a new area, (14) looking at areas that people in the discipline haven't looked at before (15) adding to knowledge in a way that hasn't been done before. These justifications are discussed below.

Carrying out empirical work that hasn't been done before

Whilst the skills perspective of leadership within literature is not relatively new, with several scholarly studies providing advancement in understanding leadership effectiveness (Katz, 1955; Katz, 1974; Mumford, 1986; Mumford et al., 2000; Mumford et al., 2007; Harrison, 2018). This study provides an empirical contribution to ethical leadership literature in the development of skills necessary for ethical leadership operationalisation. Extant literature in ethical leadership have majorly examined ethical leadership from the behavioural perspective.

Taking a particular technique and applying it in a new area

Whilst there are several key advancements in the field of ethical leadership with most body of work adopting quantitative approach to research, there exist substantial studies adopting a qualitative methodology in ethical leadership literature, limited studies in the field have explored the Nigerian context (developing world perspective). A semi-structured interview qualitative research methodology is adopted in the Nigerian context. In this regard, this can be considered an application of a well-known technique or method and applying it in a new area within ethical leadership literature (Phillips & Pugh, 1994; Guetzkow et al., 2004).

Looking at areas that people in the discipline haven't looked at before

The field of ethical leadership within the body of literature in the last three decades has provided various understanding and advancement to the development and operationalisation from an attribute perspective and from a behavioural point of view (Kalshoven et al., 2011; Walumbwa & Schaubroeck, 2009; Emery, 2016; Hoogervorst, 2011; Brown et al., 2005; Zhu et al., 2004; Bouckennooghe et al., 2015; Bormann, 2017). However, minimal recognition and focus have been placed on the skills perspective within the field. This study provides a skills perspective to the enhancement of ethical leadership. Furthermore, this study provides a skills definition to the conceptualisation and operationalisation.

Adding to knowledge in a way that hasn't been done before

Majority of studies on ethical leadership have focused on the Western, Eastern and Asian perspective in terms of demography study. Whilst focus have been placed within these regions in literature, there exist an absence of empirical research within the public sector context within Nigeria and the developing world. This study adds to knowledge by addressing the public sector context within Nigeria in the field.

1.7.2. Contribution to Knowledge

1.7.2.1. Demographical Contribution

This study explored the concept of ethical leadership from the Nigeria public sector context. This was informed by the outcome of the systematic literature review (SLR). Findings from the field have highlighted the limited empirical studies from the developing world. Furthermore, from a sector perspective, focus was placed on public sector organisations.

1.7.2.2. Empirical Contribution

Through empirical research, a skills-based framework of ethical leadership in the Nigerian public sector has been developed and presented. It depicts the skills required for ethical leadership in the Nigerian public sector to meet the ethic-based challenges and to foster employee commitment and performance. Furthermore, ethical based challenges were identified from the findings.

1.7.2.3. Theoretical Contribution

This study presents a theoretical contribution to the study of ethical leadership, informed by the findings in the field. It proffers a skills-based definition of ethical leadership from the context of the Nigerian public sector. This skills-based definition depicts the mechanism for fostering normative approach behaviours on subordinates.

1.7.2.4. Methodological Contribution

This study adopts a systematic literature review in the advancement and exploration of the field of ethical leadership. Whilst this has been adopted in other leadership approaches such as entrepreneurial leadership, the study is the first to adopt this systematic approach to literature review, which involves a replicable, rigorous and unbiased research method of existing literature in the field. The SLR provided an unbiased assessment of literature consisting of a qualitative and quantitative report. While this is not new in the field of leadership, it is new in the field of ethical leadership. The systematic review of literature provides a thematic analysis of literature works to identify themes within the body of literature.

1.8. Thesis Structure

This thesis is made up of nine chapters.

The first chapter is the introduction chapter, A research background is presented which provides the rationale of this thesis. The research aim, objectives and research questions are also presented. Methodological overview of the research is presented in this chapter and later discussed in detail in chapter six. Contributions to study are also provided within this chapter.

Chapter two provides a detailed examination of the conceptualisation of ethics within the body of literature. It examines the definition of ethics in the body of literature and how it shapes an understanding of morality. Exploration of ethical theories and the relation to leadership were presented in this chapter. Chapter three provides a review of literature on leadership, exploring the different theories and era of leadership in literature. Chapter four explores Nigeria and the public sector. Addressing the economy of Nigeria and the challenges facing the Nigerian public sector. Chapter five presents the systematic literature review highlighting the quantitative and qualitative findings in the field of ethical leadership.

Chapter six presents the research methodology. In this chapter, detailed discussion of methodological choices is made. Data analysis and other processes are presented along with the ethical considerations made.

Chapter seven provides the findings from the field. These findings are derived through the qualitative method of research. The chapter provides the skills and the challenges facing ethical leaders in the public sector. Furthermore, findings also presented participants perspective on the conceptualisation of ethical leadership.

Chapter eight provides a discussion of research findings with reference to existing literature. A skills-based framework is presented in this chapter. A proposed definition of ethical leadership is presented based on findings.

Chapter nine provides a detailed summary of this research, which includes findings of the study, limitations and future research. The contribution to knowledge is also presented in this chapter.

CHAPTER TWO: ETHICS

2.0. Introduction

This chapter provides a detailed examination of the conceptualisation of ethics within the body of literature and thorough examination of the concept of ethics and how it relates to understanding an individual's behaviour within the context of this study. The first section provides a discussion of the current definition of ethics from literature and how it shapes an understanding of morality. The second, provides the two major variation of ethics within the body of literature namely the teleological theory of ethics and the deontological theory of ethics. The third, a detailed understanding of the teleological theory of ethics, the different variations of the teleological theory namely, the utilitarianism and ethical egoism perspective. Deontological perspective of ethics will be discussed within this chapter, addressing the rule-based and act-based deontology. The chapter further explores the concept of virtue ethics and its relationship to current ethical leadership literature. Pluralism and contractarianism theory of ethics are also discussed. The final aspect of the chapter addresses the concept of ethics within leadership.

2.1. Ethics as a Concept

In everyday life, guidance of individuals is governed by principles and values to portray and act in terms of goodwill to others based on universal laws. The concept of ethics in literature can be considered as one of the most researched fields in management, leadership and even within the science field. Several schools of thought have proposed different definitions and theories to aid an understanding of what ethics means within everyday life. Fatile (2013) elucidate that the word 'ethics' originates from the Greek *ethos* which means "character". In essence, some schools of thought have stipulated that the term character may have a different perspective and can be interpreted broadly (Fatile, 2013). There exists no consensus within the

body of literature as to the exact nature and scope of ethics, and a general definition on what ethics entails is rather broad. (Fatile, 2013; Lillie, 2003).

The earliest known conceptualisation and definition of ethics can be traced back to early Greek philosophers, Plato and Aristotle. Drawing from their school of thought, (Fatile, 2013; Freakley & Burgh, 2000) posits the concept of ethics as ‘what we ought to do’. Fatile (2013) suggests this requires an individual’s reasoning and judgement in decision making that raises the question regarding what can be considered fair and just, good or bad, right and wrong. Garnett (1951) addresses the challenges facing the definition of ethics between naturalistic and non-naturalistic ethics, drawing from the standpoint of ethics as “what we ought to do”. It can be considered as an “obligation” or “duty”. Garnett (1951) provides a distinction in the definition of ethics from different theoretical possibilities highlighting five possible meaning from the combination of three distinction. Ethics can be described or agreed as subjectively right actions and the characters that produces these actions which constitutes moral good, particular intrinsic natural good, general intrinsic natural good and general instrumental natural good (Garnett, 1951). Consensus places the concept of ethics as the moral principles that oversees a person’s behaviour or the conducting of an activity. Ethics can also be regarded as morality and used interchangeably with altruism (Kamlesh, 1999). This involves carrying out morally good acts that comprises universal morals laws and principles, namely, strong values, honesty, integrity and justice (Kamlesh, 1999). Ethics can be considered as essentially the study of standards and determining what behaviours are good or bad, right or wrong (Aronson, 2001).

Thiroux & Krasemann (1980) suggest this concept involves seeking wisdom by enquiring about right and wrong, good and bad. It is the normative science of the conduct of individuals within societal boundaries which judges these conducts to be good or bad, right or wrong or in some similar way (Lillie, 2003). This involves treating people the way one will want to be treated (Banerjee & Ercetin, 2012). Okediji (1981) elucidates that the concept of ethics refers

to the code of conduct of individuals in specific and diverse situations of their life. In essence, the ability to conduct oneself in terms of behaviour and attitude by differentiating between what is right or wrong, good and bad when accomplishing a task or an activity (Kamlesh, 1999; Thiroux & Krasemann, 1980). Ethics can be considered as a philosophical branch that is involved in understanding the human values in a systematic, coherent and scientific manner (Fatile, 2013; Thiroux & Krasemann, 1980). Giving clarity to this understanding, ethics can be considered as a moral science or the characterisation of conducts and behaviours that is adjudged right or wrong, good or bad.

Davidson (1988) emphasises ethics involves two things namely, (1) an investigation into the constitution and nature of human character, (2) the formulation and enunciation of rules for human conduct. The first aspect involves the theoretical ethics, and the second aspect involves the practical aspect of ethics. As Davidson (1988) posits these two aspects of ethics work simultaneously, as the practical aspect of ethics is necessarily dependent on the theoretical. In retrospect, ethics rests on a well-considered investigation and analysis of an individual's moral and mental nature, as well as that of one's social conditions. From a scientific perspective, this can be described as the science of human conduct and human character as "they ought to be", based on the knowledge of what human conduct and human character "have been and are" (Davidson, 1988).

In essence, this involves the science of an individual's view on conduct. Chandler & Plano (1982) defines ethics as the rules or standards governing the moral conducts of a member of an organisation. This can be described as the rules, code of conduct guiding and governing the way organisation procedures are carried out from the subordinate to the management level within the organisation. While Lillie (2003) proffers a scientific point of view, Inal (1996) suggests the concept of ethics as a philosophical discipline which investigates the societal and personal relationships that defines the constructs of people's values, norms, rules, good or bad

morally or good and bad. Some schools of thought have stipulated understanding ethics as a concept which stems from what can be defined as a moral problem in a given context or situation (Garnett, 1951; Davidson, 1988; Morris, 2004). Morris (2004) definition of a moral problem requires two simultaneous operations namely, what problem can be considered as a moral problem and what cannot be classified as a moral problem. In essence, a moral problem can be considered as something (potentially) arising in every decision, to an extent that individuals can recognise generalisable class of actions that individuals or a group of people find unsatisfactory in situations (Morris, 2004). This can be considered as a class of action within any given situation that goes against the norms, codes and conduct and is deemed as unsatisfactory in that given scenario.

Drawing from these definitions, it is highly evident that ethics possess a strong link with morality. It is based on how an individual positions oneself within societal enclaves and acts based on ones underlining understanding of values, rules, norms and what is right and wrong (Kamlesh, 1999; Thiroux & Krasemann, 1980; Copp, 2006; Banerjee & Ercetin, 2012; Inal, 1996; Kamlesh, 1999). Understanding the concept of ethics can be explored in diverse spheres of literature and in the world in general. Some school of thought explores the phenomenon of this concept from the scientific and normative viewpoints (Copp, 2006; Davidson, 1988; Garnett, 1951). The inculcation of ethics constructs and application plays pivotal roles in the structure, daily guidance and ways individuals and organisations carry out their day-to-day activities. In essence, the conceptualisation of ethics in everyday life is guided by an individual or groups categorisation of a moral problem within a given scenario or situation. Several postulations and understanding of ethics can be categorised into various theories within the body of literature. To proffer a better meaning of this phenomenon, this is categorised into various dynamics (Banerjee & Ercetin, 2012; Morrision, 2001). These are the teleological

theory of ethics, the deontological theory of ethics, contractarianism, virtue ethics and pluralism.

2.2. Teleological Theory of Ethics

Teleological as the name implies, originates from the Greek word “telos” which means “an end” (Bauamane-Vitolina, et al., 2015). This theory can be considered as a particular kind of axiological theory, as scholars have disagreed on the exact defining characteristics of this perspective of ethics (Vallentyne, 1987). Teleological perspective for what is considered ethically right is the non-moral value that is created (Aronson, 2001; Frankena, 1973). Aronson (2001) elucidates that an act can be considered moral if it is judged to produce a greater degree of good than the alternatives provided, and it is considered immoral if the degree of good is lesser than the alternative. In essence, the understanding of the teleological perspective of ethics in this case is that non moral pertains to the absence of an ethical or moral issue in determining the values. Helms & Hutchins (1992) suggest that the teleological aspect of ethics stresses the outcome of a situation, as opposed to the intent of the individual behaviour.

Teleological ethics can also be described as consequentialist ethics. It is the theory of morality that draws moral duties or obligations from what is good or desirable as an end to be attained (Benlahcene, et al., 2018). This indicates that an act is considered morally right if it produces a higher level of good over evil than any other acts considered, and it is morally wrong if it does the opposite (Benlahcene et al., 2018; Helms & Hutchins, 1992). Teleological theories accept utility as the basis of understanding morality (Helms & Hutchins, 1992). It is based on the assumption that a decision behind a particular conduct has to be centred on the assessment of the respective outcome (Bauamane-Vitolina, et al., 2015).

Teleological moral theories identify goodness in the consequences of an individual’s behaviour and not the behaviour itself. White (2007) elucidates that according to teleological moral

theory, all rational individuals are teleological in the sense that we think about the means in achieving certain ends. The concept of moral behaviours within this perspective of ethics can be considered goal directed. From a teleological point of view, the understanding of human behaviour is neither right nor wrong. What is considered important is what happens as the consequence of these actions in any given situation or context (White, 2007; Helms & Hutchins, 1992). In essence, a teleological perspective theory of ethics refers to the contextualisation of consequences that makes an individual's behaviour, good or bad, right or wrong.

The concept of teleology suggests as individuals we possess one major basic duty, to adopt whatever possibilities that maximises the best possible alternative or outcome (Bauamane-Vitolina et al., 2015). Within the body of literature as regards ethics, effectiveness and leadership, Ciulla (2009) posits the parallels between the perspective of these theories in ethics. Teleological perspective differs from the deontological perspective of ethics from a leadership standpoint. For the teleological perspective, what is important is the leader's actions and results in bringing about the morally good or the greatest good, whereas for the deontological perspective, intentions are the morally relevant aspect of the act. This suggests as long as the leader acts in accordance with their duty or on moral principles then the leader is considered to have acted ethically irrespective of the consequences. Furthermore, teleological theory locates the ethics of the action in a leader's result while deontological theories locate the ethics of a leader's action in the moral intent and the moral justification for the action (Ciulla, 2009).

Scholars have theorized the variation of teleological or consequentialist form of ethics (Aronson, 2001; Copp, 2006; Audi, 2007; Benlahcene et al., 2018). These include utilitarianism and ethical egoism (Vallentyne, 1987; Audi, 2007; Dion, 2012; Bentham, 1982)

2.2.1. Utilitarianism

Utilitarianism is commonly defined in very different ways. Audi (2007) suggests there exist a wide agreement on utilitarianism as it mandates maximising some form of good. Utilitarianism stems from the word “utility” which means useful and deals with the promotion of the greatest balance of good over evil (Udofia, 2017). Utilitarianism can be described as an ethical theory to which the rightness and wrongness of acts is dependent entirely on facts about overall well-being (Eggleston, 2012). This involves the maximisation of the expected usefulness for all elements affected by an action or by a decision taking. It can be seen as a movement for political, legal and social reforms that flourished in the first part of the Ninetieth century, an ideology of movement (Quinton, 1973). In relation to the concept of ethics, it involves the provision of a criterion for distinguishing between what is regarded as right and wrong actions and by implication, an account by nature of moral judgements that characterise action as right and wrong (Quinton, 1973; Eggleston, 2012).

Bentham (1982) suggests that the principle of utilitarianism reveals that an action is morally right when it promotes the greatest wellbeing or happiness of as much people as possible. This suggests that utilitarianism implies the ability and trend to produce advantage, benefits, pleasures or happiness rather than unhappiness and pain for majority of people who are affected directly by a given decision (Dion, 2012). It involves the maximisation of goodness within society by measuring the probable consequences or outcome, the communal utilitarian principle of the greatest balance between good and evil (Knights & Majella, 2006). In utilitarianism, pleasure in itself is considered good while pain is in itself evil (Bentham, 1982; Knights & Majella, 2005; Dion, 2012). This form of ethics characterises right acts as those that achieve the greatest form of good for the greatest number (Audi, 2007). Some school of thought suggests the possibility of quantification and measurement of the quantitative aspect of an

individual's happiness (benefits/pleasure) or one's unhappiness (damages/pain) and thus it is possible to identify the resulting level of happiness/unhappiness (Bentham, 1982; Dion, 2012).

Quinton (1973) posits that utilitarianism consist of a combination of two principles. Firstly, "the consequentialist principles" that an action is considered either right or wrong by the outcome of the goodness or badness of the result that comes from it. Secondly, the "hedonist principle" which emphasises two viewpoints that what is deemed to be good itself is pleasure and what is deemed bad is pain. Knights & Majella (2006) elucidates the issues of utilitarianist principles highlighting the problematic nature of the first principle as it deals with a simple linear relationship between a moral act and its consequences while the hedonistic theory or principle is tautological in that the painful and pleasurable consequences (responses) are not independent of the ethical act (stimulus) that are deemed to be their cause. Utilitarian ethics are concerned with the outcomes. Individual or group actions are considered as ethical if the net benefit resulting from these actions is greater than the possible alternatives, thus creating the maximum social good (Beekun et al., 2010; Schimke et al., 2003; Velasquez, 1992).

Gillon (1985) reiterating this theory of ethics provides four major advantages to other forms of moral theories namely, (1) the reliance on moral intuitions to identify moral principles notwithstanding the unreliability and variability of these intuition, (2) the pluralism of many deontological theories, whose moral ideas and principles may conflict, (3) the lack of a consistent and reliable decision procedure for choosing the right course of action in a particular situation and (4) the absolutism of more than one principle in some pluralist theories. In essence if these principles apply without any exception, they must be irreconcilable. While Gillon (1985) highlights the benefits of utilities, Dion (2012) emphasises the difficulty and practicality of adopting this theory in real life. Although, the definition wholly involves the essence of an individual's happiness as the inculcation of more pleasure than pain, the problem lies in the assessment of such pains and pleasure. In most cases, one can only reach a qualitative rather

than the quantitative evaluation of the effects of these pleasure and pain on those who are solely affected by the decision given. While utilitarianism enhances somewhat level of objective assessment of pleasures and pain, it cannot guarantee such pure objectivity (Dion, 2012).

Audi (2007) suggests another problem facing utilitarianism is the clarification of what can be considered good, what can be defined pleasure and what can be defined as pain. In terms of clarification, can pleasure be partly sensory in nature, and does pain surmount to embarrassment or shame in the context of pleasure and pain? Audi (2007) also iterate the measurement problem facing this theory of ethics, stating that the difficulty is partly empirical in nature. They state that in measuring this form of ethics, duration of experience of an individual is quantitatively measurable, but the intensity cannot be accurately measured. Utilitarianism requires interpersonal comparison of pain and pleasure as a basis of ethical decision. Furthermore, for utilitarianism, pleasure and pain is central and play both positive and negative roles in all major ethical views compared to other forms such as virtue ethics.

In adaptation to the leadership construct, a leader with an utilitarian viewpoint's action is obligatory if and only if its consequences have greater utility than those of any other action available to the individual. (Copp, 2006). Udofia (2017) elucidates utilitarianism conceived as a normative principle within the body of leadership, as an effort to provide an answer to the practice question "what should a leader do?". This draws back to Garnett (1951) standpoint on the definition of the concept of ethics. In understanding the question, a leader ought to demonstrate or act in ways to promote the greatest balance of pleasure over pain.

In essence, utilitarianism as an ethical cum leadership theory becomes the promotion of the balance between what is considered pleasure over what is considered pain (Udofia, 2017). Furthermore, the consequentialist leadership philosophy focuses on the personal and general utility of the outcomes of a leader's action with the view that an individual should pursue

interests that proffers pleasure to the individual at the expense and detriment of others. In essence, utilitarians are of the viewpoint that it is possible for a right thing to be done from a bad motive (Udofia, 2017; Garnett, 1951).

Within the leadership theory, several scholars have argued that utilitarianism is associated with transactional leadership (Kanungo, 2001; Mendonca, 2001; Bass & Steidlmeier, 1999). Groves & LaRocca (2011) posit utilitarian values take the form of either acts or rule-based utilitarianism. Utilitarianist individuals base their decisions solely on their outcome by selecting the act that proffers the greatest social good while rule utilitarianism proposes that individual's actions are solely judged ethical depending on whether they follow certain rules under which the action falls (Groves & LaRocca, 2011). Consequently, utilitarianism generally leads to the least ethical intent across business ethics vignette (Groves & LaRocca, 2011; Kanungo, 2001; Mendonca, 2001; Bass & Steidlmeier, 1999).

In summary, utilitarianism is associated with the rightness of one's action being determined by its contribution to the happiness of people affected by it. By drawing on the assumption that an individual's action is deemed morally appropriate if its towards a greater cause or has overall positive impact on a group of individuals (Bentham, 1982; Knights & Majella, 2005; Dion, 2012). Some scholars have emphasised concerns on the definition of utilitarianism from the viewpoint of what can be considered as pleasure and what can be considered as pain. In practicality, it is difficult to ascertain what behaviours, actions can be considered to be pleasure or pain and to what degree these values can be measured (Audi, 2007; Ross, 1930; Aristotle, 2002; Swanton, 2003; Audi, 2004; Udofia, 2017).

2.2.2. Ethical Egoism

Rachels (1961) submits ethical egoism is the radical view that an individual's only duty is to promotes oneself interest. In conceptualisation, there exist only one ultimate principle of

conduct, the principle of self-interest, and this principle involves all of one's natural obligations and duties. Shaver (2002) suggests that ethical egoism gives claim that an individual ought to perform an action if and only if, that action maximises one's self-interest. This viewpoint is also shared by Kalin (1975) who iterates the concept of ethical egoism as the position one ought, with all things considered, to do an action if and only if that action is in the overall self-interest of that said person. Outside the teleological perspective of utilitarianism, ethical egoism has been the most widely discussed substantive ethical position in literature in recent years (Machan, 1979).

Scholars have argued that the concept of egoism can be considered a legitimate ethical theory (Brunton, 1956; Machan, 1979). Brunton (1956) is of the viewpoint that it is not universalizable. The author suggests that egoism is just as sensitive to the distinction between oneself and others. Egoist scholars have elucidated that altruism as a form of an individual's character is practically unfeasible and argues that the understanding of the concept is self-defeating (Brunton, 1956; Machan, 1979; Rachels, 1961).

In essence, ethical egoism from an ethics definitive point posits that an individual ought to do and only do what it is in the person's best interest over a long period of time; and whether a situation is in an individual's best interest over that stipulated period of time is what makes it the morally right or wrong thing for one to do. Some have argued from the standpoint of human behaviour that individuals who are supposedly altruistic can be egoist in nature, as the true definition of altruism involves an individual sacrificing oneself for the benefit of others (Shaver, 2002). In essence, self-sacrifice can stem out of an ulterior motive to get others to do something or carry out a task for one in the long term (Machan, 1979).

2.3. Deontological Theory of Ethics

Deontological theory of ethics can be described as a duty-based theory (Benlahcene et al., 2018). The concept of the word “Deon” originates from the Greek word which means “duty”. Several scholars have elucidated that deontological theory of ethics entails the nature of the action of an individual itself and also the motive of this said action in order to justify if it is right or wrong (Aronson, 2001; Benlahcene et al., 2018; Copp, 2006). Deontological theory of ethics locates the ethics of action in the moral intent of an individual and the moral justification of that action (Cuilla, 2004). A direct opposite of the understanding of teleological perspective of ethics, this form of ethics can be defined as a non-consequentialist form of ethics within the body of literature.

Copp (2006) posits deontological theories are those that take the basic matter of moral concerns and the fundamental truths to be correct about our duties or action. In contrast to the concept of utilitarianism, consequences do not matter or is not a deciding factor to which act is morally right. It is the rules that determine what motive to act from and what action you should make (i.e., what a leader’s ethical duty is within a situation) (Bauamane-Vitolina et al., 2015; Benlahcene et al., 2018).

Deontology theory of ethics can also be described as the theory of moral obligation, and it states that what can be considered as morally right is not dependent upon generating or producing the greatest level of good as opposed to evil but rather determined by the characteristics of an individual’s normative behaviour (Frankena, 1973; Aronson, 2001). There are several scholars who disagree with the notion of the entire teleological agenda by arguing that moral goodness has nothing to do with generating pleasure, happiness, and or consequences (White, 2007). Deontological theories are duty-based in nature (Audi, 2007; White, 2007). In essence, morality, according to deontologists, consists in the fulfilment of

moral obligations or duties. Duties, in the deontological tradition, are most often associated with obeying absolute moral rules (Audi, 2004; Benlahcene et al., 2018).

Deontological theories seem to contradict basic principles of Homo Oeconomicus in the sense that motives behind human conduct are based on an attempt to maximise benefit (Bauamane-Vitolina, et al., 2015). One can stipulate the concept of deontological principles as the golden rule prevailing in many world's religions: "Do unto others as you would have them do unto you" (Bauamane-Vitolina et al., 2015; Benlahcene et al., 2018, p.34). Deontological theories' scholars trust that categorical imperatives are grounded on the choice of rational humans, though this rationality differs from utilitarianism rationality. The basic principle of deontological theory involves an individual behaving in a way that everyone wants to follow, for it would promote the entire society's welfare (Cuilla, 2004; Bauamane-Vitolina et al., 2015).

Vallentyne (1987) posits the characterisation of deontological theories as theories that are not teleological in nature. In essence, this theory of ethics or the nature of deontological ethics depends on the characterisation of teleological theories. Some scholarly works have attributed the understanding of the theory being central to rule-based motives, assess the permissibility of one's actions in terms of whether they conform to the laid down rules and regulations (Vallentyne, 1987).

There exists a difference between the two forms of theories of ethics, as Vallentyne (1987) elucidates, the divide lies in the kinds of rules that they evoke. In a similar context, it is sometimes claimed that deontological theories, or at least one type thereof, are absolutist in that they suggest that there are certain kinds of actions that are obligatory or forbidden (Bentham, 1982; Vallentyne, 1987; Copp, 2006). Helms & Hutchins (1992) asserts that deontological theory considers the moral value of a behaviour to be independent of the outcome

since the certainty of these outcomes is questionable at the moment of the decision's act. A deontological evaluation process revolves on the inherent rightness versus wrongness of a behaviour, irrespective of the consequences of that action. At the centre of a deontological evaluation process are principles of justice, basic rights, duties, obligations, responsibilities, proper conduct, and inherent natural rights of others (Ishmael, 1997; Aronson, 2001).

A closely related characterisation of deontological theories of ethics is theories for which there are certain kinds of actions that are always (or never) forbidden, where whether or not a given action is of the specified kind does not depend on what is the outcome of the action (Vallentyne, 1987). Morality is centred on whether acts conflict with moral rules or not, and the motivation behind those acts. An act or behaviour is considered good if and only if it was performed out of a desire to do one's duty and obey a rule. In other words, act out of a good will (White, 2007). The major challenge or problem arising here is: *"How does one distinguish absolute moral rules from mere convention, prudence, or legality, without reference to the distribution of pleasure and pain?"* (White, 2007). In the Western perspective, there have been two approaches to the establishment of deontological principles namely, divine command theory and Kantian theory (White, 2007). Furthermore, there are two main categories of deontological theory of ethics within the body of literature. These are the rule deontology and the act-based deontology (Aronson, 2001; Vallentyne, 1987).

According to Aronson (2001), rule-based deontological theory of ethics stipulates that in all situation or circumstance, individuals should follow a set of predetermined standard or rules, so that behaviours can be considered ethical or unethical not as a consequence of one's action but as compared to the laid down standard or guidelines stated. In essence, rule-based deontology is guided by the stipulated standards set by an organisation or what is considered the norm within the organisation. Therefore, ethical judgement of a given situation is solely based on the general principles, and the overall standard is either composed of a series of more

specific guidelines, with each specifying how individuals within an organisation should act or behave in a certain manner according to a given set of conditions (Frankena, 1973; Aronson, 2001).

Act-based deontological perspective of ethics stipulates that people act or behave ethically in accordance with the norms, but is limited to a particular set of behaviours, implying that there may be some exceptions to the rules stated (Aronson, 2001). Individuals are obligated to behave toward others in a specific manner purely because they are human. There is an obligation to consider their rights and dignity regardless of the consequences, so that the concern is for the moral value inherent in the action itself (White, 2007; Aronson, 2001).

2.4. Virtue Ethics

Virtue ethics can be considered an umbrella term, covering a series of different theories and claims, which have background in the works of many different philosophers, from the likes of Plato and Aristotle to Hume, to Nietzsche and beyond (Athanasoulis, 2012). Virtue-based ethics also known as “Aretaic” originates from Greek and can be translated as “excellence or virtue” in which morality is internal and the key to an individual’s good lies not in the rules or rights, but in the classic notion of character such as honesty, fairness, compassion, and generosity (Knights & Majella, 2006). MacIntyre (1981) elucidates the concept of virtue as those qualities which enables an individual to achieve eudaimonia and the lack of which frustrate his/her movement toward that telos. Hackett & Wang (2012) elucidates the disparity in the definition of virtue from a leadership standpoint within the body of literature highlighting the different variations to the meaning of virtue from a cultural perspective. In understanding virtue as an individual or as a leader, variation in what embodies a leader will differ according to the cultural context of the individual. A leader from a Western perspective will differ in their understanding of what virtue entails than a leader from an Eastern perspective (Knights & Majella, 2005; Hackett & Wang, 2012).

Dion (2012) posits eudaimonia can be understood as happiness or sometimes as wealth. Virtue ethics extends to Aristotle and Plato and rather than viewing the heart of ethics to be in actions or duties, virtue-based ethical systems centre on the agent, the character and dispositions of persons (Knights & Majella, 2006). In comparison to deontology theory of ethics, virtue ethics focuses wholly on the agent rather than the act and, in this sense, is highly or wholly decontextualized (Knights and O'Leary, 2006).

Several scholars have stressed that most approaches to the understanding of virtue ethics rely majorly on a relatively arbitrary and almost inexhaustive list of an individual's character trait (Dion, 2012; Knights & Majella, 2006). In comparison to the deontological theory and consequentialist or teleological theory, which bases the determinant of what makes an action morally right, the virtue-based approach seeks to define what makes a person good (Sabbagh, 2009). The virtue ethical theory judges an individual by their character rather than by an action that may deviate from one's normal behavior. It takes the person's morals, reputation, and motivation into account when rating an unusual and irregular behavior that is considered unethical (Dobel, 1998; Knights & Majella, 2006). Virtues are a fundamental and integral part of the landscape of moral philosophy and provide a useful way of thinking about leadership development (Ciulla, 2006). Whilst most schools of thought have attributed virtue as a character or behaviour of an individual or a leader from an individualistic or societal context, some scholarly works have iterated the concept of virtue as a skill (Anna, 1995; Stichter, 2007; Dougherty, 2020).

Anna (1995) work on virtue as a skill draws exclusively on the skill analogy based on Socratic ideas. The study highlighted three elements vital for a genuine skill namely, the skill must be teachable, there must be unifying or underlining principles that the expert can grasp, and that experts can give an account of skilled actions (Anna, 1995; Stichter, 2007). Anna (1995) posits that the demands made of the virtuous individuals by philosophers who regard virtue as

analogous to skill are similar to the demands made by more recent theories of morality which demand that the moral or ethical individuals be able to reflect on their practices, extract the principles that these are dependent on, and produce justification when needed. According to the author's work, the first element from their findings suggests that virtue as a skill is teachable. As an individual has acquired knowledge or learned something new, one should be able to teach what they have learnt. In essence, the individual has learned the theory behind the acquired skill (Stichter, 2007).

Sticher (2007) argues Anne (1995) understanding and teachability of virtue as a skill is rather misconstrued but highlights the possibility of knowledge transfer from an individual who possess this experience to another if they possess the intellectual component required to be considered a genuine skill. The second element of virtue as a skill addresses that there must be a unifying or underlining principle that the expert can grasp. This suggests that there are principles and guides that unify the field of a skill, and that the expert has a grasp of these principles (Anna, 1995; Stichter, 2007). Sticher (2007) argues Anne (1995) understanding and the expertise within a specified field of virtue as a skill is rather vague if one possesses just an element of the knowledge but highlights the possibility that an individual require the expertise of all knowledge within the field for one to possess the intellectual component required to be considered a genuine skill. The third component of a genuine skill further advances the previous intellectual components, by requiring that an individual possesses the ability to give an account or self-reflection of their actions (Anna, 1995; Stichter, 2007). Annas (1995) suggests that an individual with a virtuous skill should be able to explicitly explain and justify their decisions and judgements, and to do so in terms of some general grasp of the principles which define that specific skill. An individual must be able to elucidate the justification for their actions, and this explanation should draw upon the individual's grasp of the principles underlying the skill (Stichter, 2007). Stichter (2007) suggest that this requirement could be

thought of as articulatable, rather than requiring that the individual can articulate the reasons personally, Annas (1995) explicitly suggests this requirement in terms of the individual being able to articulate the reasons for their actions.

Dougherty (2020) argues both Annas (1995) and Stichter (2007) miss the understanding of virtue as a skill in virtue ethics literature. While Dougherty (2020) suggests no objection in terms of correctness to both scholars understanding of virtue and skills, the scholar argues that each embodies a basic misconception of the skill analogy, a misunderstanding already implicit in both standard treatments of it. Dougherty (2020) argues, however, that neither Anna (1995) nor Stichter (2007) proposal can be correct because each defends the skills analogy of virtue by attributing to practical skill, a feature that it in fact lacks. The two proposals do lead us, however, to what is arguably the proper view of the analogy, which relies on the distinction between skill possession and skill-role occupancy (Dougherty, 2020).

With regards to Stichter (2007) disposition, Dougherty (2020) disputes the understanding and the evaluation of capacity/disposition objection of virtue as a skill as vague. According to Stichter (2007), capacity/disposition objection is the result of one's tendency to evaluate performance of an individual and not the performer itself. For whereas performance is evaluable only in terms of standards of performance (i.e., in terms of how much skill the performance exerts). Performers, according to Stichter are also evaluable in terms of their commitment to the practice associated with their skill (Dougherty, 2020). Dougherty suggests that the problem in terms of this school of thought, is that one also needs to account for skilled nonperformers. This disposition must be able to identify that skilled nonperformers, are evaluable in terms of their commitment to the practice concomitant with their skill (Dougherty, 2020). This identifies another misconception or problem in understanding of Stichter's proposal which evaluates all skilled individuals based on commitment. If all skilled individuals

are evaluable in regards of their commitment to the exercise associated with their skill, that does not entail that they are committed (Dougherty, 2020).

In essence, the problem with this viewpoint can be highlighted in the understanding that if all skilled individuals are evaluable in terms of their commitment to a cause or practice, that does not signify that all skilled individuals will possess the necessary motivation to act in accordance with the requirements and demands of the stipulated practice. In summary, Dougherty (2020) emphasises that the conception of virtue ethics is comfortable with the notion of a role and the due importance it places on being role models. As role models one must be able to possess the required fit and good skill-role expected of a specific occupation. Secondly, an individual must be able to reliably fulfil and perform positively according to the required standard of the specific practice and must be committed and motivated to quality performance. In relations to ethics as an understanding of doing good or abiding by what is right over wrong with a characteristic activity is performing that activity well. It means also that such performance is a thing worth aiming at for those who have that characteristic activity. Performing one's characteristic activity well, however, involves more than merely performing it and doing it successfully. It also involves having a certain kind of motivation for exercising one's skill (Dougherty, 2020).

Several scholarly works have highlighted the importance of virtue ethics as a theoretical foundation for understanding ethics within the concept of leadership and leadership effectiveness (Dion, 2012; Knights & Majella, 2005; Ncube & Wasburn, 2006; Ciulla, 2006; Grint, 2011). Furthermore, some studies have favoured the concept of virtue ethics over consequentialism and deontology in the understanding of ethical leadership (Knights & Majella, 2006; Whetstone, 2001; Arjoon, 2000; Knights & Majella, 2005; Morrison, 2001; Molyneaux, 2003). Ciulla (2006) highlights the disposition and differences in the properties of the moral concept of virtue and values, the importance of virtues are their dynamics (e.g.,

how they interact with other virtues and vices) and their contribution to self-knowledge and self-control.

Virtues are classified as things that you have or possess only if you practice them or through continuous development while values are important to individual or people. Knights & Majella (2006) suggest most scholarly works take an individualistic approach to morality and do not attempt to transcend the dualism between self and others. Bai & Morris (2014) addressed the challenges facing leadership and proposed a Daoist model consisting of five fundamental virtues of an ethical leader which includes vision, mission, strategy, execution and tendency. Their findings suggests that to guarantee ethical leadership, a leader is required to embark on a continuous journey of self-cultivation of morality and virtue ethics. To ensure organisational success in terms of performance, styles of leadership should be chosen in accordance with the highest standards of moral virtue and the characteristics of the specific organisational context (Bai & Morris, 2014).

In conclusion, some studies conceptualise virtue ethics as the possession of individual characteristics, attitude or traits to the understanding of what makes a person morally good (Athanasoulis, 2012; Arjoon, 2000; Dion, 2012; Knights & Majella, 2006; Hackett & Wang, 2012; Whetstone, 2001; Sabbagh, 2009). Other studies have elucidated the understanding of virtue ethics as a skill an individual must possess to influence others both in a societal context or in an organisation (Anna, 1995; Dougherty, 2020; Stichter, 2007). In understanding the roles of ethics in leadership, most works have emphasised the necessity and the need for virtue ethics in the operationalisation and conceptualisation of leadership effectiveness, ethics and performance (Dion, 2012; Knights & Majella, 2005; Ncube & Wasburn, 2006; Ciulla, 2006). Several scholars have suggested virtue ethics as the theoretical foundation and have favoured this concept of ethics over consequentialism and deontology in the understanding of ethical leadership (Knights & Majella, 2006; Whetstone, 2001; Arjoon, 2000; Knights & Majella,

2005; Morrison, 2001; Molyneaux, 2003). In essence, this study will be adopting the standpoint of virtue ethics as the ethical theoretical background for ethical leadership and the understanding of virtue ethics as a skill in the conceptualisation and operationalisation of ethical leadership within the Nigeria public sector.

2.5. Contractarianism

Contractarian approaches highlights consent as a medium of justifying principles of an individual's actions and provides needed consent for rendering normative judgements concerning economic behaviours (Dunfee, et al., 1995). This stems from the Hobbesian line of social contract thought, which holds that individuals are primarily self-interested, and that a rational assessment of the best strategy for attaining the maximisation of their self-interest will lead them to act morally (where the term normal norms are determined by the maximisation of joint interest) and to consent to governmental authority (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, 2017). Morrison (2001) elucidates the concept of contractarianism as the belief that normative ethics are determined by overall fairness. Fairness occurs when all individuals are bestowed equal respect and deference. As a result, ethical decision making recognises individual rights: the rights of employees to be treated fairly, the rights of consumers to safe and effective products, and so on (Morrison, 2001).

2.6. Pluralism

Ethical pluralism recognises that cultures can legitimately pass judgements on one another. It encourages us to listen to what other cultures say about one's culture as well as what they say about them (Hinman, 2012). The principal claim of pluralism is that there can be multiple correct answers to the ethical question of right and wrong, better and worse, good and bad, not just merely a correct answer (Lengbeyer, 2005). Ethical pluralistic views suggest there are a variation of distinctive ethical values in the world that cannot be reduced to one another or derived from any higher common source (Ivanhoe, 2009).

2.7. Ethics Construct and Leadership

The growing necessity in the demand for more ethically inclined leaders in various sectors of business can be attributed to the number of major scandals and the recent financial disaster which caused the recession in the late 2000 (Hassan, et al., 2013). In essence, the concept of leadership plays a key driving force in terms of organisational effectiveness, employee motivation and overall long-term sustainability and growth (Haq, 2011). The lack of effective, efficient and morally sound leaders on the principles of strong ethical core beliefs have driven several industries, institution into disrepute (Knights & Majella, 2005; Thompson et al., 2010).

The concept and the definition of ethicality varies from both individual and organisational perspective. The way ethicality is viewed also differ accordingly to cultural and sociological settings. The necessity for ethics as a core value plays a critical role in the establishment and a general understanding of leadership (Cuilla, 2004). There is an increasing realisation today, that organisational leaders need to be subtler to their moral obligations to the larger society, which includes all their stakeholders such as consumers, employees, suppliers, governments and local communities (Mendonca, 2001). A surge in the amount of public outcry of the necessity to take actions over unethical behaviours of several business leaders has prompted a growing interest in the ethical repercussions of leadership (Brown & Mitchell, 2010; Voegtlin, 2016). It is the recognition of these obligations that has led several large corporations to formulate codes of ethics, ethics committees and communication (Mendonca, 2001). While these moral codes act as a guide for actualising an ethically inclined and moral organisation, the enforcement and the effectiveness of these policies in both short and long term relies directly and indirectly on those in leadership positions to enforce these strict guidelines for employees (followers) and the organisation as a whole. Butts (2008) highlights the necessity of ethical guidance as a moral code and way of life and work. The growing number of illegal and unethical attitudes and behaviours within organisations in order to acquire short term profit

margins by leadership within various organisation has spurred the necessity for an ethical form of leadership.

While the leadership construct in literature has been vastly researched and the never-ending topic of discourse by scholars, most of these leadership theories fail to emphasise the ethics perspective of what makes an effective leader. This might be due to the challenges facing researchers in adopting a de facto definition of leadership or based on the numerous definitions of leadership within the research community (Rost, 1995). Also, the concept of ethics categorically differs in meaning and moral values in relation to leadership in different cultural perspectives. There exist different cultural beliefs and understanding as to what defines ethics and the critical role it plays in management (Rost, 1995).

Ethics plays a critical aspect in everyday life including the way we conduct and transact business, and overall organisational attitudes (Derr, 2012). Leadership comes with many challenges that prompt individuals with top management positions to make decisions that has diverse effects (either ethical or un-ethical) on followers within an organisation (Derr, 2012). These decisions when taken in the long run possess implications to the way organisations are portrayed within the public sphere. The insufficiency and lack of ethics as an integral part of leadership in today's business and public environment has led to the surge in the desire for a better understanding and inculcation in both public, private and hybrid sectors. There is a growing misconception of various forms of leadership such as authentic leadership, transactional and transformational leadership as one with an ethical core. While these other forms of leadership possess some merits and are similar in characteristics to each other, they do not enforce ethical standards and core ethical beliefs as a critical component for dispersing work output and the provision for organisational performance (Bass & Avolio, 1993; Avolio & Gardner, 2005; Bouckenooghe et al., 2015; Bai & Morris, 2014). Nikolic (2015) provides a

detailed link in the necessity of ethical leadership behaviours and its effect on employee climate.

For leadership to be regarded as effective, it must be inclusive of strong morals and values. A leader's role is to utilise tension and conflict within followers (employees) value system and must be able to play the role of raising people's consciousness (Cuilla, 2004; Waggoner, 2010). Effective leadership should be able to maximise output and performance from followers and gain the highest level of result without a compromise in ethical beliefs (Waggoner, 2010). While this is highly essential and involves diverse number of variables and attributes to achieve this outcome, it is critical a leader must determine and attain strong personal ethics and moral values.

The need for moral form of management is based on a strong and recurring rise in the challenges facing organisation bodies both in the public and private sector in relation to lack of ethical competences and the growing disregard by top ranking officials to inculcate and adhere to ethical structures within organisations (Brown et al., 2005; Derr, 2012; Flite & Harman, 2013). In essence, defining and the development of a leader in most spheres of leadership tend to focus on key attributes that foster organisational growth while ignoring the role in which ethics plays in governance and the overall outlook of an organisation to the public. Organisations facing challenges with managerial competencies regarding ethical guidelines have fallen out of favour from the public sight and face various legal battles.

2.8. Conclusion

This chapter has provided a detailed understanding of the concept of ethics. Whilst the discourse on the definition of ethics within the body of literature dates back to the early Greek scholars, evidence from a comprehensive review of literature have identified a gap in the general conceptualisation of ethics. Empirical studies within literature have contextualised

ethics from the scientific and the behavioural standpoint, with majority of works ideating the understanding of ethics from the viewpoint of what is considered right or wrong and can be attributed to an individual or group understanding of a moral problem (Garnett, 1951; Davidson, 1988; Morris, 2004). An exploration of the various dynamisms into ethics was provided within this chapter. Scholars have provided several understandings to ethics and have examined the concept from various approaches namely, the teleological theory of ethics, the deontological theory of ethics, virtue ethics, contractarianism and pluralism. Theories have provided several advancements to understanding ethics from the viewpoint of duty and consequences (deontological), motive (teleological) and the individual perspective (virtue).

Whilst most studies have based ethics from the determinants of what makes an action morally right, scholars have examined the ethics of virtue as the possession of characteristics, traits and attitudes that defines a moral individual. Whilst virtue ethics can be seen from the behavioural perspective, some schools of thought have asserted the understanding of virtue as a skill (Dion, 2012; Knights & Majella, 2006; Anna, 1995; Dougherty, 2020; Dobel, 1998; Stichter, 2007).

This study will be adopting the standpoint of virtue ethics as the ethical theoretical background for ethical leadership and will be adopting the understanding of virtue ethics as a skill (Anna, 1995; Stichter, 2007; Dougherty, 2020) in the conceptualisation and operationalisation of ethical leadership within the Nigeria public sector.

The next chapter will examine the current conceptualisation on the concept of leadership within the body of literature.

CHAPTER THREE: LEADERSHIP

3.0. Introduction

This chapter explores the concept of leadership within literature. It provides a better understanding of the definition of a leader and what leadership entails. A critical review of literature is conducted to provide a clearer picture of the various views and definition of leadership, highlighting the differences between leadership and management. Furthermore, the identification of various theories of leadership will be addressed identifying the missing gaps (ethical perspective) within these forms of leadership and addressing the unique attributes, similarities and differences. Finally, the chapter concludes by addressing the necessity for the ethical core within leadership and drawing a pathway for the need for and importance of ethicality within leadership.

3.1. Leadership Definition

The definition of who and what embodies a leader is one of the ongoing debates within the research community and everyday life. Various scholarly works on the concept is as old as time memorial dating back to the times of Aristotle and Plato in ancient Greek times. While a universal definition of the concept still evades academics and researchers alike, various studies in the field have suggested conceptual meanings of this phenomenon. Leadership is a process of social influence in which an individual can enlist the aid and support of others in the achievement of a common task (Chemers, 1997). Chemers (1997) suggests that the leadership construct is made up of group activities and participation, based on social influence, and it's fixated around a common task.

Understanding the concept of leadership as a construct spurns from different views and circumstances as seen by those in ancient history and in modern times. Those perceived as leaders have altered the course of history either positively or negatively during their lifetime in battles, conquest, wars and in community development (Halaychik, 2016). Getting a better

meaning of what leadership entails and what makes an individual an effective leader can be considered a daunting task. This is due to the complexity and nature of the leadership phenomenon and what it entails (Van Waat, 2005). Defining and understanding the complexity varies considerably from a specific circumstance to the next; and those seeking a deeper meaning must take into consideration more sophisticated models (Van Waat, 2005; Bass & Stogdill, 1990). This involves an array of assessment skills, a series of characteristics (traits and skills) that individuals called leaders bring to a particular setting, and a wide variety of behavioural competencies (Van Waat, 2005). Furthermore, while leadership poses some elements of commonality and attributes, they also vary significantly in some other respects.

The study of what leadership consist of draws to the study of history, what leaders did and the reasons behind the actions taken by these individuals (Bass & Stogdill, 1990). The search for the generalisation of leadership in modern times has been built on the critical analysis of the development, motivation and the competences of world leaders (either living or dead). These leadership skills or competencies needed vary substantially over certain scenarios such as organisational settings and public services (Bass & Stogdill, 1990; Van Waat, 2005). Over generalisation and the adaptation of the meaning has led in the early years to a delay in the exploration and gaining of deeper knowledge of this construct. While today's research provides a diverse view of the meaning and what it entails, further meaning has been achieved in recent times due to the shedding of light from various perspectives.

Several scholarly works on the concept of leadership have provided diverse views on the phenomenon and what it entails (Chemers, 1997; Bass & Stogdill, 1990; Van Waat, 2005). As one of those concepts that evades a standardised definition due to its difficulty in providing a definitive standpoint, there exist a significant number of definitions of leadership as there are individuals attempting to define it (Silva, 2016; Van Waat, 2005; Stogdill, 1974). The estimated number of scholarly works in regards to the definition can be estimated at over 650

and counting as there seems to be no consensus on the true meaning and the search on a deeper understanding still ongoing (Silva, 2016; Bennis & Townsend, 1995). The search for a single definition of the concept is ongoing and may be in vain since the correct definition of leadership is dependent on the field of interest, the researchers and the type of situation being investigated (Silva, 2016; Bass & Bass, 2008; McCleskey, 2014). Drawing on this argument, several studies have provided various postulation of the definition of leadership since the post-World War II era.

Stogdill (1974) work on the “handbook of leadership” provides a detailed review of the definition of leadership and works done from the Plato’s era in ancient Greece till the post-World War II era. The author argues that the concept of leadership can be described as a complex phenomenon which can be seen as the focus of group processes, as the art of prompting compliance, as a personality attribute, an exercise of influence, as a particular kind of act, as a form of persuasion, as a power relation, as a medium of interaction, as a critical instrument for fostering the attainment of goals, as a differentiated role, and the imitation of structures (Stogdill, 1974, p. 411). Drawing from this definition, this supports the argument of several researchers that a deeper and better understanding is dependent on the specific situation and research focus one seeks to explore (McCleskey, 2014; Bass & Bass, 2008; Banerjee & Ercetin, 2012; Silva, 2016).

Kotter (1988) is of the opinion that it involves the process of moving and guiding a group (clusters) towards a given direction through non-coercive manner or means. This supports Stogdill (1974)’s definition regarding the understanding of leadership as a process. While this definition is true to a certain extent, some schools of thought are of the opinion that the use of coercive means can be considered a form of leadership as it involves dealing with individuals (Kellerman, 2014; Silva, 2016; Volckmann, 2012). In regard to the use of coercive means to accomplish a task, it still falls under the key adaptation of a process between a leader and a

follower and the final purpose of attaining a desired goal (Kellerman, 2014; Volckmann, 2012). Tannenbaum et al. (1961) is of the standpoint that it involves an interpersonal influence, exercised and structured in a situation, and directed through a communication process, towards the attainment of a target or specific goals. Northouse (2007) posits it entails the process where one influences a group of individuals to attain a common target or goal.

Jago (1982) takes a different approach to providing a better understanding of the concept of leadership and suggests this involves the process of application of an individual's leadership skills and knowledge, influenced by one's traits or attributes such as beliefs, ethics and values to accomplish an action. From this viewpoint, Jago (1982) identifies the pivotal roles of managerial and authoritative skills as a requirement to the leadership construct. Rost (1991) provides a differentiation between the concept of management and leadership in literature. Rost (1991) posits that leadership can be regarded as the influence relationship between leaders and followers who effects actual changes that reflect their mutual goals. It entails the process of persuasion or motivation by which an individual or groups of individuals induce a group of followers to chase objectives held by the leader or shared between the leaders and followers. From Rost (1991) viewpoint, the concept is not just dependent on the ability of an individual in authority, but dependent on the properties of the situation and the composition of the followers to be led. Drawing on this definition, there are several differences between management and leadership. See Table 1

Table 1: Differences between leadership and management. (Rost, 1991)

Leadership	Management
Influence relationship	Authority relationship
Leader and followers	Managers and subordinates
Intend real changes	Produce goods/ sell goods and services
Reflects mutual purposes	Reflects good/services result and coordinated activities

Harrison (2018) gives a detailed viewpoint and critical outlook and a timeline on the definition of leadership. From the author's standpoint, scholarly works regarding this phenomenon is the focus and belief that leadership is centred upon the concept of process and influence.

Drawing from these scholarly works in literature and the observation of themes and patterns, it is evident that researchers in the field acknowledge the concept of leadership as a complex phenomenon (Silva, 2016; Bennis & Townsend, 1995; Van Waat, 2005; Bass & Bass, 2008; Morrision, 2001; Kellerman, 2014). From their definition and thematic observation and patterns, leadership involves a process (Harrison, 2018; Stogdill, 1974; Jago, 1982; Northhouse, 2007; Kotter, 1988; Bennis & Townsend, 1995) and the influence of individuals or group of individuals and vice versa (Bass & Bass, 2008; Jago, 1982; Northhouse, 2007), through interaction or employing communication mechanisms (Tannenbaum et al., 1961) to foster follower involvement for the purpose of attaining a goal or target (Stogdill, 1974; Bennis & Townsend, 1995; Chemers, 1997; Bass & Bass, 2008; Banerjee & Ercetin, 2012). From this definitive outcome of leadership from literature, it is evident that the concept of leadership involves four critical elements or factors working in tandem to produce a leadership process. These include the leaders, followers, communication and the situation (Sharma & Jain, 2013).

While the definition of leadership in literature has highlighted critical points and components, there are several problems and challenges facing this concept. Rost (1991) highlights some challenges facing the discourse of leadership in literature. Most researchers and academics focus on two aspects of what it entails namely, the peripheral nature of leadership and the content of leadership (focus on leaders and followers within a specific profession or organisation must adhere to in order to influence a leadership relationship).

The traditional conceptualisation and understanding of leadership literature by scholars and the basis of theories developed by these individuals have mostly focused on the traits, goal attainments, effectiveness, contingencies, personality characteristics, group facilitation, styles, greatness, management of organisations (public and private), goal attainment, goodness and issues (Rost, 1991; Rost, 1995). Rost (1991) argues and points to the notion that these peripheral elements are countable, prone to statistical manipulation, usable to train individuals and accessible in terms of causality probabilities. The sole emphasis on the peripheral aspect allows researchers within the community to have a sense of belief in attaining something tangible in the quest to defining and practising leadership. This gives researchers a sense of belief in doing something good due to the development of theories using the best scientific methods known to researchers and the adherence of the best logical positivist framework for research (Rost, 1991). In essence, researchers are mainly focused on the outcome, the traditional and quantitative methods employed and do not place emphasis on the essence of the concept of leadership. In regard to the content perspective of leadership, scholars are focused mainly on what actually pertains (content of leading) to the knowledge a leader must possess based on the type of situation, profession and field in which they are involved in. It is much more pivotal as a determinant of leadership effectiveness than the process involved in leading (Rost, 1991; Rost, 1995).

The understanding of leadership as a vital relationship, the process of leadership, the connection between leaders and followers, are all critical aspects and embodiment on the list of priorities that practitioners and scholars must possess to understand how to put leadership to work (Rost, 1991). Drawing on these assumptions, Rost (1991) identifies a critical gap in leadership studies regarding focus of works based on the “peripheral and content” side of literature and there is little research about the process of leadership. Leadership scholars have overemphasised the peripheral elements of leadership and the content elements of leadership instead of shifting to the nature of leadership as a process or viewed as a dynamic relationship. There needs to be more emphasis on the nature of the leadership process and how we initiate and build effective leadership processes whereby leaders and followers relate to one another to achieve a purpose or attain a goal (Rost, 1991).

3.2. Leadership Theories in Literature

The growing conceptualisation of leadership terminology and what it entails from time inception has seen various views on what embodies this phenomenon (Bulutlar & Kamasak, 2012). This in view, has seen the adaptation and further development of traditional and hierarchical interpretations of being an individual in authority given the complex and chaotic environment of today’s dynamic public and private environment (Bulutlar & Kamasak, 2012; lichtenstein, et al., 2006; Boultin, 2010; Hougum, 2012). Earliest adaption of leadership was from the great man and the trait theory of leadership as the embodiment to which we define power and influence of followers. King (1990), Alimo-Metcalfe (2013) and Clark & Harrison (2018) works on the state of leadership provides a detailed background of leadership within the field.

3.3. Great Man Theory and Trait Theory of Leadership

Scholars have asserted that the personality era includes the first formal documentation of leadership theories and a representation of a beginning in the exploration and understanding of the leadership process (King, 1990). The great man theory of leadership is as old as history (Boring, 1950). An assertion that certain people, certain men, are gifts from God placed on earth to provide the lightening needed to uplift human existence dates back mainly with Thomas Carlyle (Spector, 2016; Boring, 1950; Kirkpatrick & Locke, 1991; Day & Zaccaro, 2007). Successful leaders who have exemplified the epitome of greatness were examined; hence, the theories were called ‘Great Man theories’ (Harrison, 2018). A great number of literature within the early 20th century focusing on great world leaders such as Napoleon, Indira Gandhi, Martin Luther King and so forth have tried to differentiate great leaders from followers (Day & Zaccaro, 2007; Harrison, 2018). Several works related to providing a better understanding on the personality aspect (great man theory and trait theory) of an individual has seen countless numbers of traits identified as a unique necessity to becoming a leader (Allport & Odbert, 1936; Cattell, 1965; Fiske, 1949; Digman, 1990). Early research works of the early 1900s were based solely on the concept of an individual’s trait as an emergence of unique leadership efficiency and identification in both public and organisational circles. Spector (2016) suggests most contemporary survey on leadership within the field occasionally cite Carlyle’s Great man’s theory as the foundation of scholarship before moving on to more rigorous academic categories of leadership; traits, behaviours, charismatic, contingency and so forth.

Several studies have elucidated drawbacks to the conceptualisation and the relevance of the great man theory to the understanding of leadership within the 21st century (Grint, 2011; Harrison, 2018). Grint (2011) highlights the dangerous nature of idealizing the concept of the

embodiment of a leader as masculine and heroic in nature. This school of thought is shared by Harrison (2018) who elucidates the exclusion of women within the understanding of the Great man theory of leadership. Thomas Carlyle's works on the understanding of the Great man theory suggests leadership is genetically passed down and are of the male gender (Day & Zaccaro, 2007; Grint, 2011; Spector, 2016). In essence, this school of thought within that era and today's understanding of leadership suggests a gender bias, excludes the works and the leadership qualities of apparent successful female leaders due to the limited positions and opportunities for women at that time (Grint, 2011; Spector, 2016). Furthermore, in today's environment and business setting, a large number of studies have focused on the female perspective of successful leaders within major organisations in the world (Harrison, 2018). Some school of thought have iterated the relevance of the Great man theory of leadership in today's world and in most cases these heroic figure or saviour can be a woman (Spector, 2016; Harrison, 2018).

The trait theory of leadership in early research works laid suggestions that the personality traits of an individual influence leadership emergence and their effectiveness in the way they lead and govern followers (Colbert et al., 2012). Trait explanations of leader emergence are generally regarded with little esteem by leadership scholars (Zaccaro, 2007). Several acclaimed works regarding trait theory of leadership have seen several developments in the concept. Such works such as Stogdill (1948) whose survey in literature regarding post World War 2 era highlights several thematic traits exhibited by individuals acclaimed to be leaders. Stogdill (1948) also identifies the constraint of the trait theory and identifies the shortcomings in respect to necessity of specific traits regarding specific circumstances. Stogdill (1948) elucidates the notion that no consistent traits differentiated leaders from non-leaders across different situations. In essence, an individual with these leadership traits in a situation might not be suitable as a leader in another situation. Stogdill (1948) review of 124 studies suggests from

their findings that leadership can be considered as a relationship that exists between individuals in a social situation.

Another major contributor to the understanding of the trait perspective of leadership can be attributed to Mann (1959) on the relationship between personality and performance in small groups. Mann (1959) review on personality factors examined more than 1400 studies regarding individual's personality and leadership in small groups. From their findings, less emphasis and no correlation of traits was found with leadership criteria (Northhouse, 2007; Zaccaro, 2007; Mann, 1959). Mann (1959) suggests personality traits as a medium for distinguishing leaders from non-leaders, identifying leaders are strong within seven personality factors namely, intelligence, adjustment, extraversion, dominance, masculinity, conservatism, and sensitivity. Reviews by Stogdill (1948) and Mann (1959) argued instead for the importance of the group situation over particular traits in leader emergence (Zaccaro, 2007).

Lord et al.(1986) studies re-examined Mann (1959) work investigating the relationship between personality traits and leadership perceptions or the extent of leadership emergence adopting a meta-analysis method. Findings from their study iterated and supported the notion that intelligence, masculinity-femininity and dominance were significantly related for leadership perception. Lord et al. (1986) argued that the Mann and Stogdill reviews complicated the differences between leadership perceptions and leader effectiveness (Zaccaro, 2007).

Kirkpatrick & Locke (1991) expound that effective leaders are different from other people in certain core aspects. The authors identified key traits such as drive, leadership motivation, integrity, confidence, cognitive ability and the knowledge of the business. Furthermore, Kirkpatrick & Locke (1991) are of the notion that these traits help in the development and the acquisition of necessary skills for leadership. Zaccaro et al. (2004) suggests six key attributes of leaders from a review of studies over 10 to 14 years period from the 1990 to 2003. They

identified cognitive abilities, extroversion, conscientiousness, emotional stability, agreeableness, social intelligence, openness, self-monitoring, motivation, problem solving and emotional intelligence. The figure 1 below gives a summation of key studies of leadership traits and characteristics within literature.

Figure 1: Summation of Key Studies of Leadership traits and characteristics (Northhouse, 2007)

Stogdill (1948)	Mann (1959)	Stogdill (1974)	Lord, DeVader, and Alliger (1986)	Kirkpatrick and Locke (1991)	Zaccaro, Kemp, and Bader (2004)
Intelligence	Intelligence	Achievement	Intelligence	Drive	Cognitive abilities
Alertness	Masculinity	Persistence	Masculinity	Motivation	Extroversion
Insight	Adjustment	Insight	Dominance	Integrity	Conscientiousness
Responsibility	Dominance	Initiative		Confidence	Emotional stability
Initiative	Extroversion	Self-confidence		Cognitive ability	Openness
Persistence	Conservatism	Responsibility		Task knowledge	Agreeableness
Self-confidence		Cooperativeness			Motivation
Sociability		Tolerance			Social intelligence
		Influence			Self-monitoring
		Sociability			Emotional intelligence
					Problem solving

While early scholarly works were of the opinion of personality perspective as a determinant and a necessity for leadership roles, most of these studies fall short of the consensus of the defining traits for leadership effectiveness (Bulutlar & Kamasak, 2012; Colbert et al., 2012; Fleenor, 2006).

Trait scholars often develop lists of attributes that they believe are related to successful leadership (Fleenor, 2006). Drawing upon these assumption, Gardner (1986) suggests 14 attributes key to defining a successful leader. These include.; self-confidence, eagerness to task, assertiveness, decisiveness, adaptability/ flexibility, trustworthiness, courage to resolution, task competence, understanding followers and their needs, physical vitality and stamina, intelligence and action-oriented judgement, eagerness to accept responsibility, skills in dealing with people and capacity to motivate/influence people.

While these lists exhibit several critical attributes of what leadership entails, there are existing fault lines to these attributes. First, many scholars do make the mistake of misinterpreting the conception of trait with skills and behaviour (Fleenor, 2006; Kanodia & Sacher, 2016). Furthermore, some researchers are of the opinion that these traits are basically focused on the masculine perspective (Fleenor, 2006). Fleenor (2006) suggests that there exist no differences between leaders and followers with relation to these characteristics, and individuals who possess these traits are less likely to become leaders.

The trait theory of leadership in today's literature lacks and suffers from the challenges of specification of traits that makes up effective leadership (capability) and what traits are needed to cope and adapt best in different situations and scenarios (Kanodia & Sacher, 2016). Furthermore, there exists little systematic research on the process through which an individual acquires the capacity for effective leadership, what trait constitute effective and ineffective leadership and their efficacy (Kanodia & Sacher, 2016; Fleenor, 2006). Due to the shortcomings and the limitations of trait theories of leadership and the constraint highlighted by prior studies (Stogdill, 1948; Kanodia & Sacher, 2016; Fleenor, 2006), this led to the obsolescence of this theory of leadership. Having trait theories of leadership became out of touch, the emergence of other theories of leadership were presented based on the shortfalls of the trait theory of leadership.

3.4. Influence Era of Leadership

King (1990) posits the development and a shift from the trait form of leadership (personality era) towards the influence era of leadership. Majority of studies and progress in research in regards to power-influence approach attempts to proffer an explanation to leadership effectiveness based on the amount of power possessed by a leader, the type of power and how this power is exercised (Yukl, 1989; King, 1990; Van Seters & Field, 1990). Research has been

done in relation to power influence regarding leadership effectiveness such as the different types and sources of power (Yukl, 1989; McCall, 1978). Power can be classified as a potential influence or a realised or enacted influence (Yukl, 1989). This stems from personal power of an individual's attributes or position power stemming from the characteristics of the situation (Yukl, 1989). Furthermore, the possession of vital information; combination of an individual being in the right place at the right time and the right resources proffers personal power (McCall, 1978).

The adoption of the social exchange theory (SET) presents the process through which the acquisition of expert power and greater status are accorded an individual who demonstrates skills in problem solving, loyalty to the group and making decisions (Yukl, 1989; Hollander, 1978). Yukl (1989) states that the manner in which power is exercised by effective leaders is significantly determined by whether it results in passive compliance, stubborn resistance or enthusiastic commitment. Effective leaders apply both position power and personal power in a delicate, easy fashion that minimises status differentials and avoids threats to the self-esteem of followers (Yukl, 1989). This in turn, means individuals in leadership position who exercise power in arrogant, domineering, manipulative manner are likely to face resistance from subordinates or followers (McCall, 1978; Yukl, 1989; Sayles, 1979).

French & Raven (1959) gives a detailed understanding on the concept and the various types of power in respect to leadership literature. The concept of power influence in leadership in today's doctrine is very much prevalent but the authoritarian, dictatorial and controlling nature of leadership can be said to be no longer effective (King, 1990; Pfeffer, 1977; French & Raven, 1959). French & Raven (1959) work elucidates five power factors of a leader namely, reward power, legitimate power, referent power, coercive power and the expert power. Atwater & Yammarino (1996) asserts that legitimate power, reward power and coercive power are

considered the three aspects of position power. In essence power sanctioned by the leader's position in the organisation or the organisation in general.

French & Raven (1959) defines reward power as the power whose basis is the capability to reward. This can be regarded as the opposite of coercive power as it involves an individual's ability to give or withhold rewards based on performance as a major source of power that allows leaders to possess a highly motivated workforce (Kovach, 2020; French & Raven, 1959). Some scholars have cited different variation about the relationship of reward power to employee job satisfaction within organisation ranging from the positive effects (Hinkin & Schriesheim, 1994; Afza, 2005 Elangovan et al., 2000) to limited or no relationship (Faiz, 2013). While reward power has been used as a mechanism for improving motivation and enhancing performance, some studies have highlighted this power have little to no effect in some organisational settings and some leaders adopt coercive form of power to influence employees within organisations (Faiz, 2013; Kovach, 2020).

French & Raven (1959) asserts legitimate power as the most complex power of the five bases of power in influencing subordinates. Legitimate power is based on the position held by an individual within authority. The higher the position, the higher the legitimate power of the individual (Hersey et al., 1979). A leader high in legitimate power induces compliance or influences followers within an organisation because they feel that this person has the right, by virtue of their position (Raven & French, 1958; Hersey et al., 1979). Legitimate power involves some value or standard, accepted by the individual, by virtue of which the agent can assert his/her authority. It involves a relationship between officers rather than between individuals within a formal organisation. (Raven & French, 1958).

Hersey et al. (1979) elucidates that reference power is based on personal traits of an individual. A leader high in reference power is admired and liked by followers, and others wish to be

identified with the leader (French & Raven, 1959). It involves a leader's capability to positively influence other's behaviour (Lunenburg, 2012). Several studies have ideated the benefits of reference power as a source of emulation and role modelling for employees within organisation settings. While this form of leadership possesses positive benefits, this form of power in some situations can be adopted negatively and can be a form of manipulation for employees (Lunenburg, 2012; Atwater & Yammarino, 1996).

Coercive power is similar to reward power and it is the ability of a leader to manipulate subordinates for the attainment of valence (French & Raven, 1959). Raven & French (1958) asserts that coercive power and legitimate power are similar in nature in that each form of power produces initial changes which are dependent upon a leader being the influencing agent. This form of power is based on the notion of fear (Hersey et al., 1979). The strength of coercive power is dependent on the magnitude of the negative valence of the threatened punishment multiplied by the perceived probability that a subordinate can avoid the punishment of the conformity (Lee, 2008). This involves leaders exhibiting the behaviours of forcing compliance from followers through threats, confrontations and punitive behaviours (Hinkin & Schriesheim, 1994; Faiz, 2013). Some scholars have emphasised that coercive power is least related to employee satisfaction within organisations (Faiz, 2013; Podsakoff & Schriesheim, 1985; Burke & Wilcox, 1971).

Expert power is based on the possession of skills, expertise and knowledge (Hersey et al., 1979). French & Raven (1959) asserts that the strengths of expert power varies with the extent to which an individual possesses knowledge or perception within a specific area. The extent of expert power is not clearly a function of the physical interaction or the personal quality of that interaction between a leader and follower. It may be a function of the knowledge possessed by the leader, not of his/her presence (Lee, 2008). Experts are perceived to have expertise in well-defined specific areas but not outside them

(Lunenburg, 2012). To be granted expert power, followers must perceive the power holders or leaders to be credible, trustworthy, and relevant within the organisation (Luthans, 2011; Lunenburg, 2012).

Hersey et al. (1979) asserts two other forms of power in influencing followers namely, the informational power and the connection power. Connection power is based on the connections with influential or important individuals within society and organisations. Leaders with a high level of connection power induce compliance from followers because they try to gain favours or disfavours of individuals with powerful connections (Hersey et al., 1979; Burak & Bashshur, 2013; Pierro et al., 2013). Hersey et al. (1979) states that information power is based on the possession or access to information valuable to other individuals. This power base is influential according to Hersey et al. (1979) as others such as stakeholders and followers require or need this information (Hersey et al., 1979; Tjosvold et al., 2003).

3.5. Behavioural Theory of Leadership

King (1990) elucidates a shift from the influence era of leadership to the behaviour era emphasising what leaders do as opposed to their traits, attributes or source of power. Some school of thought within this era ideated the concept of leadership as a subset of an individual's behaviour (Hunt & Larson, 1977; King, 1990). King (1990) suggests an important advancement in the development of leadership theory due to strong empirical support and the practical implementation by managers in improving leadership effectiveness within organisations. Harrison (2018) elucidates four key studies in the behavioural era of leadership namely, Lewin et al. (1939), the Ohio State studies, Michigan studies and Blake and Mouton studies.

Lewin et al. (1939) works on pattern of aggressive behaviour identified three major leadership styles namely, the democratic leadership style, autocratic leadership style and the laissez-faire leadership style. The autocratic style of leadership can be characterised by behaviours focused on the centralisation of decision making process and the concentration of power through which a leader controls every aspect of follower's activities without the consideration of followers' input (De Hoogh et al., 2015). This involves a leader having full control and telling the subordinates what to do (Harrison, 2018). Some studies within the body of literature have emphasised the negative effect of autocratic style of leadership to team morale, climate and performance (De Hoogh et al., 2015; De Cremer, 2006; Bass & Bass, 2008), while some studies have attributed some positive benefits to facilitating team functioning (Cammalleri et al., 1973; Bass & Bass, 2008; De Hoogh et al., 2015).

The democratic style of leadership encourages follower participation in the decision making process and lends itself to a two-way communication between the leader and the follower as opposed to the dictatorial one-way style of autocratic leadership (Harrison, 2018; Gandolfi & Stone, 2017). Lewin et al. (1939) asserts that the democratic style of leadership is the most effective style, as it fosters input on decisions from followers, and promotes a collaborative spirit in the actualisation of goals and objectives (Gandolfi & Stone, 2017). The laissez-faire leadership style involves a complete hands off approach in followers task objectives and decision making process (Harrison, 2018; Gandolfi & Stone, 2017). Such approach to leadership is detrimental to organisational effectiveness.

Another key study dominating the behavioural era of leadership can be attributed to the Ohio state and Michigan studies which focus on important behaviours of a leader (King, 1990; Harrison, 2018; Stogdill & Coons, 1957). Ohio state studies elucidated two separate leadership behaviours namely, initiating structures and consideration (Blanchard et al., 1993; Stogdill, 1974; King, 1990). Initiating structures involves a leader's emphasis on accomplishment of

task within an organisation (King, 1990; Harrison, 2018). While consideration involves a leader's concern for follower and group cohesion, involving relationship behaviours between the leader and the followers (King, 1990; Harrison, 2018). Some scholars have criticised the Ohio state leadership studies based on the grounds that they lack conceptual base and fail to take into account the situational variables (Kerr et al., 1974; Blanchard et al., 1993). Harrison (2018) suggests another key study within the behavioural era of leadership is the Michigan studies. Michigan scholars adopting an interview approach derived two dimensions of leadership behaviours namely, employee orientation and production orientation (Cartwright & Zander, 1960; Kahn & Katz, 1953; Katz & Kahn, 1951; Barrow, 1977; Harrison, 2018). Cartwright & Zander (1960) provided a reinterpretation of these two dimensions of group behaviours into leadership behavioural dimensions of group maintenance functions and group achievement functions.

Ohio studies laid the foundation for training programs for practicing managers such as the Blake and Mouton managerial grid (Blanchard et al., 1993; Harrison, 2018). Blanchard et al. (1993) suggests that the Blake and Mouton managerial grid changed the dimensions from "initiating structure" and "consideration" to the "concern for people" and the "concern for production". The adaptation of a two dimensional axes of the concern of people and the concern for production led to the generation of five leadership styles (Blake & Mouton, 1964; Harrison, 2018). Blake & Mouton (1964) identified five leadership styles on their managerial grid namely, the authority-compliance, country club management, impoverished management, middle-of-the-road management, and team management. While Blake and Mouton managerial grid have been adapted by managers and studied by researchers within the field of leadership, some scholars have stipulated issues and lack of consideration by the grid within various situations (Van, 2008; Burke, 2017; Hersey & Blanchard, 1982).

Bales (1958) proposed that leadership behaviours consists of two generic types namely: socio-emotional and tasks (Bales, 1958; Bales & Slater, 1955; Parsons, 1951; Slater, 1955; Barrow, 1977). Mann (1965) skill mix asserts that leadership behaviour is comprised of a trilogy of skills. Mann elucidates that leaders exhibit behaviours which aid the facilitation of interpersonal relations and positive working relationship (human relations skills), task structure and work based accomplishment (technical skills), organising, planning and the evaluation of work group activities (administrative skills) (Mann, 1965; Barrow, 1977).

Bowers & Seashore (1966) provided a review of literature on actual leadership behaviours and derived a four factor theory of leader's behaviour namely, the supportive behaviour, interaction behaviour, goal emphasis behaviour and the work facilitation behaviour. The supportive behaviour involves enhancing a follower's importance and personal developmental growth, the interaction behaviour encourages positive working relationships, the goal emphasis behaviour enhances and facilitates meeting the organisation's goal or excellence and the work facilitation behaviours encompasses activities such as scheduling, planning and co-ordination of group tasks achievement (Bowers & Seashore, 1966; Barrow, 1977). This school of thought was also supported by Taylor (1971) .

Wofford (1971) provides five factor characterisation of managerial and leadership behaviours namely, order and group achievement behaviours. Personal enhancement behaviours refers to a leader's use of power and pressure to achieve employee compliance. Maintenance of interpersonal relationships defines personal interaction leader behaviours. Security and maintenance behaviours refer to reactions to, avoidance of, and insecurity of feelings. Dynamic and achievement oriented behaviours include aggression and specific goals. (Wofford, 1967; Wofford, 1970; Wofford, 1971)

While the behavioural era in leadership have provided a shift from the emphasis of personality traits, attributes and characteristics of a leader to providing a critical understanding of the processes of leadership through distinguishing the behaviours that differentiate an effective leader from others, there are several limitations to the behavioural perspective. There are limitations to the situation, process and causality or interpersonal relationship (Barrow, 1977; Hersey et al., 1979; Hersey & Blanchard, 1982; Van, 2008; Burke, 2017). Barrow (1977) states the difficulty to demonstrate via correlational methodology whether leadership behaviours at different stages affect leadership effectiveness or group work effectiveness is as a result of multiple situations.

3.6. Situational and Contingency Theory of Leadership

King (1990) asserts that the situational era made an important step forward in the advancement of leadership theory with the acknowledgement of the importance of factors beyond the leader and the subordinates. Several works within this era provided a nuanced understanding of leadership based on contextual and situational factors. Major works within this era can be attributed to leader role theory (Homans, 1959), contingency theory (Fiedler, 1964), situational theory (Hersey et al., 1979; Hersey & Blanchard, 1982), path goal theory (Evans, 1970; House, 1971; House & Mitchell, 1974; House & Dessler, 1974), multiple linkage theory (Yukl, 1971; Yukl, 1989; Yukl, 1989b) and the normative theory (Vroom & Jago, 1978; Vroom & Jago, 1988; Vroom & Yetton, 1973).

While studies in the field have provided advancement in the development and the exploration of leadership from a situation perspective, three key studies have been asserted as the most important studies shaping this era namely, contingency theory (Fiedler, 1964; Fiedler, 1967; Fiedler, 1978), situational theory (Hersey et al., 1979; Hersey & Blanchard, 1982) and the

normative theory (Vroom & Jago, 1978; Vroom & Jago, 1988; Vroom & Yetton, 1973; King, 1990).

Fiedler (1964; 1967; 1978) contingency theory of leadership asserts the need to place leaders in situations that are most suited to them (King, 1990). This approach to leadership is generally situational in orientation, but much more rigorous and exacting (Luthans & Stewart, 1977). Luthans & Stewart (1977) states that the contingency approach to leadership can be defined as the identification and development of functional relationships between environmental, management and performance variables. This approach to leadership analyses how the situational factors alter the effectiveness of behaviours and the leadership style of a specific leader. In essence, this approach stipulates that neither leader's behaviour, characteristics nor their style develops leaders automatically.

Fiedler (1978) contingency model predicts that a leader's effectiveness is based on two important factors namely, a leader's attributes, referred to as task or relationship motivational orientation and a leader's situational control (Ayman, et al., 1995). Fiedler proposed the least preferred co-worker (LPC) scale which measures the personality of a leader from two standpoints, task-motivated and the relationship motivated (Fiedler, 1978; Harrison, 2018). Fiedler states that a situation is highly favourable for a leader where there exist a good relationship between the leader and the group, a clear-cut structure and a strong position power. Furthermore, a situation is least favourable for a leader where there exists a poor relationship between the leader and the group, unstructured tasks and there is a weak position power for the leader (Harrison, 2018). In essence, leaders who score low on the scale are said to be task-motivated and are suitable for highly favourable and unfavourable conditions while leaders who are relationship motivated (high on the LPC scale) will be ideal for moderately favourable conditions (Fiedler, 1967; Fiedler, 1978).

Contingency theory of leadership provides a better understanding of effective leadership behaviours in various circumstances or situations (Bulutlar & Kamasak, 2012). However, leadership in complex environments is not about clichéd actions and characteristics that are transferable to infinite contexts. Upon recognition of the paradoxical nature of leadership and occurrence of a paradigm shift towards emphasising contradicting styles or behaviours that could indeed fit in multiple opposing situations (Denison et al., 1995; Bulutlar & Kamasak, 2012), more flexible and complex theories of leadership began to emerge (Avolio & Gardner, 2005; Bass & Avolio, 1993; Trevino et al., 2003).

Another major study within the situational era of leadership is the Hersey and Blanchard (Blanchard et al., 1993; Hersey et al., 1979; Hersey & Blanchard, 1982) situational leadership theory. Fernandez & Vecchio (1997) states that the situational leadership theory is based on the interplay between the extent of a leader's directive (task) behaviour, leader socio-emotional (relationship) behaviour, and follower maturity/readiness for performing a specific function. Blanchard et al. (1993) posits that followers are the most important factor within the leadership event, as followers vary so does the appropriate style adopted for supervision (Fernandez & Vecchio, 1997).

Blanchard et al. (1993) proposed four types of leadership styles that correspond to the four levels of subordinate maturity. As follower's maturity progresses from very low to moderate, the appropriate leadership style adopted shifts from a low relationship and high task to a high relationship and moderate task style (Fernandez & Vecchio, 1997). Further increase in follower's maturity (i.e. maturity of a comparatively high degree) are best characterised by a low relationship and low task style. Several studies have highlighted challenges or issues on the usage of the situational leadership theory such as the concept of task-relevant maturity which has been highlighted as conceptually ambiguous (Barrow, 1977; Yukl, 1989; Graeff, 1983). Graeff (1983) stresses the problems with inconsistency and substantial conceptual

contradiction such as the absence of theoretical justification or explanation in the crucial middle range levels of maturity. The existence and failure to recognise the commonly accepted notion about the multiplicative fashion to which the two primary determinants of performance combine (Graeff, 1983; Barrow, 1977).

Evans (1970) proposed the path-goal theory designed for the identification of a leader's most practiced style as a mediator for motivation to get followers to accomplish goals. The path-goal theory reinforces the idea that motivation plays a pivotal role in how leaders and followers interact and the overall success of the followers (Polston-Murdoch, 2013; Evans, 1970). House (1971) asserted that the path-goal theory has two basic proposition. Firstly the function of the leader to positively enhance the psychological state of the followers that results in motivation of the followers to perform or have satisfaction with the job. The second proposition by House (1971) states that a particular situational leader behaviour will accomplish the motivational function (Polston-Murdoch, 2013). The path-goal theory proposes four leadership behaviours vital to foster follower's motivation namely, the directive leader behaviour, supportive leader behaviour, participative leader behaviour and the achievement-oriented leader behaviour (Indvik, 1986; House & Mitchell, 1974). Furthermore, House & Mitchell (1974) based the four leadership styles on three attitudes exhibited by followers namely, follower's satisfaction, follower's expectations of the leader and the follower's expectations of effective performance (Negron, 2008).

3.7. Transactional Theory of Leadership

Transactional leadership evolved for the marketplace of fast, simple transactions among multiple leaders and followers, each moving from transaction to transaction in search of gratification. Transactional leadership focuses on the exchanges that occur between leaders and followers (Bass & Stogdill, 1990; Bass & Bass, 2008; Bass & Avolio, 1993). While other

leadership theories focus on traits, abilities, or preferences, transactional theory involves a series of transactions between leaders and followers. Ideally these transactions result in positive outcomes between leader and followers (Halaychik, 2016). Success or failure, however, depends on the ability of the leader to effectively motivate followers either through reward or punishment (Halaychik, 2016). These exchanges allow leaders to achieve their performance objectives, complete required responsibilities, maintain the current organisational situation, motivate followers through contractual treaty, direct behaviour of followers toward achievement of established goals, emphasise extrinsic rewards, avoid unnecessary risks, and focus on improving organisational efficiency (McCleskey, 2014).

Transactional leadership allows followers to accomplish their own vested interest, minimise workplace anxiety, and concentrate on clear organisational objectives such as increased quality, customer service, reduced costs, and increased production (McCleskey, 2014). This provides a short-term purpose as leaders wishing to achieve results beyond the bare minimum will have to come up with more ways and methods to reward or punish followers. The theory sets up a system whereby leaders exchange rewards or punishments based on the performance of the follower. The theory is most effective when clear outcomes, policies, and procedures coexist with the resources and training necessary to perform the tasks. In this way followers have what they need, know what is expected, and clearly understand what the consequences (positive and negative) of not performing entails (McCleskey, 2014; Halaychik, 2016).

The transactional theory of leadership provides an easy-to-follow formula that followers can understand. Do your job well and be rewarded, fail to perform and be punished. The simplicity of the transactional approach might make it appealing to leaders looking for an easy and uncomplicated way to manage. Leaders needing to swiftly achieve tasks might particularly find the straightforwardness in implementing the theory appealing (McCleskey, 2014; Halaychik, 2016; Houglum, 2012). Individuals with a task-orientation may be drawn to taking a

transactional approach as it seemingly fits with their preference on focusing on defining expectations, providing timetables, and writing policies and procedures. Some humane-oriented leaders might also value the discovery process involved with matching rewards to a follower's specific ambition or motivational pressure points (McCleskey, 2014).

While these provide short term motivational benefits for followers and help in the attainment of organisational outcomes, considerations on the process and influence of this type of leadership raises several key questions and moral problems (Groves & LaRocca, 2011). It is an individualistic philosophy, where leader and follower exchange are based solely on both parties seeking their own personal or vested interest which involves some form of contracts (Bass & Steidlmeier, 1999). Moral legitimacy of transactional leadership is demanding in diverse ways. This is determinant on granting the same right and opportunity to others that one claims for oneself, on keeping promises, stating the truth, employing valid sanctions or incentives and equal distribution of what is due to others (Bass & Steidlmeier, 1999; Groves & LaRocca, 2011). Burns (1978) cites the issue of a short-term relationship that exist between the leader and the follower. These relationships tend towards shallow, temporary exchanges of gratification and often create resentments between the participants utilising a one size fits all approach to leadership construction that disregard contextual and situational factors related to organisational issues (McCleskey, 2014).

Furthermore, this theory recognises that to be effective, leaders must maintain their position of authority. The dictatorial nature of transactional leadership lends itself to creating an environment where one leader makes all the decisions. Progress can therefore grind to a halt if the leader is unavailable. In posing one's leadership, this creates room for an authoritarian form of persuasion. It invites loophole scenarios where the will of the leader is final, and employees not favoured by the leader do not possess equal or valid rights within the organisation. Followers who begin to challenge the authority of the leader or loyal supporters who find

themselves at odds with the behaviour or goals of the leader will likely find themselves either demoted or, in extreme cases, completely removed from the organisation (Halaychik, 2016).

Using a transactional approach can also stifle organisational progress in numerous ways. Initiative, creativity, and collaborative problem-solving will most likely not be encouraged by a leader using transactions as they have the potential to destabilise their individual authority. Transactional leaders are more likely to identify heirs that share similar qualities as them. This has the potential of allowing a system of clone management to occur and promotes an environment of “yes men.” Individuals who show talent for creative leadership solutions will likely flee the organisation as it does not share their values. Due to this form of traditional hierarchical authoritarian structure, there exist no ethical climate for employees to proffer both advice and report unethical practices by employees favoured in the eyes of the leader (Gini, 2004). The dynamism between leaders and followers considered ethical is dependent on the outcome of the end and the means of reaching this end are morally legitimate and whether the legitimate moral standing of the interests of all parties is respected (Groves & LaRocca, 2011; Bass & Steidlmeier, 1999).

3.8. Transformational Theory of Leadership

Transformational leadership stands upon the absolute acceptance of employees as individuals. The transformational leaders establish good relationship with their followers. They do not offer their followers rewards in exchange of superior performance. Instead of offering rewards, they motivate them to get their workplace ownership and build their own value (Bass & Avolio, 1993). As opposed to transactional leadership, which involves commanding, transformational leaders want followers to share their suggestions and ideas. This practice helps followers to think positively in their workplace and achieve organisational goals

Transformational leaders influence their followers by developing and communicating a collective vision and inspiring them to look beyond self-interests for the good of the team and organisation (Groves & LaRocca, 2011). Transformational leaders are described as visionaries, motivators, catalysts, futuristic leaders who invoke group respect, shared vision and improved culture (Rolfe, 2011). Rolfe (2011) highlight eight key attributes that contributes towards their success namely, expertise in their fields, flexibility, vision, charismatic, authenticity, self-knowledge, shared leadership and the skills to inspire and motivate followers. While transformational leadership theory duels on the influence and motivation of followers, there exists a gap within the ethical perspective in the employment of a charismatic approach to providing leadership (Groves & LaRocca, 2011; Avolio & Gardner, 2005). Some scholars suggest transformational leadership assumes that leaders possess knowledge of the value levels to which followers are to be developed (Rost, 1991; Price, 2003). Based on these value levels, transformational leaders operate at needs and values higher than those of the followers. This suggests a disregard for followers values and needs and the inculcation and subjection of the leader's values on the followers (Price, 2003).

Transformational leaders are characterised by their quality of not necessarily responding to the wants of 'followers, but the transformation of wants into needs' (Price, 2003). Leaders respond to subjective wants and later to more objective needs as transformational leaders outline the wants and needs (Price, 2003; Burns, 1978). In this regard, transformational leaders place major emphasis on self-interest and egoism to foster transformative changes in organisations excluding ethical or morality stance in accomplishing these organisational objectives (Groves & LaRocca, 2011).

In conclusion, transformational leaders evoke transformational and charismatic changes and foster growth within organisations based on their level of charisma and the strong influence and sway power they possess on their followers. While these promotes positive changes within

organisation with regards to performance in the short and long term, scholars have alluded to the components of ethics and morality in transformational leadership (Burns, 1978; Groves & LaRocca, 2011). While focused on driving and motivating followers to achieve a desired end goal, leaders exempt the concourse of what is morally right and guided by self-interest to promote changes and accomplish their organisation's vision (Bass & Steidlmeier, 1999; Burns, 1978; Groves & LaRocca, 2011).

3.9. Skills perspective of Leadership

While King (1990) evolution of leadership within the body of literature addresses key advancement within the field, some limitations still exist in their evolution theory. Some scholars have elucidated the inculcation of the skills perspective to understanding and the development of the leadership evolution taxonomy (Clark and Harrison, 2018; Harrison, 2018). Academic scholarship within the body of literature have asserted some differences between trait understanding of leadership to skills, there exists a major difference between the two concepts in the process and influence of leadership (Harrison, 2018). While traits can be considered as innate attributes that cannot be learnt, skills or competence can be developed (Northouse, 2007; Clark and Harrison, 2018; Harrison, 2018). Furthermore, some scholars have emphasised the necessity of skills as an important factor in influencing the perception of employees of their effectiveness in organisations suggesting leaders should be able to possess the competence in inculcating positive behaviours (Mumford et al., 2000; Bass, 1990; Fleishman, 1998; Fleishman, 1973; Yukl, 1994; Mumford, 1986; Howell & House, 1992; Winter, 1991; Mann, 1965).

The earliest adaptation and exploration of the skills perspective to leadership can be attributed to Katz (1955) work on the skills of an effective leader. Katz (1955) proposed a skills-model

consisting of three core skills necessary for influencing leadership namely, technical skills, human skills and conceptual skills. Katz (1955) provides a basis for the exploration of skills and laid the groundwork for examination of the competence required as a leader in an organisation. Katz (1955; 1974) posits the importance of these skills and emphasises that individuals who are effective must possess these skills. While these skills are crucial to organisational effectiveness, some of these core skills are more important than others (Katz, 1955). In essence, as an individual progresses along the leadership ladder from supervisory role, middle management and the top management, their expertise of these skills differ and are adopted according to the requirements of the organisation. The figure 2 below provides a variation of Katz (1955,1974) skills model at different levels of an organisation.

Technical skills according to Katz are skills which an individual possesses or understanding in a specific field or activity involving procedures or techniques, methods or processes. This involves possessing prerequisite knowledge or experience of a specific field and the analytical capability to deploy this knowledge to specific situations. Human skills involve an individual's ability to effectively foster interaction with others especially employees and stakeholders within organisations. Effective leaders require these ability or skillset to foster team participation and team building within the organisation. Individuals perceived not to possess the skills are less likely to develop effective interpersonal relationship or interaction between subordinates and are deemed likely to be less influential and effective within organisation.

Some school of thought also interchangeably adopt the term (interpersonal) with human skills. While conceptual skills involve the ability to think and foster beyond the tasks at hand. This includes a leader's envisioning and foresight ability to think outside the box and provide a vision for any organisation. While this skills model proffers a solution and an effective way for fostering effective leadership, this model falls short on the required skillsets necessary for challenging moral problems and dilemmas faced within the real world. In essence, ethics

requires a leader's personal ability and adequate organisational process to function effectively. The figure 2 below highlights the core skills asserted by Katz (1955) at different organisational level. Mann (1965) stresses the necessity of skills in influencing and facilitating behaviours to foster positive working relationship and tasks structures. Mann (1965) proposed three skills namely, human relations skills, technical skills and administrative skills. While Mann (1965) core focus elucidates the behaviours, the skills highlighted supports Katz (1955) model of technical and human skills as a core skill for an effective leader within organisations.

Figure 2: Core Skills Essential at Various Leadership levels of an Organisation (Katz, 1955)

Other prominent advancement in the skills perspective to leadership can be attributed to the early 2000s and onward (Clark and Harrison, 2018; Harrison, 2018). Several prominent studies proffered further exploration and empirical studies about the influence of skills on effective leadership within organisation across various levels (Mumford et al., 2000a; Connelly et al., 2000; Mumford et al., 2000b; Lord & Hall, 2005; Kearns et al., 2015; Mumford et al., 2007; Moore & Rudd, 2004; Harrison et al., 2018). Mumford et al. (2000a) work within early 2000 provided several advancement and development from Katz (1955) and Mann (1965) skills model.

Mumford et al. (2000) proposes a different approach to leadership skills. Effective leadership behaviours in fostering employee and organisational performance are fundamentally dependent on a leader's ability or skill to solve complex problems that arise within organisations. Leadership behaviours while important and key to influencing perception of their effectiveness is not enough (Mumford et al., 2000; Hall & Lord, 1995). Mumford's model is cognitive based highlighting the proposition that leadership depends on an individual's capability to formulate and implement solutions to complex social problems.

Mumford's model highlights problem-solving, knowledge, social judgement and social skills as the core skills with influence from external and career experience as mediators for performance. In essence, this implies that knowledge and skills are a driver of performance (Mumford et al., 2000). While Mumford's work proffers a complex problem-solving aspect of the skills model, there are limitations in the understanding and adaptation towards ethical or moral issues. Ethical or moral issues within organisations are complex issues which require a leader's ability to solve them. There exists a gap in identifying, inculcating ethics, moral values and behaviours within this model. The figure 3 provides an adaptation of Mumford et al. (2000) skills model.

Figure 3: Mumford Skills Model (Mumford, et al., 2000)

Moore & Rudd (2004) proposed a conceptual skills framework for extension directors and administrators identifying six major skills necessary to be effective namely, human skills, conceptual skills, technical skills, communication skills, emotional intelligence and industry knowledge skills. Moore & Rudd's work suggest communication skills as critical to fostering effective leadership within organisations. The figure 4 below highlights Moore & Rudd (2004) conceptual model of leadership. This skills-model is an improvement on Katz (1955;1974) leadership model emphasising the importance of communication and listening skills and vision. However, this model proposed falls short of addressing the complex nature of everyday ethical challenges faced within organisations.

Figure 4: Moore & Rudd Conceptual Skills Model (Moore & Rudd, 2004)

Lord & Hall (2005) suggest five specific skills associated with effective leadership namely, task skills, emotional skills, social skills, values and meta-monitoring skills. This model proposes that emotional skills is an integral element to fostering leadership and influencing positive employee and organisation output. Though Lord & Hall (2005) skills-model suggests a value structure aspect of leadership skills development of an effective leader, its limitation is its focus on the self-awareness attribute of an authentic leader.

Mumford et al. (2007) proposed a skills model consisting of four categories of leadership skills namely, cognitive skills, interpersonal skills, business skills and strategic skills. Their work also proposed different strata level of leadership skills within various leadership roles in an organisation. Their work highlight strategic skills are partly required at the highest level of leadership while cognitive skills are vital across all levels of organisational leadership and a driver for effectiveness.

Kearns et al. (2015) explored the prioritisation of skills within non-profit organisations involving executive directors and how they accomplish tasks within their organisation. Findings from their work identified three core aspects of leadership skills namely, technical, interpersonal and conceptual skills. Furthermore, their findings highlight the utilisation of a mix of these three core skills in achieving their tasks. Also, they identify communication skills and trust building as the prevalent skills. This study did not place emphasis on the inculcation of ethics within the organisation.

Some studies addressed some aspect of leadership skills as a component of ethical competency within organisations (Bowman et al., 2004; Heres & Lasthuizen, 2013; Kavathatzopoulos & Rigas, 1998; Kavathatzopoulos, 2012; Macaulay & Lawton, 2006). Major works have addressed ethical competency as the combination of knowledge, skills and attitude (KSA) a leader must possess to be considered ethically competent. Some scholarly literature has stipulated the need for ethical competency in ethical leadership (Heres & Lasthuizen, 2013). However, some studies are of the opinion that an individual can be ethically competent but not an effective leader (Kavathatzopoulos, 2012; Heres & Lasthuizen, 2013). This implies that while they possess the ethical attribute and behaviours, they do not possess the right skillset to influence their subordinates (Whitton, 2007; De Schrijver & Maesschaik, 2013; Kulju et al., 2015). Furthermore, the boundaries between ethical competence and ethical leadership are blurry. There exists confusion and conflation between these two concepts which makes it more difficult to define (Heres & Lasthuizen, 2013).

Kavathatzopoulos & Rigas (1998) propose the necessary knowledge, skills and attitudes (KSA) an ethical competent individual must possess namely, high ethical awareness; cognitive skills; ability to discuss and handle moral problems at group and organisational level, formulation of ethical principles and guidelines; the power to argue convincingly for preferred decision or actions made and the strengths to implement these decisions no matter how controversial. They

postulate two key methods of handling moral issues adopting Piaget (1932). Individuals employ two modes of thought process in proffering solution in decision making namely, heteronomy thinking and the autonomy thinking.

Heteronomy thinking involves an automatic, emotional and uncontrolled thinking while autonomy thinking involves focusing on the actual situation or problem (Kavathatzopoulos, 2012; Kavathatzopoulos & Rigas, 1998). An ethical competent leader should possess the ability to use autonomy thinking if and when it is demanded and not for any kind of moral or ethical issue (Kavathatzopoulos, 2012).

Bowman et al. (2004) proposed an integration of virtue and technical competence as vital components of successful public management. The scholars proposed this integration rests upon a skills triangle comprising of leadership competence, technical competence and ethical competence. While Bowman proposes a skills triangle to acquisition of ethical competence, this work do not specify distinctively the key skills needed as an ethical leader.

Macaulay & Lawton (2006) proposed a detailed variation of knowledge, skills and attitude (KSA) for ethical competence within the public service. While this work does not provide a clear distinction between these skills and attitude, the categorisation of the skills highlighted within this study are technical (knowledge), conceptual (problem solving skilling; investigative skills) and interpersonal skills (written communication skills, verbal communication skills). Furthermore, the communication skills were identified as the major competence (skills).

Whitton (2007) identified six elements within their ethical competency model namely, subject-matter knowledge, reasoning skills, problem-solving skills, advocacy skills, self-awareness and consensus-building skills, and attitudes and commitment. Haq (2011) proposes five skills for ethic-based leadership within public service namely, technical skills, conceptual skills, interpersonal skills, emotional intelligence and social intelligence. While this work highlights

these skills in regard to ethics and leadership, there exist empirical limitations to support this model. Harrison et al. (2018) proposed and identified four distinct skills for the advancement of entrepreneurial leaders. Harrison et al. (2018) projected interpersonal skills, conceptual, technical and a new skills perspective of entrepreneurial skills for effective entrepreneurial leaders.

While works in the field have provided several advancements in understanding the need and importance of leadership skills and its development, there exist some limitation in addressing key issues affecting leadership in today's environment such as the ethical challenges and lack of ethical competence within leadership literature (Heres and Lasthuizen, 2013). Furthermore, works have proposed different skills model for effective leadership within organisations. There are limitations with regards to the concept of ethic-based leadership (ethical leadership) and how it fosters performance. As a result, it is necessary to explore the skills required for ethical leadership (Kavathatzopoulos and Rigas, 1998; Heres and Lasthuizen, 2013). The table 2 below provides a tabular description of skills model within literature.

Table 2: Various skills model within Literature

Katz, 1955;1974 ; 2009	Mumford , et al., 2000	Moore & Rudd, 2004	Lord & Hall, 2005	Mumford , et al., 2007	Kearns, et al., 2015	Kavathatzopoulo s & Rigas, 1998;	Bowman, et al. (2004)	Whitton (2007)	Haq, 2011	Kavathatzopoulos , 2012	Macaulay & Lawton (2006)
Technical skills	Knowledge	Technical skills	Task skills	Cognitive skills	Technical skills	High ethical awareness	Ethical competence	Subject-matter knowledge	Technical skills	Problem-solving skills	Knowledge
Human skills	Social judgement,	Human skills	Emotional skills	Interpersonal skills	Interpersonal skills	Cognitive skills	Technical competence	Reasoning skills	Conceptual skills	Creative skills	Problem-solving skills
Conceptual skills	Social skills	Conceptual skills	Social skills	Business skills	Conceptual skills	Ability to discuss & handle moral problems (moral problem-solving)	Leadership competence	Problem-solving skills	Interpersonal skills	Formulation of ethical principles and guideline	Investigative skills
	Problem-solving skills	Communication skills	Values	Strategic skills		Formulation of ethical principles and guideline	Decision-making skills	Advocacy skills	Emotional intelligence	Ability to explain and communicate	Communication skills, (verbal & written)

		Emotional intelligence	Meta-monitoring skills			Power to argue for preferred decision		Self-awareness	Social intelligence	High ethical confidence	
		Industry knowledge skills				Strengths to implement these decisions		Consensus-building skills		Ability to trust one's skill	
								Attitude and commitment			

3.10. Leadership Theories in Literature and the Ethical/Morality Gap

Due to the complexity and the ever-dynamic nature of today's environment, academics have shifted to various forms of leadership construct to accomplish organisational goals (Bulutlar & Kamasak, 2012; Chemers, 1997).

Several theories of leadership have provided some managerial advancements in regard to organisational effectiveness, performance and follower commitment and participation. Drawing on these theories, it is essentially pivotal in proffering effective leadership and such leadership should possess strong moral inclination (Rost, 1995; Cuilla, 2004). Leadership theories such as transactional leadership, transformational leadership, situational, servant leadership, spiritual leadership and authentic leadership have played critical aspects in today's management, providing guidance to followers within both the public and the private sector. While these forms do possess strong merits, various studies have cited the short-falls and challenges facing these constructs as ethical mishaps and lack of ethical directions in guiding and attaining organisational goals (Bormann, 2017; Trevino et al., 2003; Brown et al., 2005; Derr, 2012; Bello, 2012; De Hoogh & Den Hartog, 2008; Begley & Wong, 2001; Brown & Trevino, 2006).

The concept of authentic leadership is relatively new and examines authenticity and self-awareness of a leader. Several scholars have examined the concept of authentic leadership as an effective form of leadership (Avolio & Gardner, 2005; Walumbwa et al., 2008; Gardner et al., 2011). Studies have proposed varying definitions of the concept of authentic leaders in recent times. While these have been based on the concept of being authentic, some authors contradict the definition in relations to the aspect of ethics as an attribute of an authentic leader (Walumbwa et al., 2008; Gardner et al., 2011; Groves & LaRocca, 2011).

Gardner et al. (2011) provides a detailed summary of the studies in authentic leadership. From literature, several scholars have argued about the composition of the moral and ethical component of authentic leaders as a core value (Gardner et al., 2011). Studies neglect ethical focus and moral development (Shamir & Eilam, 2005). While some highlight the concept of authentic leadership is based on a moral standpoint (Gardner et al., 2011; Walumbwa et al., 2008). In general, there is an acknowledged difference between authentic and ethical leadership.

3.11. Conclusion

This chapter has provided a detailed understanding and examination of the concept of leadership in literature. Several scholarly works from literature have asserted the complex dynamism and nature in the conceptualisation of leadership. From critical examination and thematic analysis of literature, leadership conceptualisation has been explored from the viewpoint of processes, influence and has provided variation of definition. Some scholars have provided detailed exploration on the state of leadership literature highlighting several key theories and perspective (King, 1990, Clark and Harrison, 2018) namely, the great man theory and trait theory of leadership, influence era of leadership, behavioural theory of leadership, situation and contingency theory of leadership, transactional theory of leadership, transformational theory of leadership and the skills perspective of leadership.

Scholarship within the body of literature has provided several advancements within leadership conceptualisation and operationalisation. Whilst studies have provided contribution to the body of knowledge in understanding leadership from these various perspectives, there exists gaps within the field for further advancement. Most empirical studies from the 1900 within the field that have examined leadership construct have focused on the personality, behavioural and the situation aspect. There exists room for further exploration in the skills perspective of leadership. Whilst some scholarly works have addressed the skills development of leadership,

there exist gaps affecting leadership in today's environment such as the ethical challenges and lack of ethical competence within leadership literature.

The next chapter of this literature review addresses the context of Nigeria and the public sector.

CHAPTER FOUR: NIGERIA AND THE PUBLIC SECTOR

4.0. Introduction

This chapter gives a detailed overview of Nigeria and the public sector. The context of Nigeria will be provided giving a detailed background of the nation from the population and ethnicity of the country. The second aspect of the chapter provides a detailed examination of the history of Nigeria from the precolonial era to the present day. The economy of the country is also discussed providing emphasis on the different drivers of the economy since the precolonial era such as the agricultural sector and the petroleum sector as a source of revenue for the country. While the country consists of various sectors, the main focus of this chapter will be on the Nigerian public sector. The next section within this chapter provides a detailed understanding of the Nigerian public sector. Challenges within the public sector will also be discussed.

4.1. National Context of Nigeria

Nigeria, or commonly known as the Federal republic of Nigeria is a country located on the western coast of Africa. A country with a diverse geography, with climates ranging from the humid equatorial to the arid lands (Udo, 1970). With a diversification feature of people and languages ranging in the hundreds are spoken within the shores of Nigeria (Britannica, 2013). Nigeria can be classified as a country with a thriving culture and people with unique values, region and a melting pot of a variation of languages (Britannica, 2013; Udo, 1970). Various languages within the country are spoken, with some scholars citing up to 500 unique dialects and languages spoken and with its official language being English.

Nigeria can be described as a very large densely populated western country situated on the Gulf of Guinea with neighbours to the north Niger, Chad to the North East of the country, Cameroun positioned to the East, the Atlantic ocean to the south and Benin Republic to the west of the country (Udo, 1970; Commonwealth, 2012; Burns, 1929).

Regarded as the most populous nation on the continent of Africa, the population of Nigeria stands at about 200 million people with an estimated population increase within the next decades placing the estimates at 400 million people doubling the current population (Varella, 2020). There has been a very high growth rate in terms of the country's population within the last 50 years. A country consisting of thirty-six (36) states and a federal capital territory situated in the capital city of Abuja and an area size mass of 924,000 square kilometres (Britannica, 2013). As part of the commonwealth of states, the Economic Community of West African States and a member of the African Union, Nigeria can be considered a strategic player within the Sub-Sahara Africa region. Nigeria is divided into six geopolitical zones namely the North central, North East, North West, South West, South East and the South region (Ezra et al., 2014; Varella, 2020). The figure 5 gives a detailed map of Nigeria highlighting the 36 states and geopolitical regions.

Figure 5: The Map of Nigeria showing the 36 states and the geopolitical regions of the country (Ezra, et al., 2014) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Map of Nigeria showing the 36 states and Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja.

Nigeria's terrain can be described as a country with diverse environmental formations ranging from the coast low-lying with sandy beaches and lagoons, a high plateau of extinct volcanoes within the centre of the country and a mountainous area along its border with its neighbour Cameroon (Commonwealth, 2012). With a population of over 200 million people, Nigeria's population is divided into different locations with the main bulk of the population of the country focused in Lagos state, Kano state and Oyo State. While Abuja can be classified as the capital of Nigeria, Lagos is classified as the commercial nerve point of the country with a population of over 9 million people (Britannica, 2013; Commonwealth, 2012). The figure 6 below gives a detailed representation of the population distribution of Nigeria highlighting Lagos state with a population of 9 million, Kano state with a population of 3.6 million people and Oyo state with a population distribution of 3.5 million people.

Figure 6: Population distribution of Nigeria according to Cities (Varella, 2020)

While there exists a large number of languages and ethnic diversity within the country, the major ethnic groups within the country can be divided into three groups namely the Igbo tribe

to the East of the country, Hausa to the North of the country and the Yoruba to the west of the nation (Udo, 1970; Britannica, 2013).

In respect to the religious and cultural beliefs within the country, Nigeria is divided into three major religions namely Christianity, Islam and African traditional religion. A 2012 survey placed the estimated population percentage at 49.3 percent Christian, 48.8 percent Muslims and the remaining two percent to people with no religion or practicing the African traditional religion (U.S Department of State, 2018; Pew Research Center, 2019). A report from the United States Department of State asserts many individuals within the country combine a variation of religions such as practicing their indigenous beliefs with Christianity and Islam. Furthermore, 38 percent of Muslims within the country identified as Sunni, 12 percent citing Shia and the remainder of the Muslim population attributing to just practicing Islam (U.S Department of State, 2018).

Furthermore, the Christian faith within the country identified themselves into various Christian groups namely, the Roman Catholics, Evangelicals, Baptists, Pentecostal, Anglicans, Methodists, Presbyterians, Anabaptists, The Church of the Latter-day Saints and the Jehovah witnesses (U.S Department of State, 2018). While there are three main classification of religious groups within the country, there exists other religious groups namely the Jews, Baha'is and individuals who do not follow any religious doctrine.

4.2. History of Nigeria

While the history of Nigeria as a republic can be attributed to the year 1960 when the country gained independence from the United Kingdom, several scholarly works have asserted the historical origin of Nigeria to the year 1914 (Udo, 1970; Burns, 1929; Crowder, 1979; Ogbeidi, 2012). Scholars have asserted that the origin of Nigeria can be traced to the amalgamation of the Northern protectorate and the Southern protectorate under the governorship of Sir Frederick

Lugard (Burns, 1929). The Northern protectorate of predominantly Muslims and the Southern protectorate of predominantly Christians were merged to form a colony for the British empire in the year 1914.

Nigeria became independent in the year 1960 after half a century of British rule. Three years after gaining its independence from Great Britain adopted a republic constitution but remained an active member of the British Commonwealth (Burns, 1929). Udo (1970) asserts that the adaptation of the British culture within the Nigerian context is evident and visible today within every facet of Nigeria.

Having gained independence in 1960, Nigeria's political and leadership landscape has faced tumultuous events and has undergone several changes from the prime ministerial system, the military system to the presidential system (Crowder, 1979; Ogbeidi, 2012). Historians and scholars alike have attributed a growing number of challenges facing both leadership system and the route of corruption to the incessant changes in government and the manipulation of forces in power such as those from the military era. While still a very young country at heart and less than a century year old, Nigeria's political system over the years has been plagued with a series of power grabs and coup de tat by various military personnel within the Armed forces. Due to this tussle for power by some forces in the year 1966, this led to the civil war within the country. Several historians have emphasised the effects of this war is still felt today. (Ogbeidi, 2012; Udo, 1970). Some school of thought have elucidated the negative effects of the civil war within society in shaping the way some ethnic groups perceive each other as a result of the outcome and the blood shed such as lack of trust, nepotism and favouritism from fellow tribe as opposed to other tribes within the country (Obadare, 2005).

Obadare (2005) elucidates a stand-off within ethnic groups in Nigeria and is best understood within the ambit climate of distrust and suspicion that has dominated the relations between core

ethnic groups and also the federal government. Furthermore, some other factors within the Nigerian context also mediate the issues of mistrust such as difference in social beliefs, cultural beliefs and most importantly the religious beliefs. Some scholars have proposed the negative impact of the differences in these beliefs on so many important factors such as, productivity, efficiency, performance, nation building and development within the country (Chiamogu & Chiamogu, 2019; Fatile, 2013; Gajere, 2020; Ijewereme, 2020, Obadare, 2005).

Ogbeidi (2012) and Tignor (1993) work on the political leadership and corruption in Nigeria provides a detailed timeline of issues facing the nation both from a leadership standpoint and the issue of corruption within the country. Ogbeidi (2012) states that the political growth and development of Nigeria since independence in the year 1960 have shown that the reins of government have always fallen into the hands of a political leadership class that showed more interest in private, group or ethnic gains than in the general wellbeing of the country. Some scholars have suggested that the issue of corruption dates back to the pre-colonial era such as the colonial government report (GCR) of 1947. As those within the role of public service leadership in Africa seek to further their own financial interest and goals (Okonkwo, 2007).

Storey (1953) posits that there have been cases of mismanagement and misuse of resources by individuals in public service for their enrichment and benefits. This has stifled the growth and development of the country. While the origin of corrupt practices is still arguable, the impact of this led to gradual decadence in structures, leadership and in the long run development of critical facilities within the country. Some scholars have highlighted the negative effect of this culture on the behavioural elements and the conception of ethics by citizens of the country (Fatile, 2013; Okonkwo, 2007). Ogbeidi (2012) asserts that corruption became prevalent in the 1990s during the military regimes of Babangida and Abacha, but a culture of impunity spread throughout the political class when there was a return to democracy in 1999.

In essence, Nigeria as a nation has over the years been plagued with an ongoing series of issues ranging from mistrust to different social, cultural and ethnic beliefs. This has in recent years shaped the understanding and the morality of the nation. This has created division and grounds for corruption to thrive in the political leadership sphere and within the populace (Obadare, 2005; Okonkwo, 2007; Ogbeidi, 2012).

4.3. Nigeria Economy

Nigeria's economy can be classified as one of the largest within the African continent. Since the pre-colonial era and the year 1960 of Nigeria's independence, Nigeria has experienced economic growth and regression over the years. A good number of studies have examined the dependence and development of the Nigerian economy from an agricultural standpoint (Orukpe & Omoruyi, 2017). During the colonial era, Nigeria depended solely on the agricultural produce of farmers from the North, producing cash crops such as groundnuts and millets which were exported throughout the British empire.

Economic activity and development were determined by the indigenes of pre-colonial Nigeria, who jointly owned and controlled the factors of production (Orukpe & Omoruyi, 2017). Thus, agriculture emerged as the predominant occupation of people and was largely dictated by the individual's knowledge on what to plant, when to plant these crops and when to cultivate. Akanmidu, (2014) asserts that the climate within the country played a core role in its effect on the vegetation and a dominant role in the pattern of economic activities. Agriculture was considered the backbone of Nigeria's economy from the earliest time up to 1950s (Orukpe & Omoruyi, 2017; Akanmidu, 2014). Indeed, Nigerians had an enviable record of food sufficiency but this era did not last beyond the 1960s when its economy began a descent into an abysmal dependence on imports as a result of corrupt practices and favouritism from some political elements in power (Obadare, 2005; Akanmidu, 2014).

It is of significance to assert that the economy of Nigeria during this period generally recorded tremendous self-sustaining growth and expansion before crude oil became the mainstay (Akanmidu, 2014). Nigeria boasted of its groundnut pyramids in the Northern region and cocoa in the West. Palm oil also existed in commercial quantity in the Eastern region of the country. Revenue from agriculture was appropriately used to build landmark social and economic infrastructure, providing basic services like education, health, water and electricity supply (Ekundare, 1973). This enhanced farm settlements and cottage industries to service agriculture, providing vast employment opportunities for the people. In respect of food, the nation was self-sufficient before the era of crude oil. Agriculture provided 95% of the food needed to feed Nigerians, contributed 64.1% gross domestic product (GDP) and employed over 70% of Nigerian population (Akanmidu, 2014; Ogbeidi, 2012; Ekundare, 1973).

Concurrently during the height of the agricultural dependence by the Nigerian government the exploration of petroleum products was carried out within the country. The search for petroleum in Nigeria started in 1908 at Araromi area of the present Ondo State by a German Company known as Bitumen Corporation. However, in January 1956, oil was discovered in commercial quantity at Oloibiri, now in Bayelsa State, by Shell BP (Akanmidu, 2014). Towards the end of the same year, a second discovery was made at Afam now in Rivers State. The first Cargo crude oil was exported from the shores of Nigeria in February 1958, when production stood at 6,000 barrels per day with revenue accounting for about ₦122 million. (Akanmidu, 2014).

From then, growth and development took a rapid course; from 1957 to the start of the civil war, 627 wells were drilled with a rate of success of 68.9 per cent, and 176 oil deposits were identified, of which less than 20 have so far been developed and put into production. (Stolke, 1970). Stolke (1970) and Akanmidu (2014) asserts that the preliminary findings of crude oil reserves within the region of Southern Nigeria amount to more than 800 million tonnes. Due to the discovery of petroleum and the shift from the dependence on agriculture, the exploration

and the sale of crude oil has been the major source of Nigeria's income. While this provided a massive elevation and huge source of foreign investment and trade, this has adversely affected the environment and developmental aspect of every other sector in the country. This in turn has led to several unrest within the oil producing regions of the country with ecological disasters ranging from soil and water pollution to the destruction of occupations within the region such as farming and fishing (Orukpe & Omoruyi, 2017; Okonkwo, 2007).

The Nigeria economy within recent years has experienced economic growth. As Amakom (2008) asserts, Nigeria's experience with industrialisation can be considered a typical case of misfortune. The journey for Nigeria to be an industrialised economy with high sustainable growth rates, development and performance has been the preoccupation of every administration that has piloted the affairs of the nation since after independence. But amid all these challenges for sustainable growth and development, the Nigerian economy has performed poorly since the late 1970s, resulting in stagnation and increasing poverty levels. A core indicator is the fact that manufacturing value-added as a percentage of GDP was about five percent in the year 2000 (less than the proportion at independence in 1960) and not more than 7 percent in 2005 making Nigeria one of the 30 least industrialised countries in the world (Amakom, 2008).

Industrialisation in Nigeria ascended during the oil boom era (1973–81, with manufacturing share of GDP reaching 11 percent), but has had a rapid decline to about five percent in 2000 (Amakom, 2008; Ikpeze et al., 2001). Ikpeze et al. (2001) provides a detailed characterisation, journey, strategies and performance post independence. The 1970s can be considered remarkable to some historians and scholars in a variety of ways. Firstly, some have ascertained this was the decade of pure military rule in the country and for some the decade of the first oil boom which produced a lot of financial resources, providing the government of that era the power and ability to initiate and foster economic growth and development.

Uzoigwe (2004) asserts a development for social ethics at the aftermath of the civil war in which wealth was determined by defined justice and social elevation. The desire for wealth became the object of this new morality and the accumulation of an agenda for most citizens of the country. A desire for this wealth by individuals and groups produced an insatiable culture of corruption in almost every facet of Nigerian life style. This has affected the country's development all through the years and a major concern within various sectors and organisations.

During the era of the military regime, there was several development and economic growth within core areas such as infrastructure, mining, and healthcare. This was due to the rehabilitation initiated by the military government to foster cohesion and to aid in the redevelopment of the economy. As Amakom (2008) states, the major drivers of economic growth within 1970s can be ascribed to the creation of jobs to help the citizens, better health care for aiding healthy lifestyle and wealth creation. While this initiative in those years were considered positive and effective by some, the growing impact of corruption within most of these created sectors impeded the growth rate and development (Enweremadu & Okafor, 2009).

There are several challenges facing the Nigerian economy and this can be attributed to the issues stemming from corruption (Nwokorie, 2016; Anyim & Ufodiama, 2013; Opara, 2013; Egbuta, 2019; Adamu & Celik, 2019; Ofuani et al., 2018). The challenges can be categorised into various classifications such as the political factors, religious factors, cultural factors and people factor (Ehiyamen et al., 2009; Egbuta, 2019; Adamu & Celik, 2019; Ofuani et al., 2018).

The Nigerian economy can be classified as product oriented dominated by agricultural and oil production. Furthermore, sectors within the country can be categorised into distinct sectors and structures that make up for revenue generation (Edo & Ikelegbe, 2014). The sectors include

firstly, the macroeconomic environment which consist of interrelated sectors and activities that function together to foster economic growth and development. These macroeconomic structures consist of the real sector, trade and distribution sector, infrastructure sector and the external sector (Edo & Ikelegbe, 2014). Furthermore, these macroeconomic structures are broken down into other sectors such as the agricultural sector, financial sector, energy sector, petroleum sector, and a lot more.

While there exists a diverse number of sectors within Nigeria, the Nigeria economy can be majorly categorised into three key sectors namely, the public sector, the private sector and the hybrid sector of the country. These three categories of sectors within the Nigerian economy embody all other major sectors in terms of employment workforce and contribution to development in Nigeria. While these sectors play key roles to the economy, the Nigerian public sector provides the major contribution to the economy in terms of employment opportunities and avenues for development (Edo & Ikelegbe, 2014; Orukpe & Omoruyi, 2017). For this thesis, the focus will be placed on the Nigerian public sector.

4.4. The Nigerian Public Sector

The public sector of every nation is pivotal to both growth and national development (Imhonopi & Ugochukwu, 2013). Public sector definition according to the System of National Accounts (SNA) are the national, regional and local government institutional units or bodies controlled by government (United Nations, Department of Economic Affairs, 1953). Nigeria can be regarded as a nation with a surplus by providence of human and material resources pivotal for national growth and development. However, since gaining political independence, Nigeria has continued to meander the path befitting failed, weak and juvenile states (Imhonopi & Ugochukwu, 2013). Evidently one cannot but agree with the position that Nigeria is a victim of poor leadership and convoluted systemic corruption which has become a bane in the country's national life. This view has been held strongly in literature by scholars who have

identified the inexorable nexus between leadership crisis and corruption in the country as the continued reason for Nigeria's inglorious economic throes, political convolutions and national underdevelopment. Current arguments rest on the conclusion that Nigeria's leadership suffers from extreme moral depravity and attitudinal debauchery (Imhonopi & Ugochukwu, 2013).

Eliogu-Anenih (2017) states that the Nigerian public sector is grouped into three major arms namely.

- * The Civil Service: the career personnel of the presidency, ministers, Extra – Ministerial Departments, the National Assembly and the Judiciary.

- * The Armed Forces, the Police, Other Security Agencies e.g., Para – Military organisations

- * The Parastatals or Public Enterprises

The Nigerian public sector can be described as a governmental tool which functions as a medium for public services that include revenue generation, management, political and social service delivery to the people and monitoring and implementation of policies (Eliogu-Anenih, 2017; Imhonopi & Ugochukwu, 2013).

Imhonopi & Ugochukwu (2013) posits that the success and failure of any country largely depends on the mannerism of its leadership. This is attributed to poor leadership in Nigeria in form of political turmoil, insecurity, poverty among the populace within the country. The role of the public sector in national development within the African continent can be considered immeasurable. Several scholars have asserted the impact of the public sector as a driver initiating government policies, aiding and improving the quality of life of individuals through job creation processes and an agent of fostering growth and development. The Nigerian public sector in recent years have been one of the main contributors to the political, economic and social development of the country. As one of the core contributors to the development of a country, the transformation of any society hinges on the efficiency and effectiveness of various

governmental organisations (Obasa, 2018). Obasa (2018) asserts that the contribution of the public sector in recent years have become less minimal and meaningless due to its non-performance, ineffective service delivery in providing services, absence of dynamism and loss of vigour.

Various studies have attributed corruption within the Nigerian public sector as the prevalent force truncating the development of the Nigerian economy (Eliogu-Anenih, 2017; Adrani & Thakkar, 2016; Imhonopi & Ugochukwu, 2013; Ogbewere, 2015). Ogbewere (2015) highlights six forms of corruption within the Nigerian public sector. These are, electoral corruption, nepotism, budgeting corruption, favouritism, ghost-workers phenomenon and procurement scams. Furthermore, Imhonopi & Ugochukwu (2013) attributes some causes of corruption within the Nigerian public sector are based on several cumulating factors affecting both leaders and followers. These are unfair wages accruable to employees; limited opportunities accorded to workers outside the public sector; lack of funding infrastructures for supporting employee development; lack of proper pension schemes; lack of strong moral and ethical values and inadequate and ineffective structures to foster public sector efficiency.

The public sector is the major channel for resource allocation, expenditure and policy administration in Nigeria and that defines its control of the economy. The public sector serves as a conduit through which resources flow down to the private sector and to individuals (Eliogu-Anenih, 2017). The prevailing issues facing the Nigerian public sector has been due to leadership ineffectiveness creating an avenue for corruption to thrive and disregard for moral, ethics and values by both the leaders and inadvertently the followers and subordinates within this sector. As a public sector driven economy, lack of consistent work performance and effectiveness has seen a backward spiral in the output of goods and services in the country. Adrani & Thakkar (2016) suggests that the challenges facing the Nigerian public sector is because of the lack of proper leadership styles and framework.

Fatile (2013) posits that the problems within the Nigerian public sector can be ascribed to the absence of ethics and accountability. Unethical behaviours and practices by both leaders and followers appear to have been institutionalised in Nigeria. Leaders do not follow strict ethical principles in the public sector because in most cases they stand to benefit from it (Fatile, 2013). While there exist ethic laws governing and promoting ethical behaviour within the Nigerian economy, there seems to be a nonchalant attitude by public sector organisations in adhering to these guidelines (Fatile, 2013; Sanusi, 2012). Several scholars have elucidated the issues facing performance in the Nigerian public sector (Ehiyamen et al., 2009; Eliogu-Anenih, 2017; Ogbewere, 2015).

Ehiyamen et al. (2009) asserts the issues of management can be attributed to the lack of control mechanism by leaders within the organisation. Staff within the public sector are faced with a number of issues stemming from lack of motivation on the part of the employees and leaders not possessing the ability to foster motivation. Some studies have emphasised factors driving employees not to perform such as the lack of discipline within the organisation. Employee indiscipline are demonstrated in diverse ways in the public sector such as habitual lateness to work, truancy, and lack of commitment to work loafing, buck-passing or refusing to take responsibility. It also includes bribery and corruption, tribalism and nepotism, misuse of government property, embezzlement or misappropriation of public funds.

Several factors are said to foster indiscipline in staff in the public sector. Kankwenda (2002) asserts that the drivers of this can be attributed to lack of skills and understanding in resolving issues or conflicts, their root causes, interests and values of employees and leaders are challenged due to their needs not being achieved. Ehiyamen et al. (2009) iterate four reasons for employee indiscipline in the public sector namely, the economic factor, socio-cultural factors, socio-political factor and the leadership factor.

4.4.1. Economic Factors

The economic factors as described by Ehiyamen et al. (2009) includes challenges of irregular payment structures and the poor salaries of the workforce within the public sector. Within the Nigerian public sector, employees and leaders alike are faced with growing challenges of their payment and a very high level of inflation within country. Employees and leaders alike are left for months without getting their entitled salaries. This can be attributed and due largely to corrupt practices, which manifest in the mismanagement and/or embezzlement of public funds by public officers (Ehiyamen et al., 2009). Furthermore, this may be due to the trickledown effect of corrupt practices from the political leaders who have direct and indirect control of these institutions when elected into political offices in the country (Ogbeidi, 2012; Opara, 2014; Nwokorie, 2016; Gundu, 2011). This creates an avenue for workers and leaders to be less motivated to work or in some cases engage in organisational deviance behaviours to meet their personal needs.

4.4.2. Socio-Cultural Factors

The main socio-cultural factor is ethnicity. Under ethnicity we have tribalism, sectionalism, nepotism and favouritism (Ehiyamen et al., 2009). Within the Nigerian public sector, these factors are considered a hinderance to organisational progress and development. As a multi-diverse country with so many ethnic groups, individuals, management and governmental bodies are more inclined to consider their kinsmen when allocating public sector positions. There exists a cultural dimension to ethics and accountability within Nigeria. The effect of ethical concern on government influence on public sector organisation foster negative inculcation of individuals into place of leadership and employment. Leaders and employees are placed within the organisation due to their connection to these political and government figures based on ethnicity, tribe, beliefs, friendship and family relationship. Certain employment roles

and opportunities are granted to individuals who may not be qualified to take these positions (Umaru et al., 2013; Imhonopi & Ugochukwu, 2013).

4.4.3. Socio-Political Factors

In the Nigerian public sector, staff recruitment, selection and promotion are in most cases politicised (Ehiyamen et al., 2009). Some studies have elucidated the challenges of politicisation within the public sector with a disregard for the proper recruitment process (Briggs, 2007; Anyim & Ufodiama, 2013; Akinyele, 2010; Imhonopi & Ugochukwu, 2013). This in the long run has affected the performance within the public sector. There exists the problem of Godfatherism within the sector or in some instance the patronage system. Employees or staff are working based on the return of favour to influential people in power that have instated these individuals into these positions. These attitudes can frustrate and discourage those who rely on merit (hard-work, honesty and/or additional qualifications). These unmotivated employees consequently resort to acts of indiscipline and unethical behaviour for solace (Ehiyamen et al., 2013).

4.5. Leadership Factors/Challenges in the Public Sector

Van Wart (2003) asserts the definition of public sector leadership as the process of (1) providing results required by authorised process in an effective, efficient and legal manner (2) development and supporting followers who provide those results, (3) aligning the organisation with its environment. Some studies have emphasised the importance of leadership within the public sector, and in some cases elucidate a distinction in the conceptualisation of public sector leadership to leadership in business or management (Orazi et al., 2013). In essence, the exploration of leadership in recent years have focused on providing findings from the private sector and have provided few empirical studies on public sector leadership (Van Wart, 2003; Van Waat, 2005; Van, 2008; Orazi et al., 2013).

Some studies in the field have provided a review on the role of public sector leaders within public institutions (Orazi et al., 2013; Van Wart, 2003; Van Waat, 2005). The core roles involve providing effective governance and direction to subordinates and stakeholders. Furthermore, public sector leaders are faced with the huge task of providing an image for the organisation and ensuring these organisations deliver their outcomes and objectives. With this in mind, public sector leaders are tasked with meeting three key demands for their respective organisations namely, the technical performance aspect, the development of people and organisational alignment. Public sector leaders are tasked with the burden of performance delivery and are expected to meet this demand, faced with the pressure of ensuring the demands and roles are met as compared to those within the private sector.

Studies have stated that public sector leaders are faced with burden and the scrutiny of public eye and external factors, compared to their counterparts in the private sector. Van Wart (2003) suggests that public sector leaders are tasked with the roles of leading effectively and in respect to carrying out duties and fostering effective employee participation in their respective institution. In essence, leaders in this sector do not technically do the work but depend on their followers to carry out their duties effectively. Public sector leaders are tasked with providing training programmes for followers, motivation, maturation and continued development which are critical to organisational effectiveness (Van Wart, 2003).

Orazi et al. (2013) and Van Wart (2003) suggests that a critical challenge facing most public sector leaders with regards to organisational performance is their managerial skills most especially their interpersonal competence. Public sector leaders are less equipped with the interpersonal skills to foster employee commitment, participation and improving their performance in general.

Studies in recent times have highlighted the pivotal role and attributes to which leadership plays regarding success and failure in organisational output and performance. Organisation management in Nigeria has lost its way adrift in a sea of managerial mediocrity, desperately needing leadership based on ethical values to face economic competition (Opara, 2014). Nigerian public sector problem is a direct result of leadership failure and the unwillingness or incapability of individuals in power to rise to the responsibility (Eliogu-Anenih, 2017). Iheduru (2016) also addresses the lack of effective leaders equipped with critical thinking skills as a reason for public sector failures. The leadership problem can be attributed to personality, approach, aspirations, motivation and values of the person in the position of authority. These positions are opportunities to create social change by working within the lines of ethics, equity, morality, strategy and most importantly, the code of conduct for the organisation. The Nigerian public sector seemingly lacks such leadership. It could be as a result of the complexities of the cultural diversities and problems of management in a constantly changing state of governance. Opara (2014) posits that the growing challenges facing leadership in the public sector stems from the disregard for ethics as a core necessity in management. Leaders who lack skills in leadership ethics have impacted negatively on the performance outcomes of public sector organisations. The root of this crisis or failed leadership is the lack of critical thinking, prior preparation and skills acquisition of those who are entrusted with leadership roles (Iheduru, 2016). Even where leaders were ostensibly prepared both through education and training, many of them fail to rise to the occasion and provide the responsible leadership expected of them. This is because they lack the ethical core values of “ethic-based leadership” that is cultivated through liberal education and critical thinking (Iheduru, 2016; Opara, 2014; Ogbewere, 2015).

Sanusi (2012) suggests that the challenges facing leadership within the public sector can be attributed to the lack of leadership skills and knowledge to execute and perform their leadership

duties effectively. Individuals in leadership roles are ill equipped in terms of ethic skills and lack the knowledge of fostering ethic-based behaviours on employees (Opara, 2014; Eliogu-Anenih, 2017). Opara (2014) also buttresses the effects of lack of quality leadership on the employee performance. Ejimabo (2013) emphasises the leadership skills gap within the Nigerian public sector. Leaders lack effective skills for the position they hold in the Eastern region of Nigeria. Figure 7. addresses the current impact of the leadership situation and the major challenges.

Figure 7: Impact of leadership situation in Nigeria and the major problems (Ejimabo, 2013)

In this regard, the major issue facing leadership within the Nigerian public sector are deep rooted on the ethical conviction of leaders at the helm of authority (Ogbewere, 2015; Opara, 2014). The lack of responsible and ethical leaders with integrity, vision, high moral values has been the stumbling block of Nigeria's development (Ogbewere, 2015). Leaders assigned to head the affairs of organisations are selected based on favouritism and ethnic lining. Individuals are not equipped with the right needed skills to foster public sector growth and economic

development. For Nigerian public sector to be successful in this era of local and global competition, they need to equip themselves with the most effective leadership skills required to drive performance. The Nigerian public sector needs the operationalisation and enforcement of an effective ethic-based and responsible leadership to stem the growth of corruption and foster performance both within employees and the organisation as a whole (Ejimabo, 2013; Fatile, 2013; Okpala & Enwefa, 2017).

4.6. Conclusion

This chapter has provided a detailed examination and exploration of Nigeria within the body of literature. Nigeria can be classified as a country with a thriving culture and diverse people with unique culture, values, region and a melting pot of variation of languages. Regarded as the most populous nation on the continent of Africa, the population of Nigeria stands at about 200 million people with an estimated population increase within the next decades placing the estimates at 400 million people doubling the current population. Whilst Nigeria can be described as nation with a thriving population and economy, findings from review of literature have addressed the challenges facing the nation are attributed to issues stemming from corruption which are visible within the major sectors of the economy mostly the public sector (Nwokorie, 2016; Anyim & Ufodiama, 2013; Opara, 2013; Egbuta, 2019; Adamu & Celik, 2019; Ofuani et al., 2018).

The Nigeria public sector can be regarded as one of the drivers of the Nigerian economy. Whilst a major driver in the productivity and a conduit of employment within the nation, findings from literature have highlighted several challenges facing the sector. These include economic, social-cultural, socio-political and the leadership factor. While factors have negatively influenced the growth of the Nigerian public sector, findings have asserted majority of these

challenges stems from the leadership standpoint. Some school of thought have addressed the Nigerian public sector problem is a direct result of leadership failure and the unwillingness or incapability of individuals in power to rise to their responsibility and the right behaviours to guide employees. The Nigerian public sector seemingly lacks such leadership. Findings from this review asserts this can be attributed to the complexities of the cultural diversities and problems of management in a constantly changing state of governance. In essence, due to the growing challenges facing Nigeria's public sector leaders mostly regarding lack of skills to influence performance and mitigate unethical behaviours.

CHAPTER FIVE: SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

5.1. Introduction

Several theories of leadership have provided some managerial insights regarding organisational effectiveness, performance, follower commitment and participation. Drawing on these theories, it is pivotal that in proffering effective leadership, strong moral inclination is required (Rost, 1995; Ciulla, 2004). While these forms do possess strong merits and foster a positive result, various studies have cited the short-falls and challenges facing these constructs within the last two decades as ethical mishaps and lack of ethical directions in guiding and attaining organisational goals (please refer to works by (Bormann, 2017; Trevino et al., 2003; Brown et al., 2005; Derr, 2012; Bello, 2012; De Hoogh & Den Hartog, 2008; Begley & Wong, 2001; Brown & Trevino, 2006)). In essence, it is paramount that studies examine the process involved in leading ethically and effectively and the skills important in the development of an effective ethical leader (Rost, 1991; Rost, 1995).

Ethical leadership within the last few decades has seen a considerable addition to the body of knowledge. While there exists a strong base regarding prior studies, the field is still in the nascent state and requires further exploration (Toor & Ofori, 2009; Trevino et al., 2003). Brown et al. (2005) posits ethical leadership as the demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through one's actions and interpersonal relationships, through the promotion of these conducts to followers adopting two-way communication, reinforcement, and decision-making. These influences a positive exchange process between the leader and followers, with a special focus on ethical behaviour e.g., through a positive effect of ethical leadership on follower ethical decision making or prosocial behaviour (Khuntia et al., 2004; Cumbo, 2009; Moritz & Voegtlin, 2012; Kanungo, 2001). Some studies have examined ethical leadership from the lens of its emergence, meta-analysis and consequences, a behavioural perspective and mediators, moderators and outcomes (Brown & Trevino, 2006; Ko et al., 2018; Bedi et al., 2016; Den

Hartog, 2015). However, given the extant literature on the various factors and perspectives associated with ethical leadership, a more systematic review and synthesis are essential to add to the body of knowledge and provide a way forward.

A systematic literature review attempts to identify, review and synthesise all the empirical evidence that meets pre-defined or pre-specified eligibility criteria to answer a given research question (Piper, 2013). The need for a systematic literature review is driven by the limitations and the lack of evidence-based data or studies done from narrative reviews (Nightingale, 2009; Piper, 2013; Wright et al., 2007; Harrsion et al., 2016). Traditional and unsystematic narrative reviews are more likely to include research selected by scholars based on favouritism, this gives way to the introduction of bias in the selection of literature. Therefore, authors who carry out traditional literature review frequently contradict available evidence and lag behind (Wright et al., 2007).

Moher et al. (2015) suggests SLR attempts to gather all relevant works that fit pre-defined eligibility criteria to answer specific research questions. This adopts explicit, systematic approaches to mitigate and reduce bias in the identification of relevant works, selection, synthesis, and the summation of studies. It provides reliable and evidence-based findings which are adopted in decision making and future direction if carried out effectively. This employs clear and transparent methods to perform an in-depth literature search and critical evaluation of individual studies and draws conclusions about what we currently know and do not know about a given subject, topic or question (Denyer & Tranfield, 2003).

The main characteristics of the systematic literature review (SLR) include

- A clearly stated set of objectives with an explicit, reproducible methodology.
- A systematic search procedure that attempts to identify all studies that would meet the eligibility criteria.

- Assessments of the legitimacy of the findings of the studies
- The systematic presentation, and synthesis of the characteristics and findings of the included studies or research works (Moher et al., 2015).

Systematic literature review proffers several advantages and benefit and has its limitations which can affect the conclusion of a study. Inadequate literature searches and heterogeneous studies can lead to false conclusions (Moher et al., 2015).

5.2. Systematic Literature Review Process

The figure below provides a step-by-step process of conducting a systematic review. Using the above graphical representation, a systematic literature review was done to proffer a better understanding of the concept of ethical leadership and the provision of an evidence-based approach to proffer future direction in the domain.

Figure 8: Step-by-Step Process of a systematic literature review (Lavallee et al. 2017)

5.2.1. Review planning phase

The development of a systematic literature as the name implies require a systemic and procedural review planning. This is highly important, as this must be repeatable. This requires a laid down plan of review efforts and training activities needed for a successful systematic literature review (Lavallee et al., 2014; Jahan et al., 2016). Prior to the embarkment of a thorough review procedure, a detailed scoping study of literature was conducted on the concept of ethical leadership to proffer a better understanding of the concept. This was done to provide critical background studies of work done, emerging trends, varying scholarly views on the construct of ethical leadership and the emerging perspective in the field. Furthermore, a detailed scoping study on the concept of leadership and the phenomenon of ethics as an integral part of leadership and ethical leadership was conducted. To provide a systematic review of literature, several trainings regarding attaining a successful review of literature were attended and feedback from experts in the field of leadership helped shape the planning phase.

5.2.2. Question Formulation and Definition

Having successfully reviewed the planning process, the next phase of the systematic literature review is the question formulation stage. Prior to this phase, a detailed narrative review of literature was conducted to provide a better understanding of the concept of ethical leadership, community interests in the field and to highlight a few gaps within the scholarly community. The concept of ethical leadership while not relatively new in the field of leadership has evolved in recent decades. Studies have examined context and various perspectives of these form of leadership via the leader's persona to the followers understanding and its link to organisational outcomes such as effective performance and employee commitments.

For a better understanding and a systematic flow, the formulation of critical research questions can be initiated with a very generic question, this is followed by the introduction of more

targeted questions as the domain becomes clearer and better understood (Lavallee et al., 2014; Briner & Denyer, 2012; Denyer & Tranfield, 2003). The CIMO (C- Context, I – Intervention, M – Mechanisms, and O - Outcomes) framework was employed in the formulation of the review questions. Some studies have explored several definitions, antecedents, mediators and carried out integrative reviews on the concept of ethical leadership (Brown et al., 2005; Freeman & Stewart, 2006; Cumbo, 2009; Walumbwa et al., 2011; Walumbwa & Schaubroeck, 2009; Kanungo, 2001; Resick et al., 2006; Brown & Mitchell, 2010; Trevino et al., 2000; Changsuk et al., 2018). Adopting a more generic to more targeted questions were employed in guiding the review questions and directing the flow of the systematic literature review (Lavallee et al., 2014).

The following questions form the basis for conducting the systematic literature review.

- **What is ethical leadership?**
- What are the perspectives adopted in examining ethical leadership?
- What are the skills required of an ethical leader?
- What are the hindrances and limitation to the implementation of ethical leadership framework?
- How does ethical leadership influence performance within organisations?

5.2.3. Search Strategies and Definition

A good search string should be able to retrieve all the relevant papers in the domain, as well as retrieve as few irrelevant papers as possible (Harris, et al., 2014; lavallee, et al., 2014). To further provide a sizeable amount of quality studies within the systematic review, a snow-balling approach was employed. This involves scanning the content of high-quality papers, thorough scrutinization and searching of the reference lists within these quality papers and

analysing the contents for relevant works to the studies or questions being reviewed (Lavallee et al., 2014). The Table 3 below gives a detailed outlook of keywords and search strings employed.

Table 3: Keywords and Search Strings

			SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW SEARCH STRINGS AND KEYWORDS
SEARCH STRINGS NUMBER			KEYWORDS
Search string 01			Ethical leader
Search string 1a			Ethic*
Search string 1b			leader*
			Moral*
Search string 1d			Developing
Search string 1e			Skills OR Competencies OR Abilities OR Prowess
Search string 02			Ethical leadership
Search string 2a			problems OR hindrances OR limitation
Search string 2b			lead*
Search string 2c			Ethical*
Search string 03			Ethical leadership
Search string 3a			Ethical*
Search string 3b			Leader*

Search string 3c			Influence OR Impact OR Affects OR foster
Search string 3d			Organisation
Search string 04			Ethical leadership
Search string 4a			Ethical*
Search string 4b			Define* OR Definition
Search string 05			Ethical Leadership
Search string 5a			Ethical* OR Moral*
Search string 5b			Leader*
Search string 5c			Perspective OR Approach

5.2.4. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The next phase of the systematic literature review was the development of the inclusion and exclusion criteria. In developing the criteria, focus and emphasis should be placed on the provision of quality and unbiased finding of works done in the related field of interest. The development of these procedures is highly pivotal in the systematic literature review. Furthermore, it is also important in the selection of relevant databases and search portals. The Table 4 below gives the number of databases selected for the systematic literature review. Selection criteria for the databases below is based on critical review of works done in the field of leadership and the adoption of these databases by scholarly works done in regard to the systematic literature review in leadership (Harrison et al., 2016; Frangieh & Yaacoub, 2017). Furthermore, these selected databases possess several critical journals, which are pivotal to the leadership field.

Table 4: Research Databases

Sage journals and publication	Emerald insight	Wiley online
Science Direct	Taylor and Francis online	
JSTOR	Springer link	

The next task adopted was the development of the inclusion criteria. To answer the review questions, the following inclusion criteria were employed

- All selected papers must be written in English.
- It must be from peer reviewed journals.
- Articles must adhere to the research field i.e., ethical leadership
- Abstracts and title must contain information needed in relation to the research field and review questions.

The next step is the definition of the exclusion criteria.

- Not written in English.
- Definition and abstract do not contain any relation to the research focus.
- Not a peer review journal.

Employing the search strings highlighted in the step process, advanced search syntaxes were adopted, and a search string “ethical leadership” was used. This turned over a total number of 726 search results comprising of articles, research titles, books and chapters. Implementation

of inclusion and exclusion criteria and search criteria restrictions were placed from a period spanning 1987-2020. The adoption of a 1987 start date for the systematic literature review is based on the earliest use and adaptation of ethical leadership within literature by Enderle (1987). Excluding book titles, conference papers and textbooks, the number of results were reduced to 565 research articles. This technique provides a more focused approach and concentration on research articles focusing on titles with “ethical leadership” and abstract with “ethical leadership”. This method was also adopted on the other selected databases. Many articles were discovered and adopting the search strings, inclusion and exclusion criteria of the results were minimized to a total number of 150 papers. Utilisation of a snow-balling procedure to examine papers obtained and extraction of papers not discovered through the SLR process produced a total number 13 papers. This brought the papers to a total of 163 papers found. Further examination of these papers was carried out and duplicates removed (29 duplicate papers) bringing the total number of relevant papers to 135 articles. The systematic literature process was concluded on the 20th of November 2020. Table 5 gives the themes outcome of the systematic literature review.

Table 5: Themes identified from the SLR

Themes	Authors
Ethical leadership Definition	Brown et al.,2005; Bello 2012; Picollo et al., 2010; Mihelic et al 2010; Yukl 2010; Freeman & Stewart 2006
Perspectives of Ethical leadership	Brown et al., 2005; Freeman & Stewart, 2006; Cumbo, 2009; Walumbwa et al., 2011; Walumbwa & Schaubroeck, 2009; Kanungo, 2001; Resick, et al., 2006; Brown & Mitchell, 2010; Trevino et al., 2000; Waggoner, 2010; Trevino et al., 2000; Freeman & Stewart, 2006; Cuilla, 2004; Trevino et al., 2003; Yukl et al ,2013; Mihelic et al. 2010; Heres & Lasthuizen, 2013; Cooper & Denzel, 2013; Othman & Rahman 2014; Eisenbeiss, 2012; Eisenbeiss & Knippenberg, 2015; Bouckenoghe et al., 2015; Atiya et al., 2015; Gils et al., 2015; Bormann, 2017; Bello, 2012; Kim &

	<p>Brymer, 2011; Zehir & Erdogan, 2011; Elci et al., 2012; Madanchian et al., 2016; De Hoogh & Den Hartog, 2008; Hassan et al., 2013; Demirtas & Akdogan, 2015; Muhammad et al., 2016; Heres & Lasthuizen, 2010; Hassan et al., 2013; Heres & Lasthuizen, 2013; Heres & Lasthuizen, 2012; Khuntia et al., 2004; Flite & Harman, 2013; Makaroff et al., 2014; Kaptein et al., 2005; Atiya et al., 2015; Kalshoven et al., 2011; Walumbwa & Schaubroeck, 2009; Emery, 2016; Hoogervorst, 2011; Zhu et al., 2004; Cheteni & Shindika, 2017; Bello, 2012; Obicci, 2015; Temple, 2011; Ezimma, 2010; Martin et al., 2009; Begley & Wong, 2001; Tian, 2013</p>
<p>Skills</p>	<p>Rubin et al. 2010; Amisano & Anthony, 2017; Haq, 2011; Hamilton, 2009; Brown et al., 2005; Trevino et al., 2000; Zhu., 2014; Kacmar et al., 2013; Harvey et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2018; Voegtlin, 2016; Ellis, 2006; Whitton, 2008; Cisma et al., 2016; Ellis 2016; Racette, 2011; Brown et al., 2005; Ncube & Wasburn., 2006; Nikoi.,</p>

	<p>2008; Mahsud et al., 2010; Hassan et al., 2013; Resick et al., 2011; Brown & Trevino, 2014; Trevino et al 2003; Brown & Mitchell, 2010; Hassan et al., 2013; Kavathatzopoulos, 2014;Here & Lasthuzien, 2013; Firsch & Huppenbauer, 2014</p>
<p>Limitations and Hinderance</p>	<p>Quade et al, 2017; Greenbaum et al., 2015; Kalshoven et al., 2016; Temple, 2012;Stouten et al., 2013; Miao et al., 2013; Babalola et al., 2016, Evans et al., 2016; Gok et al., 2017; Jones & Lasthuzien, 2018;Backhordari-Sharifabad et al., 2017; Fulmer, 2004</p>
<p>Influence of Ethical leadership on Performance</p>	<p>Bouckenooghe et al., 2015; Bello, 2012; Elci et al., 2012; Hassan et al., 2014; Khokar & Zia-Ur-Rehman, 2017; Liu et al., 2012; Potipiroon & Faerman, 2016; Yidong & Xinin, 2013; Butts et al., 2016; Brymer & Kim, 2011; Khalid, 2014; Khademfar & Amiri, 2013; Agbim, 2018; Leung et al, 2014; Shin et al., 2014; (Demirtas & Akdogan, 2015;Mayer et al., 2009; Avey et</p>

	al., 2011; Ogunfowora, 2014; Kalshoven et al., 2011; Stouten et al., 2013
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5.3. Systematic Literature Review Results

5.3.1. Descriptive Analysis

Out of the total number of papers selected for the systematic literature review, 62% (83 papers) are empirical in nature, 21% (32 papers) are conceptual and 12% (20 papers) are review oriented (refer to figure 9). Furthermore, observation of selected studies shows 58% (63 papers) are quantitative, 9% (11 papers) are qualitative, while 3% (9 papers) adopted a mixed research method (please refer to figure 10). Further analysis of empirical works shows 85% adopted a questionnaire approach for data collection, 13% adopted the interview method and 2% employed case study approach (refer to figure 11).

Figure 9: Types of Study

Figure 10: Research Type

Figure 11: Mode of Data Collection

5.3.1.1. Sources of Literature

Out of the 135 papers identified from the SLR outcome, many of these studies have been published in several journals. Of these journals, the Journal of Business Ethics stood out with the highest number of articles. The table 6 shows the journal articles with a minimum of two publications in the systematic literature review. Figure 12 gives a demographic breakdown of studies and highlight the focus of location-based research. From the figure, the United States of America holds the highest focal point of research done in ethical leadership.

From this analysis, it is evident there exists a large focus on the western perspective of ethical leadership and the adaptation of ethical leadership towards the western demography. Furthermore, this implies understanding of ethical leadership both within definition, behaviours, influence and impact on employees and organisations are driven by studies carried out within this demography. There exists a clear rational and need to explore ethical leadership from other demographics (Resick et al., 2006). Providing a better and detailed understanding from other demographics will proffer more knowledge on the universality of ethical leadership behaviours, and the antecedents and outcomes of ethical leadership within these communities

Table 6: Journal Article Sources

Journals	Number of Articles
Journal of Business Ethics	33
The Leadership Quarterly	14
Canadian Journal of Administrative Science	4
Business Ethics Quarterly	3

Academy of Management Journal	3
Journal of Leadership and Organisational Studies	3
Journal of Managerial Psychology	2
Journal of Social Psychology	2
International Journal of Public Administration	2
International Journal of Business and Management	2
Human Relations	2
Asia Pacific Journal of Public Administration	2
Journal of Leadership, Accounting and Ethics	2

Figure 12: Demography of Studies

5.3.2. Studies with the Highest Number of Citations

Figure 13. identifies the top five articles with the highest number of citations. The most cited article is Brown, Trevino and Harrison (2005) with 3071 citations. This can be attributed to the definition provided by the authors on the concept of ethical leadership, attributes and the development of ethical leadership construct.

Figure 13: Top Five Most Cited Articles

5.4. Qualitative Results and Analysis

This section gives a qualitative outcome of the systematic literature review process. Having carried out a quantitative examination, extraction of qualitative data and synthesis was done adopting a thematic approach. To answer the review questions employed in the SLR, the following subsections provide a thorough analysis.

5.4.1. How do we define ethical leadership?

Various authors have examined the concept of ethical leadership in literature but empirical research on what defines ethical leadership is scarce (Toor & Ofori, 2009). Despite the high number of the papers and research on ethics, discussions of ethics in regards to organisational studies have focused mainly on the concept of executive leadership and have inclined to hypothesise ethical leadership in very broad, vague and simple terms (Toor & Ofori, 2009; Trevino, et al., 2003).

Bello (2012) posits the concept of ethical leadership or an ethical leader as one who sets examples for others to follow and withstand temptation that may occur during their leadership. This definition of ethical leadership provides a simple conception of what ethical leadership entails but in essence sounds pretty vague and can be mistaken for a different form of leadership. Picollo et al. (2010) implies that an ethical leader must possess the traits of fairness, honesty, principle, and trustworthy in taking responsibility for their own actions, and use rewards and punishments where appropriate to hold subordinates responsible for their actions. Mihelic et al. (2010) suggests an ethical leader is an individual that lives up to the principle of conduct, moral values and strong ethics that are critical to the person. Yukl (2010) posits the construct of ethical leadership as one that possesses multiple diverse elements and ambiguity. An ethical leader is one who lives by a code for being principled, ethically moral and in essence guiding the followers under strict values and moral conduct.

Some researchers suggest the concept of ethical leadership as a leadership framework for guiding employees or followers in carrying out the right thing, accomplishing the right task at the right time while following laid down ethical guidelines (Freeman & Stewart, 2006; Mihelic et al., 2010) .

The concept of ethical leadership as a form of leadership emphasises the need for a leader to act morally right, morally good as opposed to a compliance for acting right by displaying altruism. To be an effective ethical leader, it is essential for an individual to display attributes of a good and effective leader by establishing and accomplishing goals and targets based on strong core ethical codes or beliefs (Cuilla, 2004). Ethical leadership is a descriptive and predictive approach that engages behaviours that are beneficial to followers and not detrimental, by inculcating moral principles into their beliefs, values and actions through ethical decision-making processes. These influences a positive exchange process between leader and followers, with a special focus on ethical behaviour e.g., through a positive effect of ethical leadership on follower ethical decision making or prosocial behaviour (Khuntia et al., 2004; Cumbo, 2009; Moritz & Voegtlin, 2012).

A more extensive and widely accepted definition of the concept of ethical leadership attributed to Brown et al. (2005, p.120) states that “**Ethical** leadership is the demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through personal actions and interpersonal relationships, and the promotion of such conduct to followers through two-way communication, reinforcement and, decision-making”.

This definition implies that ethical leadership is the type of leadership which involves the process of role-modelling in inculcating ethical morals with followers. Employees adapt and learn what behaviours are expected, rewarded and punished through the process of role modelling (Brown et al., 2005). While this definition provides a detailed connotation of the

concept of ethical leadership, several authors have highlighted a misconception, ambiguity and vagueness in this definition (Price, 2017; Eisenbeiss, 2012; Voegtlin, 2016). Furthermore, many scholars have discussed ethical leadership mostly from the view point of the theoretical and conceptual lens (Demirtas & Akdogan, 2015). A growing concern facing the definition of Brown et al. (2005) ethical leadership is that it is vague and does not address some critical concerns, aspects and issues of ethical leadership (Eisenbeiss, 2012). This is attributed to the misconception of what is regarded as the demonstration of *normatively appropriate* conduct.

Eisenbeiss (2012) posits the issues facing the definition provided by Brown et al. (2005) as indistinct due to issues arising in defining normative behaviours and the differentiation of what is classified as a normative behaviour across different cultural, organisational and societal context. This raises some concerns and questions of ethical leadership in relation to compliance and an individual personal moral belief. There exist some unanswered questions on what can be regarded as acceptable normative behaviours and how this impacts organisational standard as opposed to one's personal beliefs and moral codes. In essence, the definition of ethical leadership by Brown et al. (2005) do not seem adequate without having or highlighting a minimum requirement or sets of normative reference points that help in the evaluation of ethicality of conducts and the underlying values (Eisenbeiss, 2012).

Giessner & Quaquebeke (2011) also shed light on the definition provided by Brown et al. (2005, p.120) as a concern based on the scarcity of research on what is regarded or defined as "*normatively appropriate*". Giessner & Quaquebeke, (2011) is of the notion that Brown et al. (2005)'s work does not provide a lot to work with regarding what can be considered as normatively appropriate.

Voegtlin (2016) highlights a growing concern in the definition provided by Brown et al. (2005) as it does not provide enough and appropriate amount of guidance on how an effective ethical

leader should perform when these norms seem inadequate. This suggests that ethical leadership is subject to prevailing moral norms in a particular context and this is specifically the case when research deals with ethical questions of what is right or wrong (Voegtlin, 2016). Furthermore, the author highlights the challenges of ethical leadership as the definition adopted by Brown and colleagues focuses on the social learning perspective of ethical leadership in regard to leader-follower exchange and the idealism of role-modelling as the bases of a two-way communication. They do not highlight the specific norms of ethical behaviour.

Price (2017) addresses the challenges facing the adoption of Brown et al. (2005) definition. The concept of ethics in regard to ethical leadership from Brown's EL theory possesses some ill-defined concepts and it is more complicated in terms of definition to ethics itself. Furthermore, there are all kinds of norms ranging from norms of organisational effectiveness, rationality, manners, sport, etc. Ethics must therefore be understood as a subset of the normative perspective (Price, 2017).

In summary, while nine papers have provided some understanding of the definition of ethical leadership, only one empirical paper by Brown et al. (2005) have proposed a distinctive definition. This definition dating back to over a decade has provided several arguments within the field. In this regard, several authors have postulated for a more distinct and clearer definition (Voegtlin, 2016; Price, 2017; Eisenbeiss, 2012).

5.4.2. What are the perspectives adopted in examining ethical leadership?

The concept of ethical leadership as a criterion for meeting diverse ethical and moral issues and challenges facing organisations have spurred researchers to diversify the research work on ethical leadership. Outcome from the systematic literature review highlights six major perspectives identified within literature regarding ethical leadership. The following perspectives of ethical leadership identified, are the identity perspective, followers'

perspective, performance perspective, sectors perspective, behavioural perspective and the demographical perspective.

5.4.2.1. The Identity Perspective

The identity perspective of ethical leadership can be regarded as the viewpoint of research in relation to the personality of the leader. Early research work done in the field of ethical leadership focused on the personality conception of what defines an ethical leader (Brown et al., 2005; Freeman & Stewart, 2006; Cumbo, 2009; Walumbwa et al., 2011; Walumbwa & Schaubroeck, 2009; Kanungo, 2001; Resick, et al., 2006; Brown & Mitchell, 2010; Trevino et al., 2000). The identity perspective of ethical leadership provides a detailed conception of what an ethical leader entails, attributes and character that defines an ethical leader. Empirical studies highlight the difference between ethical leadership and other forms of leadership (Walumbwa & Schaubroeck, 2009; Waggoner, 2010; Trevino et al., 2000; Freeman & Stewart, 2006; Brown et al., 2005). Ethical leadership is regarded as a form of leadership which rests upon two major pillars namely, the moral person and the moral manager (Ciulla, 2004; Trevino et al., 2000).

Brown et al. (2005) adopts a social learning theory (Bandura, 1971) as a process through which ethical leaders influence followers through normatively appropriate conducts by influencing followers. They act as role-models to effect ethical, moral and through ethical decision-making. This involves exhibiting core traits, behaviours and ethical decision-making through visible actions. Ethical leaders exhibit traits of honesty, integrity and trustworthiness (Trevino et al., 2003; Brown et al., 2005; Resick et al., 2006).

A moral person must be able to make effective and ethical decisions (Trevino et al., 2000) . A moral manager must be able to transcend the qualities of a moral person and role model through exemplary actions, reward success of others and communicate ethics and values to the followers (Trevino et al., 2000). Resick et al. (2006) supports this line of thought proposed on

the traits and behaviour purported by Brown et al. (2005). Resick et al. (2006) pinpoints four key endorsements that contributes to the development of an effective ethical leader across different cultural perspectives. These four key endorsements are character/integrity, altruism, collective motivation and encouragement. In measuring ethical leadership, Yukl et al. (2013) proposed the inculcation of a behavioural measurement as an addition to traits as an improved scale for ethical leadership. Mihelic et al. (2010) highlights the personality attribute of an ethical leader within an organisational context with a strong focus on the integrity aspect of an effective ethical leader. The authors' work also provides a basis for the determinant of strong ethical behaviours of a leader within an organisation.

Some studies suggest that for one to be an ethical leader, one must possess ethical competence (Heres & Lasthuizen, 2013; Cooper & Denzel, 2013). An ethically competent person should possess the qualities and traits necessary for ethical leadership and should be able to provide such leadership in any given organisation. Cooper & Denzel (2013) equated an ethical competent person as an ethical leader as they should be able to lead, set examples and pass on their ethical competence to others in their organisation.

While it is essential, an effective ethical leader possesses strong ethical skills, ethical competency does not reflect an individual is an ethical leader. A person can be ethically competent without being an ethical leader, but not an ethical leader without being ethically competent (Heres & Lasthuizen, 2013). Ethical competence is the basis from which the leader can build and maintain a reputation for being a moral person. It provides the ethical leader with the necessary credibility and allows the leader to become an effective ethical role model to followers (Heres & Lasthuizen, 2013). This in essence stipulates the necessity for ethical competence as a prerequisite and an essential component of becoming an ethical leader as this is important in the development of an ethical leader persona (Kavathatzopoulos, 2012).

Othman & Rahman (2014) highlight five attributes of an effective ethical leader namely, accountability, responsive integrity, fairness, transparency disclosure and responsibility. Eisenbeiss (2012) focused on the development of an ethical leader from a central orientation. There exist limited studies examining setting ethical goals as a component of ethical leadership.

5.4.2.2. The Followers Perspective

The followers' perspective of ethical leadership highlights the effect of ethical leadership from the followers point of view. This approach evaluates how ethical leadership impacts the way followers adapt and behave in various organisational settings. This takes a focal discourse from the followers' side of ethical leadership. The concept of ethical leadership involves a two-way communication between leaders and followers (Brown et al., 2005). For ethical leadership to be effective, it is essential there exist a leader-member exchange (LMX) to foster channels for implementing ethical conducts and ethical decision-making (Brown et al., 2005; Toor & Ofori, 2009; Walumbwa & Schaubroeck, 2009). A vast number of research work on the followers perspective of ethical leadership have yielded better understanding of the effects and impacts of ethical leadership on the followers perception and followers' attitude (Eisenbeiss & Knippenberg, 2015; Bouckennooghe et al., 2015; Atiya et al., 2015; Gils et al., 2015; Bormann, 2017).

The way followers view an ethical leader plays an integral part on the overall effectiveness of any given organisation. Bormann (2017) emphasises the necessity and the re-evaluation of ethical leadership as it affects the way followers view leadership. The study highlights the change in follower's behavioural attitude and work engagement when faced with an unethical leader. While an unethical leader negatively affects the perception of followers towards work engagement, an effective ethical leader boosts the morale of followers to be committed to the

task assigned. Eisenbeiss & Knippenberg (2015) suggest that moral mindfulness and moral emotions affect the interrelation between ethical leaders and followers discretionary work behaviour. Followers are more inclined to moral information assigned by ethical leaders and process this information more determinedly. The positive implementation of ethical leadership within any given organisational context provides a psychological empowerment for employees in regard to positively affecting organisational output and performance (Atiya et al., 2015).

5.4.2.3. The Performance Perspective

The concept of ethical leadership as an integral part for influencing performance from the leaders, followers and the organisational aspect has been extensively examined in the field by various scholars (Bello, 2012; Kim & Brymer, 2011; Walumbwa et al., 2011; Piccolo et al., 2010; Bouckenooghe et al., 2015; Zehir & Erdogan, 2011). The performance perspective examines the concept of ethical leadership as a catalyst for influencing performance in the public, private and hybrid sphere of business. Empirical studies have highlighted the necessity for ethical leadership and its links to improving organisational performance and impacting overall organisational output. Several themes have been identified in literature with respect to ethics in propping efficiency and effectiveness. Several scholars highlight the link between ethical leadership and organisational effectiveness (Elci et al., 2012; Madanchian et al., 2016; De Hoogh & Den Hartog, 2008; Hassan et al., 2013; Piccolo et al., 2010). To attain organisational effectiveness, an effective ethical leader exhibits core ethical behaviours which in tandem affects the perception and the commitment of employees

Piccolo et al. (2010) highlights a distinctive link between ethical leadership behaviours of ethical leaders and an influence of motivation among employees within an organisational setting. This in turns leads to a highly motivated workforce to carry out organisational tasks effectively. Walumbwa et al. (2011) examine the criticality of the social learning construct as a mechanism through which ethical leadership effects followers. From their empirical study,

leader-member exchange (LMX) and self-efficacy are important overriding variables necessary for improving ethical leadership performance relationship with followers. Bello (2012) focused on the conception and the impact of ethical leadership on employee job performance. Bello's work highlights the characteristics of an effective ethical leader as a critical mechanism for followers to imbibe and emulate. This in turn improves the performance of employees within an organisation.

Several scholars have emphasised the role of ethical leadership in organisational performance based on its positive link with the promotion of organisational values, fostering ethical awareness, creating an ethical community and the development of an ethical culture within an organisation (Muhammad et al., 2016; Bouckenoghe et al., 2015; Demirtas & Akdogan, 2015; Kim & Brymer, 2011).

5.4.2.4. The Sectors Perspective

The sector perspective highlights the studies by scholars regarding ethical leadership in various sectors namely, public, private and hybrid sector. Research on ethical leadership in recent times have focused on the benefits and impacts from the private sector and profit-oriented organisations. Several scholars have identified the impact and inculcated various ethical leadership frameworks and benefits to the private sphere of business (Trevino et al., 2000; Heres & Lasthuizen, 2010; Hassan et al., 2013; Heres & Lasthuizen, 2013; Heres & Lasthuizen, 2012; Khuntia et al., 2004). Some studies have examined ethical leadership from the healthcare sector highlighting its benefits to improving work efficiency and creating ethical culture and awareness (Flite & Harman, 2013; Makaroff et al., 2014).

While there exists a substantial number of studies in the private sector, there has been limited research in the public sector regarding ethical leadership. Some studies have evaluated the effects of ethical leadership and its influence on ethics from the perspective of public servants

(Kaptein et al., 2005; Atiya et al., 2015). Furthermore, research done within the public sector do not highlight its impact and the implementation of ethical leadership and how ethical leadership improves performance and long-term sustainability in the public sector. It is essential for future works to focus on the implementation of ethical leadership from the developing world perspective as this provides a better understanding of how ethical leadership impacts public services outside of the western world.

5.4.2.5. The Behavioural Perspective

The behavioural perspective analyses the behavioural aspect of an effective ethical leader. To be an effective ethical leader, some studies suggest necessary behaviours to inculcate positive moral values and implement ethical decisions. Ethical behaviour can be regarded as an integral part of an ethical leader. Several studies have been done on the behavioural aspect of ethical leadership (Kalshoven et al., 2011; Walumbwa & Schaubroeck, 2009; Emery, 2016; Hoogervorst, 2011; Zhu et al., 2004; Bouckennooghe et al., 2015; Bormann, 2017). Leaders exhibit ethical behaviours when they are doing what is morally right, just, and good, and when they help boost followers' moral awareness and moral self-actualisation (Zhu et al., 2004).

Kalshoven et al. (2011) highlight the effects of ethical leadership behaviours on personality. Ethical leadership possesses a significant link with three important personality attributes namely, agreeableness; conscientiousness and emotional stability (Kalshoven et al., 2011). Of the three, agreeableness has been suggested as the most important predictor of an ethical leader (Kalshoven et al., 2011; Walumbwa & Schaubroeck, 2009). Another critical aspect of the behavioural perspective of an ethical leader is the ability of an ethical leader to display behaviours of fairness, self-sacrifice and be able to frown and issue discipline and dissent towards unethical behaviours (Emery, 2016; Brown et al., 2005; Trevino et al., 2000). Effective ethical leadership behaviours are essential in improving and boosting employee organisational commitment. Effective psychological behaviour from ethical leaders helps inspire trust, instil

sense of value and belonging within employees and foster effective communication between leaders and followers (Bouckenoghe et al., 2015; Zhu et al., 2004; Bormann, 2017; Brown et al., 2005).

5.4.2.6. The Demographic Perspective

While research have reached an advanced stage in other highlighted perspectives, the demographic perspective in recent times have majorly focused on one demographical aspect (Eisenbeiss, 2012). Empirical works carried out have focused solely on the western aspect of an effective ethical leader (Eisenbeiss, 2012; Khuntia et al., 2004). Some studies have focused on the developing world, but these works only highlight the theoretical aspect of the importance of ethical leadership. They lack the necessary empirical data to support the concept and the effectiveness of ethical leadership in developing countries (Cheteni & Shindika, 2017; Bello, 2012; Obicci, 2015; Temple, 2011; Ezimma, 2010).

Martin et al. (2009) highlight shared attributes (integrity, collective motivation and encouragement) of ethical leaders within two western countries namely, the United States of America and Germany. While there exist similar attributes within diverse cultures, there are disparities and differences in the conception of ethical leadership across various demographics (Martin et al., 2009; Begley & Wong, 2001; Tian, 2013).

5.5. What are the skills required of an ethical leader?

While the concept of ethical leadership is not relatively new and several advancements in this research field has yielded outstanding results in better understanding this form of leadership, there exist more room for advancement and further exploration due to the nascent state within literature. While traits and behaviour do play a critical role in the development of an effective leader, the necessity of the required leadership skills is highly critical in further developing and improving the role and efficiency within their specified organisations. Few works in relation

to the role of leadership skills and competencies have addressed the importance they play within organisational settings, public institutions and government.

Organisational leadership development programmes are generally geared toward developing functional and interpersonal proficiency, ignoring skills for navigating political and ethically ambiguous cultures or developing the moral facets (Rubin et al. 2010). While ethical leadership is driven by a leader's moral principles and core values, one must possess ethical competence or skills to foster follower commitment, motivation and in the long run organisational goals (Kavathatzopoulos, 2012; Heres et al., 2013). Directly and indirectly, followers are drawn by the skills possessed by leaders and are eager to acquire these skills. Out of the 135 reviewed papers, eight papers addressed one or two skills as a criterion for influence. Out of these eight papers, one focused directly on the skills aspect of ethics within public service leadership (Haq, 2011) but lack the empirical evidence to support these necessary skills.

While some of the scholars have emphasised the importance of developing the appropriate skills for becoming an ethical leader, there exists a scarcity in the number of studies focusing on the development of an ethical leader and the core skills necessary for influencing effective ethical leadership within organisations and society. Furthermore, some scholars have misrepresented the definition of skills within literature and adopted various terms to emphasise the concept. Some scholars adopt and misuse behaviours and characteristics to define the influence of an ethical leader when defining the skills perspective of ethical leadership. A large proportion of work lack a distinction of skills from behaviours when providing a definition of what makes an ethical leader. Table 7. highlights the misuse of behaviours and characteristics as skills for the development of effective ethical leadership.

Table 7: Identifiable misrepresentation of skills as behaviours and characteristics that influences an effective ethical leader

Ability to identify complex patterns of relationship and forecast future event from current developments (Amisano & Anthony, 2017; Haq, 2011)
Communicate and participate in dialogue with stakeholders. (Kavathatzopoulos., 2014)
Creative problem solving (Haq, 2011; Hamilton, 2009)
Defining and communicating ethics (Brown et al., 2005; Trevino et al., 2000;)
Effective planning, organising and problem solving (Amisano & Anthony, 2017)
Encouraging creative and critical thinking. (Zhu., 2014)
Navigate political environments which may make them effective members of the organisation. (Kacmar et al., 2013; Harvey et al., 2013)
Negotiation skills to reconcile differences among employee perspectives and establish mutually satisfying relationships (Zhang et al., 2018)
See past negative workplace environments and focus on their goals (Kacmar et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2018; Voegtlin, 2016)
Concern for the welfare of subordinates and willingness to protect, help, develop, and empower them (Ellis, 2006; Whitton, 2008)
Creativity, innovation and original thinking (Cisma et al., 2016; Ellis 2016; Racette, 2011)
Decision making skills (Brown et al., 2005; Ncube & Wasburn., 2006; Nikoi., 2008)

Empathy towards subordinates (Mahsud et al., 2010; Hassan et al., 2013; Resick et al., 2011; Brown & Trevino, 2014)
Ethical expectations are promoted to followers through two-way communication (Brown et al., 2005; Trevino et al., 2000; Trevino et al 2003; Brown & Mitchell, 2010)
Excellent knowledge and adaptability of effective decision-making processes (Ncube & Wasburn., 2006)
Helping followers build their strengths and developing concern for others (Trevino et al., 2014, Hassan et al., 2013)
High ethical confidence and trust to own skills and competence (Kavathatzopoulos, 2014)
Identification of the corporate common goals while recognising individual needs, goals and interests, and determining the appropriate outcomes for employees
Identify and further common goals while accepting the autonomy of individuals to pursue their own interests.
Implementation of ethical principles and obligations. (Zhu, Han.,2014; Kavathatzopoulos., 2014; Here & Lasthuzien, 2013)
Instil pride in followers for being associated with the ethical values, norms and practice. (Zhang et al., 2018; Zhu, 2014)
Moral/Ethical intelligence (Firsch & Huppenbauer, 2014)

Seeking differing perspectives when solving ethical problems (Firsch & Huppenbauer, 2014; Haq, 2011;)
Setting up vision (Zhang et al., 2018; Zhu, 2014; Kavathatzopoulos., 2014)

5.6. What are the hindrances and limitations to the implementation of ethical leadership framework?

While majority of studies in the field of ethical leadership have focused on the positive impact and the direct effects on leader's personal outlook, employee and organisation. Few works have highlighted the boundaries and delimits of ethical leadership within the research community. Some scholarly works in recent times have attributed some curvilinear effects on employees and organisations (Stouten et al., 2013; Miao et al., 2013). Furthermore, some studies examine the challenges facing a clash in values and beliefs of both the ethical leader and followers within organisations. The table 8 below gives a summative outlook and recurring themes regarding impediments and challenges facing the ethical leadership framework.

Table 8: Impediments and Challenges facing the implementation of Effective ethical leadership framework

Little or no effective communication of ethics and values (Trevino et al., 2003; Greenbaum et al., 2015)
Lack of visible ethical display and making private ethical decisions (Greenbaum et al, Trevino et al., 2003;)
Lack of ethical influence (Greenbaum et al., 2015)

Disregard and lack of moral influence and competence by moral leaders (Trevino et al., 2003)
Failure to communicate ethical expectations and refrain from serving as visible ethical role models (Greenbaum et al., 2015)
Perceived threat to career and social goals (Greenbaum et al., 2015)
Threat to leader's integrity (Greenbaum et al., 2015)
High levels of (a) role stressors, (b) reduced short-term performance, (c) supervisor-directed deviance. (Quade et al., 2017; Greenbaum et al., 2015; Kalshoven et al., 2016)
Absence of ethical culture and lack of recurrent ethic-based training of employees (Fulmer, 2004)
Induced stress by supervisors and job-related stress (Quade et al., 2017)
Doubt in ethical leader's behaviour and act (Not Walking the Talk) (Fulmer, 2004)
Organisational constraint and philosophy (Backhordari-Sharifabad et al., 2017)
Pressure to deliver performance output (Babalola et al., 2016; Greenbaum et al., 2015)
Differentiation in ethical beliefs and moral values (Stouten et al., 2013; Miao et al., 2013; Babalola et al., 2016, Evans et al., 2016; Gok et al., 2017).

Job autonomy (Stouten et al., 2013; Miao et al., 2013, Greenbaum et al., 2015).
Ethical distress from organisational policies (Backhordari-Sharifabad et al., 2017)
Societal constraint (Temple, 2012; Backhordari-Sharifabad et al., 2017; Fulmer, 2004; Brown and Mitchell, 2010)
Organisational culture constraint (Jones & Lasthuzien, 2018; Backhordari-Sharifabad et al., 2017; Temple, 2012)
Religious commitments (Backhordari-Sharifabad et al., 2017; Temple, 2012)

While there exist, vast studies referencing the positive outcomes of ethical leadership, few scholars have examined the challenges and impediments facing the concept of ethical leadership. (Quade et al, 2017; Greenbaum et al., 2015; Kalshoven et al., 2016; Temple, 2012; Backhordari-Sharifabad et al., 2017; Fulmer, 2004; Brown and Mitchell, 2010). Majority of works done in this regard have taken a conceptual approach and little done with respect to empirical works (Stouten et al., 2013; Miao et al., 2013; Babalola et al., 2016, Evans et al., 2016; Gok et al., 2017).

One major drawback affecting the effectiveness of ethical leadership frameworks within organisations has been a lack of effective communication mechanism and link between leaders, followers and stakeholders (Trevino et al., 2003; Greenbaum et al., 2015). As one of the most crucial elements in leadership facets, leaders who lack the skills of communication of ethical guidelines, behaviours and values affect the overall effectiveness within organisations.

Individuals with management roles who fail to communicate reduce employee perception of ethical leadership and indirectly creates an unethical atmosphere within organisations.

Furthermore, lack of effective communication between both leaders and followers also affects the leader's ability to make sound and effective decisions. Due to lack of ethical display (role-modelling), leaders are perceived low in ethical values. The lack of communication by leaders who fail to foster ethical behaviours in followers creates an avenue for employees to engage in organisational deviant behaviours.

Another impediment facing the effectiveness of an ethical leadership framework within organisations is the curvilinear effects of leaders perceived as highly ethical within organisations (Stouten et al., 2013; Miao et al., 2013; Babalola et al., 2016). Some scholars have attributed the indirect negative effect of ethical leadership on employee's voice and role engagement (Stouten et al., 2013).

5.7. How Does Ethical Leadership Influence Performance?

Major empirical studies have focused on the influence of ethical leadership within private and hybrid sectors. Studies have majorly focused on the focal point on the effects and influence this leadership construct proffers to the total outlook of subordinate and organisational performance (Butts et al., 2016; Brymer & Kim, 2011; Khalid, 2014; Khademfar & Amiri, 2013; Agbim, 2018; Leung et al, 2014; Shin et al., 2014). Several researchers have provided pivotal breakthroughs in further understanding the role and importance of ethicality within the concept of leadership and how this impact both organisation reputation and climate (Demirtas & Akdogan, 2015; Shin et al., 2014; Leung et al., 2014; Zhu, 2014;).

Research within the field of management have highlighted the pivotal role leadership qualities, skills and behaviours play in the prediction of job satisfaction, employee motivation and organisational performance (Bouckenooghe et al., 2015; Bello, 2012; Elci et al., 2012; Hassan

et al., 2014; Khokar & Zia-Ur-Rehman, 2017; Liu et al., 2012; Potipiroon & Faerman, 2016; Yidong & Xinin, 2013). While majority of scholarly works focused mostly on the employee aspect of performance in relations to ethical leadership. There exists scarcity of works in respect to the influence of ethical leadership on overall organisational performance. Some researchers have attributed the positive influence of ethical leadership on the reduction of business incurred cost (Bouckennooghe et al., 2015). Several studies have examined the impact of ethical leadership and its positive influence on fostering organisational citizenship behaviour both on the individual and organisational level (OCBI and OCBO) (Avey et al., 2011; Ogunfowora, 2014; Kalshoven et al., 2011; Stouten et al., 2013). Furthermore, some works have attributed the positive effect and trickle-down influence of top management ethical leadership through the mediating role of supervisors in fostering employee involvement, commitment and in the long run performance (Mayer et al., 2009). Drawing upon Bandura's social learning theory, ethical leaders act as role models and these influences follower's attitudes towards expected values and achieving the desired end goals.

Some scholarly works suggest the positive influence of ethical leadership on the provision and the alignment of leader-member goal congruence and psychological capital as critical indicators and effective mechanism (catalyst) for determining employee job performance (Bouckennooghe et al., 2015). Ethical leaders foster trust through interpersonal mechanisms which in turn leads to employee willingness, job satisfaction and roles within decision-making policies. Furthermore, some studies have provided empirical results on the benefit and the mediated effect and influence of ethical leadership through corporate social responsibility (CSR) to improving operational performance, firm performance and economic performance (Leung et al., 2014).

Ethical leaders through their normative ethical conduct and behaviours and through communication mechanisms proffer a positive effect on follower's exertions through the

mediation of task significance. By fostering employees voice in organisational decisions and decision-making processes, using rewards to encourage ethical behaviour and punishment to discourage unethical behaviours, and injecting ethical values through communication skills and mechanism in regular business activity, ethical leaders enrich the autonomy and significance of work (Khalid, 2014; Khademfar & Amiri, 2013). This in turn leads to employee job performance. Few studies have signified the role of ethical leadership influence on long term performance and sustainability while addressing the drawbacks of ethical leadership in respect to short-term goals. Ethical leadership also foster reduction in employee absenteeism and helps mitigate the effect of deviant behaviours from employees.

The table 9 below gives a detailed representation of the influence of ethical leadership on both employee and organisational performance.

Table 9: Influence of Ethical leadership on performance

Organisation citizenship behaviour (Avey et al., 2011; Ogunfowora, 2014; Kalshoven et al., 2011; Stouten et al., 2013).
Leadership effectiveness (Potipiroon & Faerman, 2016; Yidong & Xinin, 2013)
Reduction in employee deviance (Avey et al., 2011; Babalola et al., 2016; Mayer et al., 2009; Stouten et al., 2013)
Firm reputation (Leung et al., 2014)
Job satisfaction (Bouckenooghe, et al., 2015; Demirtas & Akdogan, 2015)
Improved ethical climate and culture (Bai et al., 2017; Demirtas & Akdogan, 2015;)
Employee task performance (Hansen, 2011; Liu et al., 2013; Piccolo et al., 2010; Potipiroon & Faerman, 2016; Walumbwa et al., 2012)
Reduction in employee absenteeism (Hassan et al., 2014)

Employee commitment (Brymer & Kim, 2011; Abuzaid, 2018; Agha et al., 2017; Demirtas & Akdogan, 2015; Evans et al., 2016; Hansen et al., 2016; Hassan et al., 2013; Kalshoven et al., 2011; Khokar & Zia-Ur-Rehman, 2017)
Organisation promotability (Rubin et al., 2010)
Employee voice (Bai et al., 2017; Huang & Patterson, 2017; Stouten et al., 2013;)
Improved corporate social responsibility (Leung et al., 2014)

5.8. Gaps Identified within Literature

Ethical leadership is one of the most widely explored form of leadership theory in the last few decades spanning from the understanding and ground works of what it entails to the impact towards both efficiency and follower's effectiveness (Brown & Mitchell, 2010; Brown & Trevino, 2006; Brown et al., 2005; Eisenbeiss, 2012; Demirtas & Akdogan, 2015; Giessner & Quaquebeke, 2011; Kavathatzopoulos, 2012; Mihelic et al., 2010; Yukl et al., 2013; Piccolo et al., 2010). While these works have provided a grounded establishment of the concept of ethical leadership, this concept is still within its nascent stage and proffers various avenue for further exploration. The following gaps were identified within the body of literature from the systematic literature review. These gaps are classified into four distinct categories namely, methodological gaps, demographical gap, empirical gaps and theoretical gaps.

5.8.1. Methodological Gap

There are several methodological gaps within the body of literature. Exploration of literature has shown there exists no work done with regards to the implementation of a systematic

literature review. Works done within the field have adopted a traditional approach to developing a literature review. It is essential to the domain of ethical leadership that a thorough, unbiased and detailed review of literature is conducted to provide an unbiased view of ethical leadership.

Regarding the methods of research employed in the field of ethical leadership, most empirical studies tend to adopt the quantitative form of research as their choice to better understand the impact of ethical leadership within organisations (please refer to figure 10). There exist a limited number of qualitative (interviews) form of research within the community. There is more avenue and room to explore qualitative research to get a better understanding of the human factor and to address the shortcoming of the quantitative form of research.

5.8.2. Demographical Gap

From the demographical aspect of research done in the field of ethical leadership, strong focus has been placed specifically from the Western and Eastern perspective of ethical values, norms, and culture. There exists scarcity of empirical studies on ethical leadership from the sub-Saharan region, with most studies from this region (mostly African perspective) focused on the conceptual spectrum. While few works have attributed and compared the concept of ethical leadership from several geographical perspectives (please refer to Resick et al., 2006; Eisenbiess, 2012; Eisenbiess & Brodbeck, 2014), these works only highlight the personal attributes of an ethical leader or the concept of ethical and non-ethical leadership among these geographical arrays.

Further empirical research is necessary to proffer better understanding of the African cultural values, norms and understanding of what constitutes morality and ethicality in the private and public organisation and its impact on ethical leadership. Temple (2012) outlines the metaphysical challenges of ethical leadership effectiveness within the African perspective,

while this paper provides some insight, it lacks empirical evidence to support these viewpoints. Empirical focus is necessary to understand the mediation and effect of cultural views on what is regarded as “morally wrong and ethically right” behaviours and its mediating links and effects of ethical leadership on organisational outcomes. Out of the 135 papers reviewed; 11 papers placed emphasis on the developing world perspective (see Table 10).

Table 10: Ethical leadership from a Developing world perspective

Authors	Location
Agbim, K C (2018)	Nigeria
Agha, C N; Nwekpa, K C and Eze, O R (2017)	Nigeria
Babalola, T M; Stouten, J; Camps, J and Euwema, M (2016)	Nigeria
Bello, M S (2012)	Nigeria
Cheteni & Shindika (2017)	South Africa and Botswana
Mitonga-Monga, J; Flotman, A and Cilliers, F (2016)	Congo
Nnabuiife, E K N (2010)	Nigeria
Nwagbara, U (2016)	Nigeria
Obicci, P A (2014)	Uganda
Prozesky, M (2016)	Lesotho and South Africa
Temple (2012)	Africa

5.8.3. Empirical Gaps

From the empirical standpoint, there are several gaps within the body of ethical leadership literature. The systematic literature review outcome has highlighted some deficiency with regards to empirical evidence in relation to the development of ethical leadership skills. While the systematic literature review has highlighted few works, skills needed for the development of ethical leadership within the community are scarce. There exist gaps within literature of the role these skills play in the attainment of positive ethical leadership outcomes.

Furthermore, only one work provided a basis for ethic-based skill (Haq, 2011) but it lacks empirical support. Several authors have attributed the mediation of certain skills as important for organisational values, firm reputation and organisation performance (Zhu, 2014; Brown et al., 2005; Ncube & Wasburn., 2006; Nikoi., 2008; Kacmar et al., 2013; Ellis, 2016; Harvey et al., 2013; Haq, 2011; Kavathatzopolous, 2012; Rubin et al. 2010). There exist several shortcomings in understanding how these skills are developed and how they are utilised. Question lie within literature on what skills are regarded as critical for effective ethical leadership and how does this directly or indirectly relate to organisational targets and goals (outcomes). Rubin et al. (2010) posit the disregard of skills within the development of ethical leadership concept. Further research is necessary to provide better understanding of ethical leadership skills as a role modelling tool for organisational performance.

Secondly, empirical findings have shown the positive outcome of ethical leadership on employee and organisational performance. While these are vital impacts needed by organisations from the leadership point of view, there exist gaps in the relation and link between ethical leadership and its direct and indirect effects towards employee commitment.

Thirdly, while some studies have examined the positive outcome of ethical leadership within public, private and hybrid sphere, researchers have been biased towards understanding the

drawbacks of ethical leadership. Few studies have identified negative effects or challenges in the implementation of ethical leadership (linear and curvilinear effect) on employee behaviour, employee performance and stakeholder challenges (please refer to works by Gok et al., 2017; Stouten et al., 2013; Greenbaum et al., 2015; Brown & Mitchell, 2010; Evans et al., 2016, Quade et al., 2017; Babalola et al., 2016; Miao et al., 2013). These works highlight a growing discourse that require critical attention for effective implementation of ethical leadership framework.

There is a growing need to further investigate the antecedents of leaders perceived as ethical in the early stages becoming amoral or unethical leaders in the latter stages (Greenbaum et al., 2015). It is important for studies to investigate the factors influencing ethical leaders becoming unethical, what mediate unethical behaviours from ethical leaders and how do ethical leaders negatively affect employees with high ethical awareness.

5.8.4. Theoretical Gaps

From a theoretical standpoint, there are several gaps within the body of ethical leadership literature. Firstly, several authors have outlined the challenges facing the definition of ethical leadership within literature (Voegtlin, 2016; Price, 2017; Eisenbeiss, 2012). The only definitive understanding of what ethical leadership entails was proposed by Brown et al. (2005) and authors have highlighted the confusing and vague nature to which the definition proposes. It is highly essential to provide a critical and validated definition of ethical leadership.

A growing number of empirical studies conducted on ethical leadership has focused on the private sector perspective of ethical leadership antecedents, mediators and outcomes within the research community. Most studies on ethical leadership conceptualisation and operationalisation have taken two main organisational perspectives namely, the private and hybrid settings. While more empirical findings are conducted within private organisations and

for-profit ventures, there appears to be limited empirical research on ethical leadership antecedents and outcomes regarding employee performance and organisational performance within the public sector. There exists a scarcity on the impact within the public-sector perspective. While some research has been carried out in the public-sector, these works are minimal and less detailed compared to the private sector. The need for more focus on public-sector ethical leadership presents a viable niche for further empirical studies. The figure 14 provides a graphical representation of the organisation focus by prior studies.

Figure 14: Distribution of organisational focus on ethical leadership

5.9. Conclusion

This chapter has explored the field of ethical leadership through the adoption of the systematic literature review of existing body of work in literature. As highlighted within this chapter, this

was conducted adopting a step-by-step process in order to proffer a methodology which is reproducible (Denyer & Tranfield, 2003; Moher, et al, 2015; Harrison et al., 2016). This systematic review of literature involved a detailed and comprehensive search of core literature from a number of academic databases with the utilisation of defined research protocols such as the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Several papers were excluded which did not meet the criteria. This search outcome of this review yielded 135 ethical leadership papers which were then subjected to a quantitative and qualitative analysis. The findings from the qualitative and quantitative analysis were reported to proffer a description of literature and identify themes within ethical leadership.

The findings from the thematic analysis identified several gaps within the body of literature in the field of ethical leadership. From the findings, it is evident that there exists a scarcity of empirical literature in understanding the mechanism for leaders to influence ethical leadership on followers. Whilst literature have emphasised the behavioural perspective of an ethical leader asserting the notion and view point that ethical leaders possess behaviours to be perceived as ethical from followers, there exist a shortage of literature in the skills perspective of what makes an ethical leader. Furthermore, literature have elucidated the misconception of some behaviours as skills in the development of an ethical leader. Further findings from the systematic literature review have identified challenges facing the implementation of an effective ethical leadership framework. Whilst scholarly works from the outcome of the SLR did elucidate these challenges, they fail to provide empirical avenues in mediating these challenges.

There is a need for an ethical leadership skills empirical study as this is absent within the field. Furthermore, many studies have addressed the developed world perspective and mainly the private sector. There are limited empirical studies focusing on the developing country perspective (Africa) and the public sector. This study aims to address this gap in literature.

The research methodology employed in this study is presented in the next chapter.

CHAPTER SIX: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

6.1. Introduction

The concept of research can be emphasised as a logical and systematic approach to proffer new, insightful and evocative information to a specific issue or topic through the adoption of a tailored methodology in any research field. This involves a systemic process and provision of a platform for discussion, evaluation and basis for methods and principles adopted within a subject area (Horn, 2011; Rajasekar, et al., 2013). Research in leadership have over time employed a wide range of research methods although the diversification in method can be considered relatively recent in terms of origin. The adoption of a single method of data collection; the self-completion/self-administered questionnaire have largely dominated the field of leadership in exploring leadership processes, behaviours and its outcomes. (Bryman, 2011; Conger, 1998). Several studies have asserted the dominance and over-reliance of a single methodology in the study of leadership (Bryman, 2011; Conger, 1998; Bryman, 2004; Avolio, et al., 2009). In the field of leadership today, the adoption of a qualitative approach remains relatively rare (Conger, 1998).

While previous research in the field of leadership have been dominated by a single method of choice, understanding the complexity of the leadership phenomenon and providing greater insight requires the exploration of different methods of research as a source of rich data (Conger, 1997). Furthermore, the adoption of a research methodology should be guided by the research purpose and research objectives (Jonker & Pennick, 2010). This chapter presents the research methodology of this study. In this chapter, the rationale for the adoption of these selected choices will be discussed including the research philosophy, research approach, the research method, participant recruitment processes, data analysis, quality assessment and the ethical consideration.

The sole purpose for this doctoral research is to examine the concept of ethical leadership from the context of the Nigerian public sector. To accomplish the aim of this study, the following objectives guided the methodological course of this research. These are.

1. To examine the current conceptualisation of ethical leadership.
2. To identify the ethic-based challenges facing leaders within the Nigerian public sector.
3. To provide a skill-based ethical leadership framework within the Nigerian public sector.
4. To investigate the influence of ethical leadership skills on performance in the Nigerian public sector.

To ensure the purpose and the objectives of this study was actualised, key questions were provided to guide this research study and to provide quality findings and answers to the problem definition. These questions are.

1. How do we define the concept of ethical leadership?
2. What are the required skills necessary for an effective ethical leader?
3. What are the perspectives adopted in literature in examination of ethical leadership?
4. What are the hinderances and limitations to the implementation of an ethical leadership framework?
5. How does ethical leadership influence performance within an organisation?

6.2. Research Philosophy

Research philosophy is the belief or path in which data about an event or phenomenon are collated, analysed and used (Saunders, 2009). Saunders (2009) asserts research philosophy as a system of beliefs and assumptions about the development of knowledge. This acts as a guide for researchers to follow. There are various philosophies guiding research namely,

interpretivism, positivism, realism and pragmatism (Saunders & Tosey, 2013). However, the two major philosophies are positivism and interpretivism and are discussed below.

6.2.1 Positivism

There are several issues posing a challenge to the definition of positivism within literature (Heidtman et al., 2000). Heidtman et al. (2000) address three distinct challenges to the definition. Firstly, there are several different meanings of positivism understood as methodology or as metatheory. Secondly, positivism proffers a different meaning and dimension to philosophers and to sociologists. Thirdly, especially for social scientists, positivism is often associated with and understood as a philosophical doctrine developed by August Comte, and further continued by his followers (Heidtman et al., 2000).

Positivism refers to the theory of knowledge which asserts the pursuit of causal explanation by way of inductive generalisation and that the only kind of sound knowledge available is that of science grounded on observation (Heidtman et al., 2000). Positivism philosophy argues that reality exists externally and must be investigated through the rigorous process of scientific inquiry (Creswell, 2013; Ali & Chowdhury, 2015). Positivism is based on three principles within the field of social science (Heidtman et al., 2000; Ali & Chowdhury, 2015).

- The ontological principle of phenomenalism (knowledge can be established on experience alone).
- The methodological principle of the unity of the scientific method (measures of natural science are directly applicable to the social world with the goal of establishing invariant laws or generalizations about social phenomena).

- The axiological principle of neutrality (refuses to grant normative statements the status of knowledge and maintains a rigid separation between facts and values) (Heidtman et al., 2000).

Positivism follows the concept of empiricism where progress is made from observation to verification by means of experimental and scientific methods. This view of empirical facts is quantified and correlated to generate universal statements or laws about the world (Ali & Chowdhury, 2015).

From the point of view of interpretivist or post-positivist critics, the positivist approach to social science is philosophically inappropriate for studying social phenomena (Ali & Chowdhury, 2015; Heidtman et al., 2000). For them, the scientific approach which positivism embodies is inadequate when it comes to learning about how people understand the world and interact with its elements. Furthermore, critics argue that positivism does not provide rich information on a phenomenon. (Chowdhury, 2014; Walsham, 1995; Elster, 2007).

6.2.2. Interpretivism

An interpretive philosophy provides a better understanding of a given phenomenon from an individual's perspective and an investigation of interactions among individuals within the historical and cultural context they live in (Creswell, 2013). Interpretivist scholars argue that only through a subjective interpretation of and intervention in reality can that reality be fully understood. Saunders et al. (2009) state that interpretivism is necessary for researchers to understand differences between humans in their roles as social actors.

Interpretivist philosophy is directly linked to the study of social phenomena in their natural environment. It focuses on conducting research amongst individuals rather than on objects, adopting an empathetic stance to understand their social world and the connotation they give to it from their point of view (Saunders & Tosey, 2013). Unlike the positivists, the interpretivist

researcher considers research is value bound, what is being researched being a purpose of a set of conditions and individuals at a specific time. Data collection and analysis are, therefore, likely to involve qualitative data from in-depth investigations with small samples (Saunders & Tosey, 2013; Creswell, 2013). Interpretivists look for meanings and motives behind people's actions like behaviour and interactions with others in the society and culture (Chowdhury, 2014; Walsham, 1995; Elster, 2007).

In the view of interpretivism, it is argued that value free data cannot be obtained, since the researchers utilise their own preconceptions to guide the process of research. Furthermore, the researcher interacts with the human subjects of the enquiry, changing the perceptions of both parties (Walsham, 1995; Chowdhury, 2014). Interpretivist researchers not only seek for the acceptance or rebuke of a causal relationship or link, but also the specific ways in which it is manifested and the context in which it occurs (Chowdhury, 2014). Consequently, these researchers go beyond what has occurred to see how it has occurred (Chowdhury, 2014; Lin, 1998; Walsham, 1995). The fundamental idea of interpretivism is to work with these subjective meanings in the social world (i.e., to acknowledge their existence, to reconstruct them, to understand them, to avoid distorting them, to use them as building blocks in theorizing) (Göran, 2013).

Interpretive philosophy allows researchers to explore the world through the observations and experiences of the respondent. In seeking answers, the interpretivist researcher uses those experiences to construct and interpret his/her understanding from gathered data. Interpretive research is more subjective than objective (Nguyen & Tran Thi, 2015). Interpretive researchers do not seek solutions for their research in rigid ways. Instead, they approach the reality from participants, typically from people who own their experiences and are of a particular group or culture (Nguyen & Tran Thi, 2015).

Interpretivism, by its nature fosters the necessity of qualitative data in the quest for knowledge (Kaplan & Maxwell, 1994; Chowdhury, 2014). This philosophy is concerned with the exclusivity of a specific situation, contributing to the underlying pursuit of contextual depth. (Myers, 1999; Chowdhury, 2014). However, while interpretive research is recognised for its necessity in the provision of contextual depth, results are often criticised in terms of validity, reliability and generalisability (Chowdhury, 2014; Eisenhardt, 1989; Perry, 1998). So, to avoid this philosophically driven criticism, a diverse proposition to combine quantitative and qualitative methods, sometimes termed as “triangulation”, in researching the social world is suggested by a handful of researchers (Silverman, 2004; Hammersley, 2003).

This thesis was guided and grounded by an interpretivism philosophy. Most interpretivist researchers adopt the qualitative method of data collection (case study, interviews). Drawing from prior studies reviewed within the systematic literature review, few researchers (10 research articles) adopted a qualitative mode of research, influenced by an interpretivist philosophy to garner a better understanding of ethical leadership. This study adopted an interpretivist philosophy so as to obtain rich information and provide a clearer picture of the phenomenon and to fulfil the researcher’s belief and aim to get a deeper understanding and investigate the personal views, opinions and ideas of participants, which cannot be attained by the positivist philosophy. Furthermore, based on the qualitative nature of the research, it is essential an interpretivist approach be implemented in relations to the social and human context of observation and investigation.

6.3. Research Approach

The research philosophy provides guidance to the research method to be adopted. As outlined in the previous section, this study uses an interpretivist stance in the acquisition of data and

knowledge. Following up on this philosophy and guided by a qualitative method, it is pivotal that research is guided by an effective approach.

Several research approaches have been adopted within the research community. There exist three main approaches namely, the inductive, deductive and abductive research approach. Two main types stand out and are utilised most commonly within the research community namely, the inductive and the deductive approach (Trochim, 2006; Elo & Kyngas, 2007). Deductive approach adopts a top-down (up to bottom) approach to knowledge. It begins with a theory from which the derivation of a hypothesis is acquired and applied to observations about the world around (Ritchie et al., 2014). Deductive approach is adopted when the structure of analysis is operationalized on the basis of existing knowledge and the purpose of the study is theory testing (verifying or refuting existing theories) (Elo & Kyngas, 2007).

The inductive approach to research can be defined as a systematic process for analysing qualitative data in which the analysis of the data acquired is guided by specific evaluation criteria (Thomas, 2006). This involves the adoption drawn from the specific to the general, so that specific instances are taken into account and then combined into a general or wide statement (Elo & Kyngas, 2007; Thomas, 2006). This involves the process of carrying out detailed readings of raw data to extract themes, concept or a model through interpretations made from the raw data by a researcher (Thomas, 2006; Jebreen, 2012). In essence, researchers adopt the inductive approach by beginning from the area of study (specific focus) and creating a theory from the collated data acquired (Jebreen, 2012; Thomas, 2006; Elo & Kyngas, 2007).

Drawing from a better understanding of the concept of inductive approach to research from the research community (Jebreen, 2012; Trochim, 2006; Elo & Kyngas, 2007) and its extensive use in the qualitative method of research, this approach was adopted for this doctoral research work. The implementation of the inductive approach was based on the provision of a better

understanding of the concept of ethical leadership. It will be valuable in exploring and gaining a better understanding of how ethical leadership skills foster effective performance within public organisations. This approach was adopted based on its suitability for carrying out a qualitative research. Also, an inductive approach to research provides a medium for understanding and enquiring quality information from humans, collating data and drawing from this acquired information to garner a better picture of the phenomenon. This research involves gathering and interpreting data of the research population to get a better understanding of the research problem.

6.4. Research Method

This section gives a detailed research method to be utilised for this thesis. To attain suitable data, the proposed research method applied will be the qualitative method. Based on the philosophical stance of the researcher and inductive approach adopted, such method is better suited to provide a richer understanding of a phenomenon.

There has been debate over the years about what research method is most suitable in understanding the phenomenon and concept of leadership and the impact on follower behaviours, outcomes, organisational effectiveness and performance (Bryman, 2004). While most research within ethical leadership literature has focused on the adoption of the quantitative method to research (please refer to the systematic literature review), there has been minimal adoption of the qualitative research method within ethical leadership research (Ko et al., 2018).

The qualitative approach is concerned with the why and how of individual's decision making; this implies that qualitative studies usually consist of small and focused samples. There are various forms of qualitative research methods, such as interviews, observation, document analysis, and ethnography, which are often divided into different types (Babar, 2015). In the qualitative method of research, a researcher begins with a reflection and self-valuation about

themselves as situated in a social-historical context (Looi, 2014). The qualitative method of research does not narrowly focus on a fixed question or scaling level but dwells on the theoretical paradigm in an open-ended, inquisitive setting (Neumann, 2006). This provides an effective method for researchers to explore the views of same as well as diverse groups of individuals. Which helps unravel these differing views and perspectives within a given sample size or ethnic community.

Qualitative research deals with an assessment of opinions, attitudes and behaviours. Some school of thought postulate the benefits and strengths of the qualitative method as it deals with groups of people. It involves asking this group to respond together to certain questions and hypothetical situations and proffers information that is more distinct than information derived from field surveys (Bryman, 2004; Neumann, 2006; Looi, 2014).

The mantra of qualitative research is a commitment to seeing the social world from the point of view of the actor, a theme which is rarely omitted from methodological writings within this tradition (Bryman, 1984). Clear statements of this emphasis can be discerned in a broad range of writings. This is because of the commitment to see through the eyes of one's subject's close involvement is advocated. There is a simultaneous expression of preference for a contextual understanding so that behaviour is to be understood in the context of meaning systems employed by a specific group or society.

Qualitative research is deemed to be much more fluid and flexible than quantitative research as it emphasises discovering novel or unanticipated findings and the possibility of altering research plans in response to such unforeseen events (Bryman, 2004; Bryman, 1984). This is contrasted sharply with the quantitative methodologist's research design with its emphasis upon fixed measurements, hypothesis (or hunch) testing, and a much less protracted form of fieldwork involvement (Bryman, 1984). While this method of research is important in

pinpointing and attaining a more distinct information about critical issues regarding human related situations, qualitative method of research has its drawbacks. Firstly, this method is time consuming and require time in gathering quality data from sample subject and in terms of data analysis. Furthermore, data interpretation can be limited for the researcher (Looi, 2014).

6.4.1. Research Method Trend in the Field

Several scholars in the field of leadership have asserted that research in the field have mainly adopted a quantitative approach (Bryman, 2011; Conger, 1998; Bryman, 2004; Avolio et al., 2009). While this has yielded significant progress to the body of leadership literature, some scholars have stressed that it limits the development of leadership theory (Conger, 1998).

Some studies have shown a gradual shift from the quantitative form to other diverse methods of research (Conger, 1998; Harrison et al., 2018). Bryman (2011) provides the variation in methodology approaches adopted in the field of leadership utilised by leadership scholars and researchers within the field. Parry et al. (2014) proffer that while quantitative research will evidently be the main method of research in leadership within the field for many years, there is little doubt that qualitative research is beginning to make inroads into the field.

The dexterity within the body of research in relation to research method adoption is variably visible in the field of ethical leadership literature. From the outcome of the systematic literature review in chapter five, it is evident that there exists a consensus in the adoption of the quantitative method. Outcome from the systematic literature review findings suggests a higher percentage of studies utilised the quantitative method of research (76%), while 13% of scholarly works in the field adopted the qualitative method of research. From findings, these shows a disparity in the adoption of qualitative method to garner a deeper understanding of the impact of ethical leadership within organisation.

While there exist, a minimal number compared to the quantitative method of research, this method provides a basis to acquire a better understanding of ethical leadership. It explores and provides a deeper knowledge of the human factor and the influence and effect of ethical leadership on these human factors. For detailed information about a given issue such as challenges facing ethical leadership within the public sector and the influence of effective ethical leadership skills, it is essential that researchers explore the perspective view of the participants and get a clear picture of the situation. This gives an in-depth knowledge of the situation (Bryman, 1984; Bryman, 2004; Creswell, 2013; Looi, 2014).

6.5. Data Collection Methods

A systemic and consistent approach of data collection will be adopted throughout the duration and process of this doctoral research thesis. There exist several methods used in collecting qualitative data namely, interviews, focus groups, observations etc. (Bryman, 2011; Conger, 1998). While there exist several methods in the collection of qualitative data within the leadership field (Bryman, 2011; Conger, 1998; Bryman, 2004; Morse, 2015), the use of interviews have provided deeper insights into the understanding of the subject (Morse, 2015). In adopting a qualitative method to research, interviews can be sub-divided into three categories namely, semi-structured interviews, unstructured interviews and structured interviews. An interview involves the process of verbal exchange whereby the interviewer attempts to elicit information from the interviewee by posing questions. There are several advantages to the utilisation of interviews within research context. The table 11 below gives a detailed summation of the advantages and the disadvantages of the adoption of interviews.

Table 11: Advantages and Disadvantages of Research Interviews

Advantages of Research interviews	Disadvantages of Research interviews
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They proffer useful insight and context. • They help research participant describe what is important to them. • They are useful in the generation of stories and quotes. • They enable the researcher the opportunity to observe and listen to the participants. • They enable more complex questions to be asked to the participants • The researcher can explain the purpose of the research and answer any question the participant may have about the study. • They help the researcher probe participants responses and seek further clarification. • The participants can seek classification as regards questions posed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They can be intrusive to the participant in question. • They are time-consuming with regards to conducting these interviews, arrangement, transcription and analysis of the data collected. • They are expensive in comparison with other methods. • Interviews on a personal and/ or intimate subject can evoke strong feelings and these feelings need to be handled with great sensitivity. • They are susceptible to bias, which may include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participant's desire to please the researcher. - Saying what they think/feel the researcher wishes to hear, such as giving an official point of view rather than a personal point of view.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They provide avenues for participants to give detailed responses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The desire to create a good impression may lead to participant not answering honestly
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Whilst there are several advantages to the adoption of qualitative research questions within qualitative research in literature, several challenges or disadvantages were encountered during the course of the research study. One major drawback faced during the field study can be attributed to the time factor in the preparation, execution and the transcription of data during the course of the research. In carrying out this research, a longer duration of time was taken from the process of sending out letters, to the process of arranging interview sessions and the transcription process of these interviews to extract quality information as compared to the utilization of a quantitative approach to research. A time duration of two years and three months was done to successfully complete the field study and the transcription of data into key themes. While this study was time consuming, the quality of data extracted and presented were much more detailed than the process of carrying out a quantitative study. Another experience faced during the course of this research study is the aspect of emotional feelings and sentiments evoked by the nature of the research questions. Some participants were passionate and emotional towards some of the research questions posed as regards the issues facing ethical leaders within the public sector in their respective departments. Most information provided during the course of these interviews were sensitive in nature. In order to ensure the participants outputs were provided in a dignified way, anonymity and ensuring interviews were carried out in safe and secured locations were each participants felt comfortable and safe.

6.5.1. Structured Interviews

In this mode of interviewing participants, each respondent is asked similar questions with the same order and wordings (Doody & Noonan, 2013; Clifford et al., 2016). The advantages of a structured interview are that it provides efficiency with regards to time. It limits researcher subjectivity and bias, and the researcher controls the topics and format of the interview, making it easier to code, compare and analyse data (Doody & Noonan, 2013; Holloway & Jefferson, 1997). Furthermore, structured interview ensures that comparable responses are collated from each research participant, it can be like a spoken questionnaire, leaving no room for further explanation.

6.5.2. Unstructured Interviews

An unstructured interview begins with a broad, open question concerning the area or topic in discourse, with subsequent questions dependent on the participants responses (Doody & Noonan, 2013; Holloway & Jefferson, 1997). In unstructured interviews, the researcher adopts a non-directive and flexible form of interview, not adopting or sticking to an interview guide, comprising themes rather than specific questions (Doody & Noonan, 2013).

Data processing from unstructured interviews can be difficult and time consuming because it involves bringing together similar statements from different participants and links are often difficult to make (Doody & Noonan, 2013). While this provides an avenue for unrestricted questions, unstructured interviews can be daunting for beginners and are very prone to bias. Furthermore, the research participant can also deviate from the issues discussed into irrelevant topics.

6.5.3. Semi-Structured Interviews

In a semi-structured interview format, the interviewer adopts a conversational manner of posing a list of predetermined questions to the participant (Clifford et al., 2016). This provides an

avenue for research participants to explore issues they consider important. The researcher is provided the opportunity to vary both the order and the wording of the questions posed to the research participant. This is dependent on the direction of the interview and provides the opportunity to ask additional questions. Furthermore, this presents avenues for exploration of new paths that emerges during the process of the interview that were initially not considered (Doody & Noonan, 2013; Gray, 2004).

Semi-structured interview was utilised to acquire qualitative data for this research project. The adoption of a semi-structured interview is driven by the necessity to acquire important and valuable information from correspondents drawn from broad themes in the literature. This drives and results in more open-ended responses that will guide the researcher's follow up or probing questions. Additionally, such an approach benefits from the expert knowledge and the ability to provide meaningful interjections that the previous chapter has provided.

In the development of the interview questions, three primary sources were utilised: relevant literature, background and critical knowledge and experience in this area, and informal conversations with individuals that are familiar with the leadership structures and frameworks within public sector institutions. The inclusion of demographic questions will create a foundation of who the informants were and outlined their experiences within the Nigerian public sector. Utilisation of this approach to carrying out qualitative interviews helps foster trust, provide a scenario for participants to be free, allows for robust communication and the ability to ask clarifying questions.

6.6. Pilot Study

Though pilot studies may have many important benefits in conducting qualitative research, they have attracted limited attention in research literature (Kim, 2010). A pilot study can be described as a feasibility study that comprises small-scale versions of the planned study, trial

runs of planned methods, or miniature versions of the main research for the purpose of answering methodological question(s) and to guide the development of the research plan (Prescott & Soeken, 1989; Kim, 2010; Malmqvist et al., 2019). A pilot study is used to evaluate the practicalities of the main study in respect of its application and utility and often includes an assessment of resources, such as time and costs for the main study (Gudmundsdottir & Brock-Utne, 2010; Malmqvist et al., 2019).

Evidently within the body of research, a pilot study within qualitative research helps a researcher refine and develop research protocols, assess the level and degree of observer bias, aid in the collection of background information, frame research questions and adapt research procedures (Creswell, 2007; Sampson, 2004). Furthermore, it provides the researcher the ability to highlight the themes from initial findings and avenue to access the suitability of research question protocol in addressing the research objectives.

A pilot study was carried out during the course of this study to assess its feasibility and viability. Two leaders were interviewed for the pilot study. Each participant of the pilot study was briefed about the project and were presented with the participant information sheet. Each participant was briefed and provided assurance of privacy and confidentiality which is critical to the ethical consideration of this research. Whilst the pilot study will not be integrated into the main study, this provided the avenue for the application of pre-testing instruments (Baker, 1994; Prescott & Soeken, 1989; Kim, 2010). Furthermore, the pilot study provided an avenue for the assessment of the interview timeframe, adaptation of the research protocol and the research analysis and evaluation method to be adopted for the main study. The adaptation of a semi-structured form of interview and thematic form of qualitative analysis (Braun & Clark, 2006; King et al., 2019) was utilised in the pilot study and found suitable for the main study.

The pilot study provided some insights, reflection, insights and opportunities to some aspect of the main study. Findings from the pilot study highlighted the necessity for a distinction in the definition and understanding of terms adopted in the research protocol. As seen from the pilot study, there is a need to differentiate the aspect of attributes and skills. Furthermore, the pilot study provided an insight in better shaping questions that addressed the ethical challenges as opposed to other conventional challenges facing leaders in the public sector. Furthermore, the pilot study provided an insight into the stipulated time frame for each interview session that is suitable for the main research study. There are several benefits provided from the outcome of the pilot study to this doctoral thesis. Several research questions were tailored to proffer a better outcome from research participants based on the outcome of the pilot study. Research questions were adjusted based on feedbacks from leaders who participated such as questions relating to the ethical challenges facing leaders in the public sector. Furthermore, the pilot study provided an avenue for the researcher in terms of experience in the field and ensuring the research protocols to be adopted were effective and efficient.

6.7. Sampling

6.7.1. Population and Sampling Size

Sampling can be defined as a subset of a larger group (Parker & O'Reilly, 2013). Sampling design can be considered an important aspect in the development and process of carrying out any research study (Aggarwal, 2011). It involves the selection of the right participants, events, groups and representation of a large group or population (Aggarwal, 2011; Parker & O'Reilly, 2013; Fox, 2010).

There are two main sampling techniques namely, the probability or the non-probability sampling (Aggarwal, 2011; Coyne, 1997). Probability sampling is the basis for the statistical calculation of the potential error associated with an estimate of a population parameter developed from sample data (Fox, 2010). This form of sampling is attributed to quantitative

form of research and are defined by the values of a set of design variables like strata and cluster indicators (Pfeffermann et al., 1998).

Studies associate non-probability sampling methods with qualitative research as it mostly involves judgment. Instead of randomisation, participants are selected because they are easy to access, with a potential to generate valuable insights and the focus of research findings does not provide a statistical representation of the population (Aggarwal, 2011).

Purposeful sampling is a technique widely adopted in qualitative research for the identification and selection of information-rich cases for the most effective use of limited resources (Palinkas et al., 2016; Patton, 2002). The purposive sampling technique, also known as judgment sampling, is the deliberate choice of a participant due to the qualities the participant possesses. It is a non-random technique that does not need underlying theories or a set number of participants (Etikan et al., 2016). For this research, purposive sampling was adopted as it was important that the group had the knowledge that was relevant to the research questions (Morse, 2015; Creswell, 2013). The sample size for this study was determined based upon a review of several study elements. As the goal of this qualitative study was to understand the meaning of the phenomenon in enquiry, and not to develop a generalisable premise, it is the occurrence of an idea and not the frequency that was important. As with this research study, sample size determinant can be characterised by factors such as time constraints, interview groups, funding and other obstacles beyond the sphere of the research data (Parker & O'Reilly, 2013; Mertens, 2014).

For this research, determination of target sampling for the actualisation of the research was focused on individual's presently occupying mid-level to senior positions in the Nigerian public sector. Critical emphasis was placed within the Oil and Gas industries of the public-sector drawing from both the upstream and downstream sector. To this essence, focus was

placed on the Nigeria National petroleum corporation (NNPC) as the basis of investigating the Nigerian public sector. Adopting the definition of the system national account (SNA) on public sector organisation, the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) within this context is described as a public sector organisation.

6.7.2. Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC)

NNPC came into being in April 1977 to manage the Nigerian government interest within the oil industry. The Federation or any of its agencies did not have participatory interest in the industry for 15 years after the commencement of production of commercial--quantity crude oil in Nigeria in 1956. Through the 1960s, the industry remained entirely in the hands of IOCs (international oil companies), with state involvement restricted to regulation (including price control on refined petroleum products in the domestic market), and to collection of fees from exploration licenses and production leases, as well as taxes and royalties on crude (Thurber et al., 2019).

As the overseer of the Federation's interest in the oil and gas industry, NNPC is central to the Nigerian economy. The responsibilities of the corporation range from exploration and production, petroleum product marketing, engineering and data support services, training, and crude oil refining to construction and maintenance of a network of pipelines. NNPC is an integrated oil and gas company, wholly owned by the Federation. It is a holding company with 12 wholly owned and two partially owned subsidiaries or corporate business units (CBUs). It also has a growing number of corporate divisions or corporate strategy units (CSUs). Staff strength has shrunk drastically since 2003, when it was about 17,000, to about 9,000 in the first quarter of 2007 (Egbuta, 2019; Egbuta & Hamed, 2019). Figure 12 gives a detailed description of the significant subsidiaries within the Nigerian national petroleum corporation.

As a public sector institution, The NNPC leadership structure can be broken into two main sectors. These are the organisation's board headed by the executive council selected by the federal government comprising the minister of petroleum. The second sector consists of the management board of the company with the group managing director (GMD) as the head of the organisation. Each subsidiary of NNPC is controlled by a managing director with two executive directors (operations and services).

Each SBU is made up of a three-staged workers' structure. These include the management, the senior staff and the junior staff. Each staff is graded using a civil service grading system.

The management staff consist of managers and deputy managers. Senior staff consist of chief superintendent officers, supervisors and assistant supervisors. Junior staff consist of employees within the early years of their career.

Figure 15: Significant Divisions and Subsidiaries in NNPC

<u>Interface with IOCs</u>	
NAPIMS	National Petroleum Investment Management Services
<u>Crude Oil Buyers and Sellers</u>	
COMD	Crude Oil Marketing Division
PPMC	Pipelines and Products Marketing Company
HYSON	Hydrocarbon Services Nigeria (marketing JV with Vitol)
<u>Operational (Upstream and Natural Gas)</u>	
NPDC	Nigeria Petroleum Development Company (exploration & production)
NGC	Nigerian Gas Company (natural gas pipeline operation)
NLNG	Nigerian LNG (LNG facility operation, 49% NNPC-owned)
<u>Operational (Downstream)</u>	
WRPC	Warri Refining & Petrochemical Company
PHRC	Port Harcourt Refining Company
KRPC	Kaduna Refining & Petrochemical Company
EPCL	Eleme Petrochemicals Company Limited
<u>Services</u>	
NETCO	National Engineering & Technical Company (engineering design)
IDSL	Integrated Data Services Limited (seismic data processing)

6.7.3. Research Participants

This section addresses the process of participant recruitment for this doctoral research. To attain the desired research outcomes, letters of invitation to participate in this research were employed to acquire quality respondents for attaining and meeting the goals for this research thesis. These letters were sent to a selection of SBUs within the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation to proffer a diverse perspective of leaders within the public sector. **Whilst other mediums of invitation such as emails were available for utilization, the researcher adopted a**

traditional form of letter writing and postage to the intended participants for this study. This is due to various reasons within the Nigerian culture and economy such as the demography of participants having limited access to internet network and priority given to paper based letters by an older age group of people in management. Furthermore, a total number of 45 paper-based written invitations were sent out to participants with a total number of 25 responding to participate in the research, six potential respondents declining and a total number of 14 individuals not responding to the invitation. This research was centred on top-level management individuals and supervisors with significant years of experience within the sector. Having beliefs, experiences, or knowledge relevant to the research questions was an important consideration in the selection of participants.

A total number of 25 respondents agreed to participate in this research study. For attainment of a successful research, each response was weighed on participant's positions (criteria mid-senior roles and senior roles) such as managers of public institution (Kaplan & Maxwell, 1994; Thomas, 2006). This is essential based on the number of years spent in the public sector. For this study, emphasis was placed on respondents in leadership within the Nigerian public sector as a minimum of five years. This was done to ensure that the respondents selected have the required experience in the sector and can proffer a better insight on their leadership perspective.

The interview process with each respondent during the research process was carried out within the period of 12th of June 2019 to the 14th of July 2019. Given the multiple location of each respondents during the course of this study, the researcher travelled to the various SBU locations within the country to conduct these interviews namely Lagos, Warri and Port-Harcourt in Nigeria to ensure the possibility of a face-to-face interview process. Whilst this process was time consuming and financially strenuous, this was essential to get qualitative information and non-verbal information such as body languages which cannot be acquired from the use of telecommunication software such as Microsoft teams or Skype and through the

telephone. Each interview sessions during the process of data-gathering were done face-to-face by the researcher and the respondents at designated locations each participants selected based on safety, security and anonymity. A good example of such location selected by a respondent can be described as a club centre quiet and distant from their place of occupation. Each face to face interviews were carried out and audiophiles recorded using a voice recorder for each sessions with prior notification and authorisation from each respondents. Open ended semi-structured research questions were asked to the respondents with follow-up questions provided based on the responses of each participants. After each session of the interview process, written transcription and recorded documentation of the interview process was provided to the participant to ensure credibility of information provided. After each session of the interview process was done, a written and detailed transcription of the recorded files was done thoroughly with the researcher replaying the recording to multiple to times to ensure each details in the recording was captured and efficiently documented in written form. These transcribed files were provided to each respondent to ensure both bias, alteration of data were mitigated and to ensure credibility in the process of this research study. Furthermore, to ensure a thorough evaluation process for this doctoral study.

At the point of the 18th interview, leaders within the Nigerian public sector were found to provide similar understanding on the concept of ethical leadership and saturation had been reached. Whilst the remainder 7 interview process were conducted to ensure the success and honour the participants engagements, data from these interviews produced similar themes from the previous interview process carried out. Saturation means that no additional data are being found whereby the sociologist can develop properties of the phenomenon (Glaser & Strauss, 1971). Thematic saturation was achieved at the 18th interview, revealing no new themes or findings from the interview process (Glaser & Strauss, 1971). The average duration of the interview was 60 minutes.

6.8. Data Analysis

The next step involves a thorough analysis of research data acquired from the interviews. In qualitative research, there are several methods of data analysis. These methods include narrative analysis, textual analysis, thematic analysis, grounded theory and qualitative content analysis (Vaismoradi et al., 2013; Maguire & Delahunt, 2017). For this research study, a thematic analysis method was adopted to analyse the acquired raw data from the field and provide adequate themes from the participants.

Thematic analysis involves the process of identifying patterns or themes within qualitative data (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017). It involves the search for and identification of common threads that extend across an entire interview or set of interviews (Vaismoradi et al., 2013). Unlike other forms of qualitative analysis, thematic analysis is not restricted to a unique epistemological or theoretical perspective and provides flexibility (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017). Furthermore, Braun & Clarke (2006) stress that thematic analysis provides a purely qualitative, detailed and distinct account of data.

Thematic analysis provides a medium of better understanding a phenomenon and can either adopt an inductive or a deductive form (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The inductive form of thematic analysis involves the process of coding data without the task of fitting into pre-existing code frames. In contrast to this, the deductive form is driven by the researcher's theoretical or analytical area of interest (mapping codes to the research questions). For this research, an inductive approach to thematic analysis was adopted. A rigorous thematic analysis can generate trustworthy and insightful findings (Nowell et al., 2017; Braun & Clarke, 2006)

Thematic analysis allows the researcher's social construction of meaning to be articulated with reliability (Boyatzis, 1998). There are several benefits to the use of thematic analysis such as the examination of perspectives of different research respondents, highlighting similarities and

differences, and generation of unanticipated insights (Nowell et al., 2017; Braun & Clarke, 2006; King et al., 2019). It also provides useful summarisation of key features of large data set, as it forces the researcher to take a well-structured approach to handling data, producing clear and organised reports of findings (Nowell et al., 2017).

Several scholarly works have provided detailed guidance about the process of carrying out a thematic analysis (King et al., 2019; Braun & Clarke, 2006; Saldana, 2013). Braun & Clarke (2006) provides a detailed six step framework for conducting a thematic analysis and King et al. (2019) provide a three staged approach. While there exists a similarity of both frameworks, for this research study, King et al.'s thematic framework was used.

Before the commencement of the thematic analysis, the interview transcripts were generated and the familiarisation of interview excerpt was done to get a better understanding of the participant's perspective (Saldana, 2013; Braun & Clarke, 2006). In carrying out the transcription of the research interview, consideration of non-verbal communication was inculcated into each participants transcripts to give clarity to information being provided (King et al., 2019; Braun & Clarke, 2006). King et al. (2019) provides a three staged approach to thematic analysis which consists of the descriptive coding , interpretive coding and developing the overarching themes.

At the completion of each session of the interview process, a written and detailed transcription of the recorded files was done thoroughly with the researcher replaying the recording to multiple to times to ensure each details in the recording was captured and efficiently documented in written form. Having completed the process of converting the audio data into text format, the researcher utilized and adopted a qualitative data processing tool namely NVivo to aid in the analysis of transcribed files from respondents. Having prior knowledge from themes that emerged from the outcome of the literature review and preliminary findings

from the pilot study, the researcher was able to generate initial codes. Furthermore to provide further understanding and context of the interview extract, the researcher referred back to each transcript and audio data to grasp a better understanding in the coding process.

6.8.1. Descriptive Coding

King et al. (2019) assert that the first step of the thematic analysis process is descriptive coding. At this stage of the thematic analysis, the researcher's aim is to identify the parts of the data that are helpful in addressing the research questions without reading meaning to the data (King et al., 2019; Braun & Clarke, 2006). Furthermore, the descriptive coding process helps define initial themes and the categorisation of codes based on the research criteria (King et al., 2019; Saldana, 2013).

To demonstrate the descriptive coding for this research, respondents' excerpt is provided below showing the demonstration of the coding process. For example, when Respondent 010 was asked about their understanding on what ethical leadership means. Respondent 010 states "the ability to apply moral beliefs and organisation beliefs to influence followers".

From this statement, two descriptive codes can be identified namely: "ability" and "application of morals".

6.8.2. Interpretive Coding

King et al. (2019) assert that the second step of thematic analysis is interpretive coding. At this stage of the thematic analysis process, the researchers define the codes beyond the relevant features of participants account and place more emphasis on the interpretation and the meaning of the descriptive codes (King et al., 2019). This involves grouping similar descriptive codes that share some common meaning and creating interpretive codes that capture these commonalities (King et al., 2019; Nowell et al., 2017). However, in the process of looking at the descriptive codes, it is essential that the researcher refers back to the transcripts to help keep

the process in context and define interpretive codes that are not related to particular descriptive codes (King et al., 2019).

To demonstrate the interpretive coding for this research, respondents' excerpt is provided below. For example (Respondent 005) *understanding of communicative skill* and (Respondent 006) *understanding of listening and talking to subordinate* form interpretive codes of communication and listening skills.

6.8.3. Developing Overarching Themes

King et al. (2019) assert that the final step of the thematic analysis is developing overarching themes. Overarching themes are built on the interpretive codes and at a higher level of abstraction than the interpretive codes. At this final stage, the researcher draws directly on theoretical ideas that underlie the research (King et al., 2019). Overarching themes in this stage sometimes may not include codes identified in the previous coding process (Braun & Clarke, 2006; King et al., 2019).

To demonstrate the overarching themes for this research, respondents' excerpts are provided. For example, skills such as communication, active listening skills and empathy were considered to be relevant to interpersonal skills and thus defined as such.

6.9. Evaluation of Research

The concept of validity and reliability can be described as pivotal tools utilised for research evaluation (Golafshani, 2003). Golafshani (2003) suggests the lack of relevance of reliability in the field of qualitative research. In essence, to elucidate information in qualitative research, information test should be based on the quality and relevance of work done. To examine the quality of work done in a qualitative based research, criteria for ascertaining the level of quality should be based on the selected researcher's paradigms (Golafshani, 2003; Healy & Perry, 2000; Patton, 2002). Lincoln & Guba (1985) posit the need for a better description and use of

the term reliability and validity within qualitative research. While these terms are essential to quantitative research, the use of terms such as credibility, dependability, applicability and confirmability are more suited towards the qualitative form of research (Healy & Perry, 2000; Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

The need for trustworthiness in qualitative research has been a topic of discourse within the body of literature. Patton (2002) ascribes the necessity of triangulation method as an important aspect for ensuring credibility in qualitative research. According to Lincoln & Guba (1985), credibility can be defined as the confidence placed in the truth of a research finding. This deals with the focus of the research and refers to the confidence in how well the data provided addresses the intended focus (Elo et al., 2014; Polit & Beck, 2012). Some school of thought have asserted the equivalent nature of credibility to internal validity in quantitative research and with its main focus on the aspect of truth value (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Elo et al., 2014). There are several techniques within literature to ensure the credibility of a qualitative research, this can be done from the inception of the planning and preparation phase of the research, to the methods adopted in the data collection stage and the process of ensuring the data collected conform to the focus of the research. Lincoln & Guba (1985) posit several key techniques in ensuring the credibility of findings and interpretation in qualitative research namely prolonged engagement, persistent observation, triangulation and member checks.

To provide credibility for this study, these key techniques were adopted. A prolonged engagement with respondents was carried out in the field to ensure the researcher built trust, understand the environment to avoid information distortion and to also ensure rich quality data are collected from the field (Korstjens & Moser, 2018; Lincoln & Guba, 2018). Furthermore, data triangulation and member checking were employed for this research. Data was triangulated from multiple sources to generate themes or categories for this study. On completion of each interview, participants were given the opportunity to review and go through

the transcripts to ensure accuracy and comfort with the nature of the text. This helps reduce bias and validates information gathered from the managers, deputy managers and supervisors. At the completion of each session of the interview process, a written and detailed transcription of the recorded files was done thoroughly with the researcher replaying the recording to multiple to times to ensure each details in the recording was captured and efficiently documented in written form anonymous coded to ensure confidentiality. These transcribed files were provided to each respondent to ensure both bias, alteration of data were mitigated and to ensure credibility in the process of this research study. Furthermore, the researcher also iterated to each respondents of this doctoral study of their rights to withdraw from the process at any given time.

Dependability refers to the stability of data over time and under different conditions (Elo et al., 2014). The concept of dependability in qualitative research can be akin to reliability in quantitative research (Lincoln & Guba, 1989). Dependability occurs when another researcher can follow the decision trail used by the researcher (Thomas & Magilvy, 2011). Thomas & Magilvy (2011) assert that audit trail is achieved by (a) the description of specific purpose of study; (b) discussion on the selection criteria of participants and why; (c) describing how the data was collected and how long the data collection lasted; (d) explaining how the data was reduced or transformed for analysis; (e) discussing the interpretation and presentation of the research findings; and (f) communicating the specific techniques used to determine the credibility of the data. Dependability which is essential for trustworthiness (Healy & Perry, 2000; Golafshani, 2003) can be achieved through verification and thorough examination of items such as raw data, process notes, and data reduction products (Golafshani, 2003). To ensure dependability for this research, the creation of audit trails was achieved through the description of the data collection process and how it lasted. Furthermore, the participation and

the purposive selection of leaders within the public sector provided credibility (Lincoln & Guba, 1989; Thomas & Magilvy, 2011).

Transferability or applicability is considered parallel to external validity or generalisability in quantitative research (Sinkovics et al., 2008). Thomas & Magilvy (2011) assert the concept of transferability as the capability to transfer research methods and findings from one group to another. It is how one determines the extent to which the findings of a particular inquiry have applicability in different circumstances or with other subjects/participants. This refers to the potential for extrapolation which relies on the understanding that findings can be generalised or transferred to other groups (Elo et al., 2014; Nowell et al., 2017; King et al., 2019). The researcher cannot know the sites that may wish to transfer the findings; however, the researcher has sole responsibility for providing thick descriptions, so that those who seek to transfer the findings to their own site can judge transferability (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). This research study did not explore the transferability or attempt to transfer the findings to other groups.

Thomas & Magilvy (2011) assert the concept of confirmability can be akin to objectivity in quantitative research. This involves the process of providing transparent description of the research steps taken from the start of the research to the development and the reporting of the findings (Korstjens & Moser, 2018; Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Some school of thought elucidate confirmability is attained when credibility, transferability and dependability are all achieved (Nowell et al., 2017; Lincoln & Guba, 1985). This refers to the degree to which a researcher demonstrates the neutrality of research interpretations through confirmability audits (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Hoepfl, 1997). King et al. (2019) assert the distinct nature of confirmability to objectivity, as a researcher must be able to sufficiently provide details of the process of their data collection and analysis that a third party can see how they reached their conclusion. There are three major techniques to ensure confirmability of a qualitative research namely, confirmability audit, triangulation and keeping of a reflective journal (Lincoln & Guba, 1985;

Thomas & Magilvy, 2011; Nowell et al., 2017). For this research, triangulation was adopted to proffer confirmability.

6.10. Ethical Considerations

The necessity for confidentiality and integrity is critical in carrying out any qualitative research. Consideration of participants involved must be respected during any given research interview. This involves respecting participants right to privacy and anonymity. The importance of ethical considerations when dealing with social respondents (human beings) must be given important reflections when carrying out qualitative research (Creswell, 2013; Morse, 2015). There is an ethical obligation that researchers have in any project that involves human research participants.

The basic ethical impasse facing research methodology adopted is to ensure a balance between the obligation to science and to the research respondent. To balance some responsibilities, one must take into consideration the “scientific obligation to do research in the best way we know how” (Lewis, 2015, p. 20) and the “humanistic obligation to treat people with dignity and to safeguard their interests” (p. 24). There exist eight principles that guides qualitative research, these include: respect for human dignity, respect for free and informed consent, respect for vulnerable persons, respect for privacy and confidentiality, respect for justice and inclusiveness, balancing harm and benefits, minimizing harm, and maximizing benefit (Lewis, 2015). To adhere to the ethical construct, the UWS ethics guidelines was adopted, and approval obtained from the university ethics committee (please see appendix 4). Following these laid down guidelines, each step was carried out.

6.10.1. Autonomy, Veracity and Informed Consent

Correspondent’s dignity and respecting their privacy, values and norms are essential for a successful research outcome (Lewis, 2015; Morse, 2015; Marshall & Rossman, 2014; Mertens,

2014). To ensure each participant is aware of the research to be carried out, detailed summary was provided highlighting the aims, objectives and the purpose for the research. It is important that respondents know their roles. Participation in the research was voluntary using informed consent. In addition, the notification of withdrawal from the research at any time is solely based on their consent. Furthermore, it is very essential the researcher develops a level of trust and confidentiality with the respondent due to the sensitivity and emotional attachment of information gathered. An informed consent form was prepared and provided to the participants of this research and signed upon agreement (Marshall & Rossman, 2014; Morse, 2015) (Appendix 2). Each participant was fully briefed on the detail of the interview process and to garner their understanding of the research process before the commencement of the interview.

6.10.2. Privacy and Confidentiality

The adoption and employment of pseudonyms for the interview transcripts and the elimination of questions identifying the correspondent, further mitigated harm by maintaining a strict level of anonymity for the participants. Furthermore, each participant's department, SBUs and location were removed to further protect their identification and that of the subsidiary. The major focus of this research project is to gather data to assist in providing solutions to the research questions and attaining the objectives of this exploratory research. It was highly imperative to provide them with access to the interview transcripts. Involvement allowed the respondents the opportunity to better understand this phenomenon, as one that has a direct effect on them (Marshall & Rossman, 2014; Mertens, 2014), and therefore may assist in their future decision-making.

6.10.3. Justice and Inclusiveness

Justice in qualitative research refer to the obligation to treat people with respect, fairly and equitably (Tri-council policy statement, 2014). This involves the provision for fairness and equity to all research participants through the process of providing specific obligations to those

who are potentially vulnerable where appropriate (UWS ethics committee, 2016). In adhering to justice and inclusiveness, each participant for this research was accorded fairness and equity. Adoption of equality-based involvement was done by observing strict recruitment guidelines and participation based on the recruitment processes (position and experience). Furthermore, to ensure participation of all individuals, special instruments was in place such as observing and carrying out interviews in locations provided with quality standard facilities, conducive and highly confidential.

6.10.4. Benefits and Harm

The necessity and ethical obligation for the minimization of risk is essential in the design process and the conducting of research (UWS ethics committee, 2016). Some school of thought within the body of literature have also classified this as the process of providing beneficence or non-maleficence (Townsend et al., 2010). Drawing from the understanding of ethics as it pertains to the concept of doing good and avoiding harm, this involves the researcher providing benefits for the participants and to balance this against the risks (Townsend et al., 2010; Aluwihare-Samaranayaje, 2012). To achieve beneficence, a researcher must take into consideration the recruitment process of participants, autonomy of participants to share information willingly and ensuring the moral obligation of protecting participants identity (Orbs et al., 2001; Aluwihare-Samaranayaje, 2012).

To ensure the mitigation of harm towards each participant, sensitive information was removed. Furthermore, to adhere to non-maleficence, avoidance of questions and divulgement of information that will bring cultural, emotional and physical harm to the participant was clearly avoided.

6.11. Conclusion

This chapter justified the methodological selection made in the actualisation of the research aim. Inductive approach was adopted in this research study to find solutions to a problem by beginning from the area of study (specific focus) to create a theory from the collated data acquired (Jebreen, 2012; Thomas, 2006; Elo & Kyngas, 2007). An interpretivist philosophy was adopted to proffer a better understanding in relation to social and human context of observation and investigation. Furthermore, the adoption of an interpretivist philosophy was done to understand and explore the views of leaders in the Nigerian public sector so as to produce a better picture of the required ethical leadership skills necessary for improving effectiveness and performance.

Due to the adoption of an interpretivist philosophy, a qualitative research method was employed. Semi-structured interviews were used to acquire quality data from participants (Bryman, 2004; Neumann, 2006; Looi, 2014). Interviews were conducted with 25 research participants who were identified through the recruitment process and purposive sampling. A thematic analysis as the mode of analysing qualitative data was employed. King et al. (2019) three-stage coding process was adopted to identify themes. The quality of this study was ensured adopting various measures.

The next chapter will present the findings of this study.

CHAPTER SEVEN: RESULTS AND FINDINGS CHAPTER

7.0. Introduction

This chapter provides the findings from the field research carried out, this involved semi-structured interviews of 25 respondents. The details of the participants can be found in Table 12. Each recorded interview of the 25 respondents was rigorously transcribed. To adhere and ensure full anonymity, interviewees are referred to as “respondent” with an assigned number code. Data acquired from the field research were analysed with the application of thematic analysis. The result from this thematic analysis identified three main themes: conceptualization of ethical leadership, the skills and the challenges. These themes are discussed with direct quotes from the respondents. The purpose of this study is to examine the concept of ethical leadership and to explore the skills perspective in ethical leadership development for improving performance within the Nigerian public sector. To accomplish the aim of this study, the following objectives guided the course of this research These are.

- To examine the current conceptualisation of ethical leadership.
- To identify the ethic-based challenges facing leaders within the Nigerian public sector.
- To provide a skill-based ethical leadership framework within the Nigerian public sector.
- To investigate the influence of ethical leadership skills on performance in the Nigerian public sector.

To ensure the purpose and the objectives of this study was actualised, key questions were provided to guide this research study and to provide answers to the problem definition. These questions are.

- How do we define the concept of ethical leadership?
- What are the required skills necessary for an effective ethical leader?

- What are the perspectives adopted in literature in examination of ethical leadership?
- What are the hinderances and limitations to the implementation of an ethical leadership framework?
- How does ethical leadership influence performance within an organisation?

Roles and Responsibilities within the Organisation

This section gives a description of the roles and responsibilities of the participants within the organisation addressing the diversity and dexterity. A total number of 25 participants were interviewed, with a balanced distribution from the gender perspective. To comply and protect their anonymity, their departments were omitted from the findings chapter. The table 12 below gives a detailed breakdown of the participants gender, age and their positions.

Table 12: Participants Position, Gender and Age Demography

Respondent Code (Pseudonym)	Gender	Position	Age
Respondent 001	Male	Manager	53
Respondent 002	Male	Manager	58
Respondent 003	Female	Manager	59
Respondent 004	Male	Deputy Manager	48
Respondent 005	Male	Supervisor	44
Respondent 006	Male	Supervisor	47
Respondent 007	Female	Deputy Manager	55
Respondent 008	Female	Supervisor	43

Respondent 009	Male	Manager	60
Respondent 010	Male	Manager	56
Respondent 011	Female	Supervisor	48
Respondent 012	Female	Deputy Manager	40
Respondent 013	Female	Manager	50
Respondent 014	Male	Manager	54
Respondent 015	Male	Supervisor	55
Respondent 016	Male	Manager	48
Respondent 017	Female	Manager	57
Respondent 018	Male	Supervisor	45
Respondent 019	Female	Manager	52
Respondent 020	Female	Manager	53
Respondent 021	Male	Deputy Manager	48
Respondent 022	Male	Deputy Manager	45
Respondent 023	Male	Manager	52
Respondent 024	Female	Supervisor	39
Respondent 025	Male	Supervisor	37

Table 13 provides the gender perspective of the roles occupied and the percentage of each participants.

Participant Gender	Figure	Manager	Deputy Manager	Supervisor	Percentage
Male Participant	15	7	3	6	60
Female Participant	10	4	2	3	40
Total	25	11	5	9	100%

Table 13: Participants Gender and Position Demography

7.1. Conceptualisation of Ethical Leadership

The research question one examines the definition of ethical leadership from the viewpoint of the respondents in the Nigerian public sector. This also correlates to research objective one which entails the investigation of the current conceptualisation of ethical leadership from the perspective of the Nigerian public sector. To meet the requirements and satisfy research objective one and research question two, their understanding of the definition of ethics as an influence on their leader and ethical leadership were included in the interview schedule (please refer to Appendix).

The interviews with leaders in the public sector revealed their perception of ethics and their understanding of who an ethical leader is in the sector. To better understand the concept of ethical leadership from the Nigerian public sector, three questions were posed to the

participants (the managers and supervisors). Respondents provided multiple understanding of ethical leadership and addressed the influence of ethics on their leadership.

Respondents during the interviews provided various definitions of ethics within the public sector. All respondents attested to the fact that ethics can be regarded as the process of differentiating between the concept of right and the concept of wrong. Leaders in the public sector addressed the need for one to have a clear understanding of what is considered right and wrong when carrying out their duties within the organisation. This shaped their approach to different issues and adoption of different styles in their leadership within the organisation and impacted directly and indirectly in every process of their leadership such as decision-making.

Respondent 012 stipulates ethics can also be considered as morals. The respondent further iterates *“the influence on the perception of ethics in leadership concerns the discipline, the ability under process of adapting the concept of morally right and morally wrong to one’s role as an effective leader in an organisation (Respondent 012).”*

There is a consensus by respondents for leaders to have a general perception of what is considered right in terms of a leader’s behaviour and actions. While each respondent provided some examples of the application of ethics in their leadership, there exist different variations to what can be considered right and wrong from a personal standpoint. As this can be strongly influenced by the organisation’s standpoint on what is considered appropriate and what is not considered right. Some respondents attributed this standpoint of ethics and emphasised the importance of organisation’s rules and regulation as a guide in adapting the right behaviours in the organisation. Leaders are bound by organisational standards rather than their own personal understanding of what is right and wrong.

Respondents (003, 005, 009, 013) emphasised the need and importance of a standard guide for ethics in an organisational setting as a way of keeping leaders and employees in line with the right values and to adhere with the organisation's goals and objectives.

This school of thought is further expatiated by Respondent 009 who states that *ethics are sets of rules that are written and unwritten, behavioural patterns that guides the operation of an organisation*. To a large extent the respondent suggests that ethics play a very large role and is very much expected in an organisation. This was implied by other respondents.

Respondents 004 provides a more definitive understanding of ethics within the organisation.

“Well, my own understanding of ethics is the rules and guidelines given to us by the organisation. Without these rules, we cannot function as an organisation effectively. With these rules as a leader, you tend to use it to guide your followers on what is right and wrong when carrying out your duties. There are things leaders must oversee and making sure we follow the rules set is one of the functions of a leader in the refinery (Respondent 004)”.

Respondent 002 provides a more analytical view on ethics and its influence in the public sector of Nigeria. While ethics is the ability to differentiate between right and wrong, the participant stresses the concept as more of one's behaviour than the skills to influence what is morally right and wrong as a leader. The respondent is of the viewpoint that a leader must possess the qualities and the moral behaviours of an ethical leader rather than necessarily possessing the skills of an effective leader. The respondent suggests that one can be skilful and be amoral or unethical in the execution of their duties in the organisation.

Ethics as an instrumental aspect of leadership and its influence is more to do with behaviours rather than skills as a leader. You can possess all the leadership skills necessary to influence and impact your followers but if you don't have the right behaviour to reflect on your subordinate then it is meaningless. Ethics as a role in leadership is more to do with your

behaviour and attitudes towards things and people rather than one's skills. It is you having the right behaviours and attitudes to things and having been brought up with the right behaviours and mindset (Respondent 002). "

Respondent 018 gives a diverse view on how ethics influences leadership. The respondent states that ethics has to do with one's upbringing and one must not be taught the process of ethics. Furthermore, as a leader one should be able to influence employees using your upbringing as a yardstick of right and wrong. Respondent 018 suggests:

"My own knowledge of ethics can be considered as the act of doing what is proper in an organisation and it influences the way an individual within leadership operates to make them go smoothly. Nobody needs to be taught this or what they are supposed to do. This is more about involving one's upbringing and influencing these training on them one way or the other by the way you do things morally within any organisation or job you do (Respondent 018)."

Respondent 007 provides a different perspective as regards ethics and influence on leadership. The respondent provided a nuanced conceptualisation of ethical leadership. The respondent states:

"My understanding of ethics and its influence on leadership will be the ability to apply ethics or morality to leadership. I believe moral or ethical leadership is leadership that is directed by respect for ethical beliefs and values and for the dignity and rights of others. It is thus related to concepts such as trust, honesty, consideration, charisma and fairness.

My perception of ethical leadership goes a long way to imbibing the culture of respect for others, transparency, accountability and integrity and professional excellence (Respondent 007)."

In summary, evidence from the field and the outcome from the interview of the participants shows understanding of the concept of ethics and its influence on leadership. Findings all

concur to the universal belief that ethics can be regarded as the capability to differentiate between right and wrong. This involves having the behaviour, the capacity and the knowledge of distinguishing between doing what is right as a leader and desisting from wrong doings in the public sector. As a leader, one must be able to adapt moral values and influence these values on employees. Participants all concur that ethics and leadership within the sector involves utilising their moral compass and abiding and understanding laid down rules and regulation. This serves as a guide for leaders to follow personally and influence positively and effectively through their behaviours, skills and as role models to their employees within the organisation. Leaders are ideally supposed to possess this knowledge as a way of life as stipulated by Respondent 018 before they are able to implement or influence ethics within subordinates in the organisation.

7.1.1. Ethical leadership definition from the Nigerian Public Sector

All participants during the interview process provided their understanding of the concept of ethical leadership within the Nigerian public sector. To examine the conceptualisation of ethical leadership from a Nigerian public sector perspective, the researcher posed a follow up question to get respondent's perspective on the definition. Respondents all defined the concept into two themes namely, process and ability. Most respondents (23) suggest ethical leadership involves influencing the rules and regulations of the organisation on the employees.

Some participants suggest ethical leadership involves being a role model to the subordinates within the organisation and displaying the attributes of an ethical leader while influencing one's ethics and the organisation's rules, norms and values in achieving the desired outcome. Table 14 and 15 provide a detailed breakdown of the participants definition of ethical leadership from the process and ability standpoint respectively.

7.1.1.1. Ethical leadership as a Process

In terms of definition of ethical leadership from the findings, the appearance of the term “process” appeared 4 times (refer to Table 14). Leaders within the public sector emphasise the concept of process in defining who an ethical leader is and what ethical leadership entails within the organisation.

Table 14: Conceptualisation of Ethical Leadership as a Process

Ethical Leadership Definitions with the term “Process”	Description
1. Ethical leadership can be described as the process of being an ethical leader. An ethical leader you can say is one that guides his or her followers based on both personal moral principles, organisation codes and conducts and delegates instruction.	The process of guiding followers based on personal, organisational principles and delegation skills.
2. Ethical leadership can be described as the process of being an ethic inspired leader	Process of inspiring ethics in your followers.

3. Ethical leadership to me as a manager is the process of defining rules and regulations that create a transparent and cooperative environment for me to manage.	Process of defining rules and regulation
4. Ethical leadership is the process of employing ethics, morals and guidelines to lead your followers.	Process of implementing ethics and rules to lead.

7.1.1.2. Ethical leadership as an Ability

In terms of the definition of ethical leadership from the findings, the appearance of the term “ability” appeared seven consecutive times (please refer to table 15).

Table 15: Conceptualisation of Ethical leadership as an Ability

Ethical Leadership Definitions with the term “Ability”	Description
1. The ability to influence ethical and moral principles when dealing with employees	Using a leaders’ ability or skills to influence moral principles on employees
2. The ability to possess trust, honesty, consideration, charisma and fairness when dealing with employees in an organisation	Having the ability or skills to use the attributes of an ethical leader such as trust, honesty, consideration, charisma and fairness when dealing with employees.

<p>3. Ethical leadership is the ability to use your leadership skills and experience to influence ethic guidelines and regulations of an organisation on our subordinates</p>	<p>Using one's leadership skills and experience to influence ethic guidelines and regulation on subordinates</p>
<p>4. As long as they are doing their jobs well and within the right frame, with the ability for them to freely reach one as a leader and state their concerns</p>	<p>Ability of a leader to be accessible to employees and for employees to be able to state their grievances and concerns to their leader.</p>
<p>5. Ethical leadership is the ability to adapt one's ethical behaviour to fit one's leadership style.</p>	<p>Ability/skills to adapt one's ethical behaviour to fit one's leadership style</p>
<p>6. Ethical leader or what ethical leadership entails is the ability for a leader to adopt and apply his or her own moral beliefs and principles and apply this to those set by the organisation using both experience and his/her skills to influence his/her followers</p>	<p>A leaders' ability or competency to use his/her skills and moral beliefs and those of his/her organisation to govern his/her employees</p>

<p>7. It is the ability to fit one's ethical behaviours into his or her leadership approach through one's competency and taking into consideration organisation's norms and values when leading employees.</p>	<p>A leader imbibing his/her ethical behaviours into his/her approach to leadership using his/her skills and taking into account organisation's norms and values.</p>
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Some respondents iterate ethical leadership involves being a role model to their subordinates with the embodiment of ethics to influence their personal and organisation's objective.

"Ethical leadership simply put is guiding your people, leading by example, and doing the right thing without abandoning your personal or organisational values (Respondent 008)."

Respondent 022 iterates the definition of ethical leadership as the application of the concept of ethics (knowing what is right and wrong) when working with employees, assignment of roles and the delegation of tasks. Few respondents stated that this type of leadership involves an ethic-based approach using leadership styles such as autocratic or democratic forms to foster ethics within the organisation. Some respondents suggest the reason for the adoption of an authoritarian approach within the organisation is based on the outlook one presents especially when you are jovial and open to reach by your employees. Respondent 018 states

"The style of leadership adopted by me is somewhat an authoritarian or autocratic style to be honest this is due to the nature and corrupt culture that has been the bane and infested the Nigerian public sector. If people perceive you as weak, it's a problem and they take you for granted (Respondent 018)."

Respondent 017 suggests the concept ethical leadership involves a transparent and cooperative environment providing a multi-way communication between the leader, the employees and the executives.

“Ethical leadership to me as a manager is the process of defining rules and regulations that create a transparent and cooperative environment for me to manage. It is whereby I manage the demands of those I lead and also from those that have placed me in a particular position or a specific task. As a manager, I communicate with subordinates to understand their needs and expectation from my employees while also having an idea or having a knowledge of what my employees expect from me and my subordinates in my organisation such as rules and regulations.” (Respondent 007)

In summary, ethical leaders within the public sector have provided their understanding of the concept of ethical leadership emphasising how ethics influences their belief and how they affect or influence their employees. In defining ethical leadership, most respondents suggested that it involves the ability or capacity of a leader to influence their moral beliefs and those of the organisation. Some other respondents stipulate the concept of ethical leadership as the process of effecting and inculcating ethic-based leadership upon employees to influence both positive employee and organisational output. In essence, respondents have majorly highlighted the core aspect of organisation’s rules and regulation.

7.2. Skills

This section of this findings chapter discusses the skills identified by leaders as essential in the execution of their duties, effectiveness and success in the public sector. The research question three seeks to identify and explore the required skills necessary for effective ethical leadership in the Nigerian public sector. This also correlates with research objective three which seeks to provide an empirical ethical leadership skill-based framework for the Nigerian public sector.

Haq (2011) posits ethical or ethic-based leadership skills as those skillset learnt and perfected over time to influence ethics within followers while driving performance. To foster efficiency and effectiveness, a leader must possess the ability to positively effect employee commitment and motivation. They ought to provide avenue for growth and development while enforcing ethical values within the organisation without hindering organisational performance.

Several skills were identified through the thematic analysis of participant responses during their interviews within this section. These skills identified are grouped into key themes identified during the coding process. The following skills group identified are core ethical skills, interpersonal skills, technical skills and conceptual skills. Figure 16 below gives a graphical representation of the skills and subskills identified during the field study.

Figure 16: Skills identified from Findings

7.3. Ethical Skills

While the definition for core ethical skills within the body of literature is not provided, some school of thought defined this form of skillset as a complex phenomenon. It is a combination of multiple skills to proffer and influence the concept of ethics within an individual and a group of people. For this research, the researcher adopted the stance of understanding the skills the respondents adopted in effecting ethics on their employees within the Nigerian public sector.

During this research, core ethical skills were identified as the main skill set an ethical leader must possess to stand out from any other form of leader. These skills are essential and ensures a leader can effectively and positively affect follower's perception of the concept of ethics. The followers can also become ethical in the way they carry out their given task and in the long run emulate an ethical leader's attitude in terms of role modelling. Furthermore, leaders who possess these skills are perceived to be highly ethical when they are displayed. The following sub skills identified as the core mechanism for inculcating ethics are ethical awareness, ethical decision-making and integrity.

7.3.1. Ethical Awareness

A theme which emerged during the interview and thematic analysis was the ability of an ethical leader to possess ethical awareness. Some participants (11) during the interview process highlighted the need and necessity of having ethical awareness of the situation within the organisation. Participants cited that a leader should be able to grasp the situation at hand, adopt critical thinking to analyse the situation most especially issues facing ethical concerns. Respondents 003, 012 and 018 emphasised that as leaders, they are faced with situations whereby they have to use their ability of being aware of a situation at hand in the department.

“Well yes it does. In as much the environment feels less ethical, in making critical decisions, ethics plays a role within the organisation. You need to possess the ability to know what is happening at any given time. You have to make sure you have the ability to take control of the situation, use your sense in knowing when to analyse if this goes against your own moral code, the organisation’s ethical guides and also take note of the employee’s own too. How do you weigh these scenarios, how do you analyse these problems and how will it influence how your people see you in the department? You do not have to trample on your ethical belief and that of another individual. Also, are you creating a future problem for yourself if you allow a subordinate not to get punished (Respondent 003).”

Respondent 018 supports the opinion of Respondent 003 that having command of the situation and awareness of an issue that is about to happen within the organisation is key. It can be a distinction between who employees perceive to have integrity and another. A leader needs to be ethically aware and possess the intelligence based on experience to deal with this situation.

7.3.2. Ethical Decision-making Skills

Several respondents (17) suggested that ethical decision-making skills are pivotal in the Nigerian public sector. Participants within the sector iterate the importance of possessing effective decision-making ability in carrying out their roles within the organisation as an ethical leader. While decision making skills can be classified as a conceptual skill within literature, results from participants and some works done within the body of literature suggest ethical decision-making skills are essential to the influence of ethical leadership. It involves the concept and understanding of ethics as a deciding factor in making key decisions. Furthermore, some participants addressed that it is important to carry along employees when making these decisions. From tasks to the execution of assignments passed down from the executive to the managers and supervisors while taking into consideration the ethical issues. Leaders within their various department adopt these skills to effect positive change, plan around employee’s

ability and make decisions on what tasks and roles employees can execute. This is based on their strengths and weaknesses most especially when taking into consideration variation of subordinate moral standpoint and beliefs. A leader should be able to assess, understand, carry along employees and get their opinion during the process of making these moral decisions.

As suggested by some respondents, there are situations whereby a leader must be decisive, abide and adhere to the ethical codes and values both personally and from the organisation's perspective. This in the long-term helps employees to emulate the leader's approach to dealing with ethical challenges and positively influences employee's development in adopting these ethical decision-making skills. This is seen in the quote below.

“You need to be able to be good at employee involvement and taking them along in decision making process. You must be willing to involve followers within the capacity of making critical ethical decision most especially ones that have to do with these individuals assigned to a role or given a task to carry out within the organisation. You as a leader must not make the mistake of assigning tasks to individuals that are incapable of carrying out these tasks. (Respondent 007).”

Some respondents also stress that ethical decision-making skill influences employees to emulate the leader. They are drawn to leaders that take key decisions within the organisation. Respondent 014 quotes,

“You must be very decisive in both decisions taken and in the assignment of tasks to each member of staff. Employees are drawn towards leaders that show and know what they are doing.”

Respondent 010 highlights the need for carrying along employees within the public sector. Furthermore, leaders are supposed to be able to communicate to their followers, listen and inculcate their inputs in the process of decision-making.

“This brings me to the next skill where both communication and listening to your followers come to play, and that is, ethical decision making. You must be able to carry along everyone in the decision-making process (Respondent 010).”

Employees require the input of their leader and their needs are most times expected to be managed and decisions made on their behalf which in turn creates a sense of belonging to their organisation. Evidently, respondents attributed some cases or situations to which they had faced ethical dilemmas within the organisation and had to adopt a proper decision-making process to provide the best possible solution. A good instance can be seen from Respondent 023 situation of the provision of hand gloves for subordinates working within the plant and finding the best possible way to mitigate a reduction in performance due to lack of hand gloves.

“The two things are if the management have provided things and equipment to carry out the job, that is one and the employee is not knowledgeable or ignores guidelines in carrying out his duties and issues abound. Such person is liable to demotion or is removed from the institution but if there are no materials provided for safety and the job requires these equipment's, but it must be done and there arise an issue or accident. We will place the fault on the management as there isn't any provision for workers welfare, in essence the management has failed to carry out its duties.

A leader should be able to make sound ethical decisions in this process while not negatively affecting the performance output of the organisation or negatively affecting employee's perception of one's ethical behaviours. One needs to be a role model in providing these ethical decisions irrespective of the way you feel about a situation in the department” (Respondent 023)

This view is also taken by Respondent 001 on managing subordinates going against organisational policies and how as a leader, one must be able to weigh the situation from an

organisational performance perspective, a leader's perspective and how this will affect the way employees perceive a leader in the organisation. Respondent 001 states:

“Even with these challenges we are facing in the organisation, we need to do our jobs as leaders whether we like it or not. You can't be emotional and have it in your mind they have someone who is at their back to support them at the top. You still have to carry out the institution demand or imposing punishment to the subordinate. You have to serve them query and pass it to the executive branch for investigation. You have done your part as a leader and punished the fellow. It is up to the executive management to act on these actions (Respondent 001).”

7.3.3. Integrity

Integrity was identified as a core ethical skill within the public sector from the outcome of the research findings. While some school of thought within the body of literature have described integrity as an attribute of an ethical leader, some scholars are of the viewpoint that it is the ability to determine the right course of action that is ethical in a given situation or problem. All respondents during the interview stipulated the need for leaders to possess integrity within the organisation. Some participants attributed the need for integrity in every area of leadership within the organisation. As emphasised by some respondents (002, 009, 012, 017), there is a need to show integrity in carrying out their duties.

“Someone with integrity and someone who can help you develop. You must possess the integrity needed to show you are moral and can hold your own in any situation irrespective of who you are dealing with (Respondent 002).”

A leader must be able to display ethical soundness in their judgement, stand by their beliefs and must be able to enforce the right morals and values on employees. Leaders must be able ensure they stand by their guiding principles; they are not emotionally attached to a situation

and must not be biased in any given situation. In the Nigerian public sector, there are various challenges that they face from the corrupt practices and insubordination from employees who have connections at the top. Respondent 021 and 012 all stipulate that a leader's integrity must not be influenced when making decisions or resolving ethical situations within the organisation. As Respondent 012 suggest.

“One should be able to display soundness and must be able to stand by his words and actions irrespective of circumstances within the organisation. As a public institution in Nigeria influenced by a growing case of corruption of illegal practices, you must be able to exhibit transparency through your actions, be accountable to them with integrity and be able to show ways of relating this to the subordinate. You should be able to stand by the right principles (Respondent 012)”

Respondent 017 gives a more diverse view and suggests the need for integrity when proffering fair judgement to employees, most specifically employees with a strong interpersonal relationship with the leader. Employees who perceive leaders to be just, fair and unbiased and stand by their moral code help leaders to motivate the followers to emulate their actions. They create an avenue for subordinates to reach out to them in situations where there is a need for leaders who are reliable. This is seen in the quote below.

“I believe as an ethical leader, you should be firm when dealing with subordinates especially in situations where you don't want to be seen as biased to certain people. I mean those close to you or those you have a very good rapport with. If you are not firm in dishing out punishment, especially to defaulting employees, you stand the risk over time of letting employees think you don't have the integrity and courage to punish them and this breeds insubordination. This will feel as if you are siding those that you consider your own (Respondent 017).”

7.4. Interpersonal Skills

Interpersonal skills can be defined as the knowledge about human psychology, behaviour and group processes. It is the ability to understand the feelings, intentions and the attitudes of others (Haq, 2011). Some scholars have suggested that interpersonal skills can be described as the ability to work with others or understand coordination and processes. During this research, interpersonal skills were identified as one of the integral and key skills needed for an ethical leader to be effective within the Nigerian public sector. The following interpersonal skills identified are communication and listening skills, empathy, team-building skills, motivation skills, employee development skills and political skills.

7.4.1. Communication and Listening skills

One of the key themes that emerged during the interview was communication skills. Communication skills in this regard can be described as a two-way channel between the leader and the follower. The channel is adopted for effectively communicating ethical outcomes and expectation within the organisation. Respondents in this research identified effective communication as one of the key criteria for an individual to become an effective ethical leader within the Nigerian public sector.

Out of the 25 respondents, 22 respondents attested that communication is important and has been effective in carrying out leadership responsibilities and in implementing rules and regulation. Leaders within the organisation are supposed to communicate clearly to their subordinates with various forms or channels of communication. Communication in this regard can be verbal or non-verbal (written form). This is seen in the quote below,

“if you cannot communicate as a leader, then there is a problem. There is a growing issue mostly within this organisation and that’s the problem of effective communication between

both leaders and followers. Proper communication is a necessary element of an effective ethical leader (Respondent 002)”.

A high number of respondents (22) suggested communication skills within the public sector as an important skill an ethical leader must possess to execute their given role within their departments. An effective leader should be able to communicate to his/her subordinates the goals of the organisation, the objectives, the tasks at hand and the requirements of the given tasks while adhering to ethical structures from a personal and organisational standpoint. Leaders are supposed to provide avenues for subordinates to communicate with them within the departments, communicate effectively with executives at the central office and more importantly disseminate the right information in the clearest form and context. This viewpoint is iterated by Respondent 016:

“Communication skills such as clearly talking to your subordinates is very important in this industry especially when dealing with people of different background, language, understanding and level of reasoning (Respondent 016).”

Respondent 006 addresses the ability to listen and communicate with subordinates within the organisation as the most vital skill a leader must possess to influence employees and foster performance. It is important as a leader that you can clearly define ethical guidelines, boundaries in ways they grasp this information.

“Well, the most important skill I will say is the act and experience of being able to listen to your subordinates and communicate rules and regulation. You must be able to clearly define these rules, values and norms of the organisation (Respondent 006).”

This supports the school of thought of Respondent 015 that the skill of being an effective communicator as a leader within the public sector is key. Respondent 015 and Respondent 003

both stressed the relevance of this skillset and the problems which can arise from not possessing effective communication skills.

“One must communicate effectively both ethical guidelines of the organisation and the core values and goals of the institution. As a public body, we have mission statements and tasks needed to be done by everyone within the organisation. If effective communication isn’t adopted and assignment of tasks communicated effectively to our supervisors and team. Then there will be issues arising (Respondent 015).”

“You can possess all the qualifications and years of experience but if you cannot communicate these to your followers then there is no use being a leader. Have you ever seen a leader who cannot talk properly or communicate instructions to his followers, or is shy to talk to his or her employees? People will see that individual as shy or afraid to face issues at hand (Respondent 003).”

Furthermore, Respondent 003 states that as a leader, communication skills also go hand in hand with other leadership skills such as problem-solving skills.

Respondent 005 goes further to stress the importance and the influence of possessing interpersonal and communication skills on employee motivation within the department. Effective leaders are supposed to possess the ability to motivate employees through their actions, their interrelationship with the people they lead and the information they effectively disseminate to their employees using the various channels of communication provided verbally, written or in pictorial form.

“This is an essential part of one’s leadership journey and accomplishment. First you have to... ‘what do they call it’ you must have communicative skills to influence your values and that of the organisation, inter-relationship between a leader and the subordinate and you must perfect these skills so as to know how you can encourage your staff (Respondent 005).”

One must be able to address and communicate organisational instructions, tasks and objectives from the executive and management. You need to channel these instructions to the subordinates in a clear and understandable way for the accomplishment of set out plans and goals without infringing on personal ethical values, rules and guidelines of the organisation.

7.4.2. Empathy

Respondents during the interviews also highlighted empathy as a skill of an ethical leader within the Nigerian public sector. As a leader, a high percentile (14) of the respondents articulated the need for this skill in dealing with subordinate's concerns and in building a bond or working relationship within the organisation. A leader should be able to understand the needs of the followers, show ethical concerns and also respect the values of the subordinates in the organisation. Respondent 025 stipulates the need and the importance of this skill within the organisation.

“It is very necessary and important for one as a leader or in leadership position in the organisation to have empathy. You must have the ability to look at things from the perspective of those who are being led (Respondent 025)”.

This point of view is also buttressed by Respondent 016 especially the importance it plays and the influence on the subordinates.

“One must show empathy towards your subordinates and letting them know you care for their needs and understand their values. As a leader, empathy is necessary as one must not be an individual who is rigid and absent minded towards employee grievances (Respondent 016).”

Another respondent also iterated the need for empathy and the inter-relationship with the skill of effective communication. A leader should be able to connect to his or her followers by being a good listener to the needs, ideas and concerns raised by the followers.

“An effective leader must also be a good listener; this is also part of being empathetic towards your followers. One must be able to listen, not just listen but pay attention to the ideas, issues and suggestions of both employees and also show them you will act on these feedbacks (Respondent 014).”

Respondent 025 suggests a detailed outcome of the importance of an ethical leader being empathetic to the course of the employees within the organisation as an avenue of fostering employee participation and involvement. In essence, employees exhibit organisational citizenship behaviour and are more inclined to exemplify the skills and attitude of their leader than those without empathy within the organisation.

“Employees prefer ethical leaders with the ability to hear their cries. They want to know that both the organisation and oga [Boss] is hearing their voice in everything they do and things of concern to them. They want to participate and want to show you they are dependable. (Respondent 025).”

Respondents concur that they have had to adopt empathy towards employees in their various subsidiaries to get the best out of them and to show concern to their needs. In showing concern to their needs, some of the participants also iterate the need of not just only showing concern to their needs, but also assimilating their needs and concerns. They also acted on the needs of the subordinates if they are in the right capacity to provide this requirement within the confines of ethical principles and guidelines. They ensured that it does not infringe on the rights of others within the organisation. This in turn leads to employees giving their best to the organisation and are most especially committed to the department. In essence, in environments where leaders are empathetic to their subordinates, there is a positive influence on employee performance which in turn leads to organisation’s objectives and goals being attained by the followers.

7.4.3. Team Building Skills

Team building skills as an interpersonal skill was one of the skills to emerge during the course of the interviews. Respondents (6) suggested the need for collaboration with the clear goal of accomplishing a task. Ethical leaders are supposed to create an ethical environment and culture for employees to participate as a member of the organisation. Employees are provided opportunities by leaders to voice out their ideas and concerns while driving organisational citizenship behaviour from their subordinates.

Some respondents suggest the necessity of creating an environment of unbiasedness and equality. By providing avenues for employees to express themselves, the issues and fears of employees not voicing their concerns to them are eliminated. Respondent 017 stressed the need for employee involvement to create an avenue for a leader to influence ethical concepts, values and norms within this environment. Employees are said to be more involved with leaders within the organisation who foster team cohesiveness and can be approached to report incidences such as unethical acts within the refinery. Respondent 017 states:

“You need to be skilful in the act of fostering the spirit of collaboration among the employees. Be involved in what they think about a project, what ideas they present. Help in building teams and making collaborative relationships. You don't want to work in an environment where everyone is keeping to their selves or scared to contribute.”

Respondents also attributed the need for an ethical leader to carry along their followers in every step taken within the organisation. Employees are more inclined to interact with leaders who are team players and provide avenue for fostering team participation in the organisation. Respondent 008 states:

“As an ethical leader, you should be able to carry along your followers and also interact and seek their counsel regarding any issues or challenges facing them and also be unbiased to their concerns and taking actions”.

This school of thought is shared by Respondent 018 who iterates the need for a leader in the organisation to carry subordinates along as a team. For this respondent, leaders need to be able to ensure an avenue for followers to be part of a team, as this allows the leaders and the followers to learn from each other.

“To function properly in this field, you must be able to carry along everybody irrespective of their position. As a leader, you should be able to learn also from your followers whether you like it or not. We all learn every day in the things we do even though we have been here for a very long time.” (Respondent 018)

Respondent 019 iterates the importance of fostering team building within the organisation. Leaders are meant to foster interpersonal relationships and create a level playing ground for employees and leaders to interact. As stipulated by the respondent, this in turn will evoke a two-way transaction between leaders and followers.

“We need a level playing ground for all staff and employees, and relationship. We need strong cordial interpersonal relationship. Because without this relationship, there will be struggle between a leader and followers, without that, a leader won't lead, and a follower won't follow well. So that cordial interpersonal relationship has to be there so that a leader will not look down on a follower and a follower will respect the leader (Respondent 019).

7.4.4. Motivation Skills

Another theme to emerge from the thematic analysis is the ability to motivate employees within the public sector. Several respondents suggest ethical leaders within the Nigerian public sector

must be able motivate employees and also motivate themselves in carrying out tasks while adopting morally right attitudes to inspire work performance within employees. Motivation skills play a critical aspect in leadership effectiveness in any given organisation. As ethical leaders, one must be able to collectively impact their followers through the act of lifting their spirit to enhance performance.

For organisational objectives to be executed, it is necessary that ethical leaders influence followers through motivation. Respondent 020, 024, 007 all posit motivation skills is very vital on subordinates within the public sector. For employees to be able to align to a leader's ethical stance and abide by the strict moral code, it is essential that a leader influences their ethical behaviour and serves as an example to the employee. Leaders are only as effective as the way they carry themselves through positively influencing their personal beliefs, values and organisation beliefs on employees. Respondent 024 suggests this skill of an ethical leader helps one stand out and differentiates a manager from an effective leader.

“A leader is a good manager. As a leader, you should be able to have the capacity of influencing your followers and effectively leaving a positive impact on the subordinate. Most people are good at just managing and following guidelines of duties and assigning duties to people but to be a leader, you should be able to carry them along, influence their action morally, positively and guide them to achieve the desired result. You should be able to impact your followers to the extent they possess the values, ethical compass and attitudes of a leader (Respondent 024).”

Some respondents (0013, 006) suggest leaders must possess the ability to influence their subordinates to meet the organization's goals and objectives. Respondent 006 states:

“Leadership can be described as getting things done through influence on people to achieve objectives within the organisation. This involves the ability of leading, assigning and guiding

people through various tasks and assignments to achieve organisational performance and the main goal of the company” (Respondent 006).

Respondents agreed that while this skill plays a critical role in the way employees perceive one within the organisation, one should be able to influence the right set of attitudes, character, values and behavior dealing with followers. This is not just through verbal communication but through the way a leader carries his/herself within the organisation. Employees are more inclined to adapt and understand one’s perspective and the way a leader influences ethics through their character. Participants emphasized that this ability could affect the employee commitment to abiding by the rules and regulation of the organisation positively or negatively when faced with the issues surrounding ethical dilemmas. Employees who are positively influenced by their leader tend to emulate the thought process and values. If a leader walks the talk, and influences the followers positively, there is a positive effect on the way the employees carry out their assignments taking note of the rules and regulations that have been inculcated by their leader. Respondent 025 gives a clear understanding of the positive effect of motivation skills on followers through leading by example or being a role model within the organisation.

“In the absence of a leader, your followers should be able to pass and emulate the things you do to accomplish given things. Example will be in a place where they are to make a decision and you are not there. They should be able to think to themselves and ask what Oga [Boss] will do to achieve the right results. Or what steps will Oga [Boss] make to carry out this plan and activity (Respondent 025).”

In essence, a leader’s motivation skill in the inculcation of right ethical values within the organisation is pivotal to the effectiveness of how employees perceive ethical leadership. A leader must be able to accomplish set out organisational tasks and objectives, through their understanding and assimilation of what is morally right and morally wrong, aligning these

beliefs with that of the organisation and influencing these beliefs on the followers. While some respondents did state motivation skills played a crucial role in the way employees perceive their ethicality, one of the respondents did highlight that this can also be adopted in the negative way. Respondent 013 states:

“While ethical leadership is the ability to influence my employees according to my universal ethical beliefs and those of the organisation, you must be able to instill the right ethos within them. If you are to walk the talk, be able to live by example in the way you carry out your duties diligently and effectively. Your subordinates are watching you in all you do both in the office and even when they see you outside the office. If you are preaching ethics and all righteous to them and you are acting differently or they perceive you are a pretender in your attitude, this will influence their actions poorly too. Employees will take you for a fraud and will indulge in your negative practices in the long run. This means as a leader you have negatively influenced their actions due to your own ways.”

Respondent 001, 005 and 007 all concurred to the existence of reward management systems to foster motivation within employees and leaders alike. However, these mechanisms do not tend to curb the issues of lack of motivation as individuals within the public sector are promoted regardless of the outcome of their performance in the organisation. Furthermore, some leaders who are unethical in nature influence the perception of indulging in unethical or amoral behavior on other leaders and also drive employees to adopt these unethical behaviors. These respondents emphasized the need to inculcate and provide intrinsic motivation from the leader and imbibe the culture of rewarding those who are ethical and punish those who are not ethical in the organisation. Respondent 007 states

“We are in an environment whereby people most times are down psychologically due to one reason or the other, or seeing things happen beyond their control from management above.

You need to be able to drive people through motivation and bring out the best in them by cheering them, or else employees will not give their best and this will affect performance in the organisation, and this will reflect on you one way or the other (Respondent 007)."

7.4.5. Employee Development Skills

The ability of a leader to develop their subordinates in any given organisation is one of the critical skills of an effective ethical leader. Ethical leaders are driven by the interpersonal relationship through the act of showing concern to their followers and letting them know that they are worthy and belong within the organisation. One of the recurrent themes to emerge during the interview from respondents was the employee development skills. Respondents (8) implore that ethical leadership require the skillset to foster employee development within the organisation. Leaders are to foster employee growth and development through interpersonal relationships, communicating and influencing ethical norms and culture. This is seen in the quote below,

"If you mean communication, decision making and carrying your followers along yes it does foster employees to engage more with you and the organisation. They give their best because they feel connected to the organisation and they will perform better because you have created a platform for them to grow and be expressive (Respondent 011)."

Respondent 002 implores that employees are eager to work with leaders who possess integrity and create room for them to execute their giving task.

"Employees are willing to work with someone with integrity and someone who can help you develop in a balanced and unbiased environment."

Respondent 019 suggests that a leader must possess this skill and is necessary in the development of ethical followers. This school of thought also suggests that ethical leaders are more inclined to ensure a culture and succession system within the organisation of making

ethical leaders out of followers. These followers are inspired by the culture and ability to personally develop and master their skills within the organisation. Respondent 019 states:

'If there is that cordial relationship and level playing ground. If there is no fear about anybody's worse with respect to authority, you will find out there will be respect on all sides. Remember that there must be a foundation that before you become a leader you were once a follower. The important thing is to let room for the follower to assist and grow into the job. Listen to them. Because there are times a follower will advise a leader. Because only one person cannot carry the whole wisdom upon his head. Some of your followers are able to provide good advice on some issues, and when they provide this advice all things will go well. Do not forget they also have the capability of doing better when put through in the right way and ethical setting (Respondent 019)'.

In summary, to foster employee effectiveness and to inculcate and communicate moral values, organisational rules, ethical leaders within the public sector should ensure employees are provided the avenue for self-efficacy, job autonomy to carry out their given tasks while being bound by the ethical code instilled in them. Respondents (002, 008, 011, 017, 019) stress that to positively effect employee commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour, there should be room for them to feel empowered and be part of an ethical community. This in the long run leads to increased performance. Furthermore, these respondents also highlight that this helps foster an effective ethical leadership culture within the organisation. Through a leader's ability to foster employee development, employees are inclined to give their best and become part of the team in terms of performance, follow laid down guidelines and help mitigate unethical behaviours within the organisation.

Employees who feel they are part of the team and follow in the leader's footsteps aid in reporting unethical issues. This atmosphere creates an environment whereby employees and

leaders alike have faith in their contribution to performance following these laid down guidelines and also voice out their concern. This creates a level playing field for employees.

7.4.6. Political Skills

Political skill was identified by two respondents during the interview process (Respondent 014 and 022). Respondent 014 suggests a leader must be able to adapt to the situation of subordinates in the Nigerian public sector. A leader must be able to understand the personality of their subordinates for the purpose of achieving the organisation's objective. Leaders are meant to understand their followers, create a perception of ethicality and ensure they influence their employees to carry out tasks and objectives. Leaders should be political and good negotiators. This is seen in the quote below.

“You must be able to also negotiate with employees, stakeholders and executives within this terrain. Nigeria public sector is unpredictable and dealing with people most especially those within the community that have influence within the organisation. One as a leader should be able to adjust to your employee's situation, you need to be able to come to their level and understand them and channel this issue to something positive in the organisation (Respondent 014).”

7.5. Technical skills

Katz (2009) posits that technical skills involves methods, processes, techniques and procedures that foster better understanding of a particular subject matter or field. These skills include rules, structure, background, factual knowledge and employee characteristics of the organisations (Katz, 2009; Haq, 2011). This also involves the knowledge of the organisation's culture, customs, understanding and knowledge of ethics, rules and regulations. Within the public

sector, these include specialty knowledge acquired from formal education or training programmes such as university degrees to be better equipped or suited to bring change and foster performance within the organisation.

During the course of the interview, participants stated the presence of technical skills as a requirement and the need for an ethical leader to possess such to be effective and efficient in the Nigerian public sector. The technical skills which emerged were education and training and experience. Respondents highlight these skills are necessary in influencing the activities and the performance of the organisation.

7.5.1. Education and Training

All respondents during the course of the interview attributed the need of education and training for an ethical leader. Respondents emphasised the need for academic degrees ranging from a diploma and other qualifications during their career journey. They are provided further training programmes to develop their skills, their knowledge of the way the organisation works such as the refineries and how to manage the subordinates they are tasked to lead in the organisation. Respondent 010 explained that at the beginning of a leader's journey in the organisation, they are employed based on the relevant degree needed,

“Erm... when we started at the beginning in NNPC, it was with national diploma in electrical engineering, do you understand? There used to be a time when we were all promoted together because it was still in the beginning. But after a while it was not the same and I have to do more degree programs to support our diploma and help in taking us further (Respondent 010).”

As a leader, one must be equipped with the right skill set to take on roles and accomplish task and objectives within any given organisation. All participants were of the suggestion that leadership skills development were provided during the course of their career journey within the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation. Respondents 001 and 003 both attest to the fact

that training programmes are provided based on the level one attains from being a junior staff, to becoming a senior staff (attaining supervisory role within the organisation) and moving towards managerial positions. Attaining these managerial positions, leaders are meant to attend strict leadership training courses which are required for them to understand the concept of leadership within the organisation, garner the appropriate skill and also examine their performance and suitability for the managerial role within the organisation. This is seen in the quote below,

“During the course of your service year in the NNPC, individuals are equipped with several training courses both home and abroad for both self and professional development. When one reaches the senior staff level 3 (SS3) you are required and mandated to go for leadership courses to develop yourself in order to take up a deputy manager role or managerial role. These courses are mandatory and can take 3 months to complete before an individual is promoted to a deputy manager. Also, these courses are like examinations and you need to pass them and show you possess the leadership skills and experience to lead in the institution. Yes, these programs are provided to make sure you meet these responsibilities (Respondent 001).”

7.5.2. Experience

While all participants are of the positive opinion that education was a key criterion for recruitment, and leadership training and skills development programmes were provided during the course of their progression, a few participants were of the suggestion that skills training and development programmes are not enough within the organisation. Respondent 019 is of the opinion that even though this leadership training exists, she has over the years learned on the job. Respondent 019 states:

“Unfortunately, there are leadership training programmes and skill development courses that are provided for us during the course of our leadership journey. But as a leader within the public sector such as NNPC, you are not fully equipped with the right skill set to tackle some challenges. As for me, over the years I have learned to develop my skills and learn on the job as one is promoted to a new role. I believe there are some things that are not adequately taught during the course of leadership training programmes (Respondent 019). “

In essence, findings from this research shows that while there is evidence of education and training programmes, some respondents believed that these development programmes are not enough in the course of their leadership roles and responsibilities. Furthermore, it is perceived and suggested from the findings that there are some certain circumstances that these leaders feel the skills acquired from the training programmes are not sufficient to cater for within the public sector. In addition, some skills are better learnt on the job rather than during the training programme. Some skills are best learnt via experience in the field. As an effective leader in the public sector, you do not learn your skills just through a programme. But you must continuously adapt and learn new skills to deal with employees of different background, values and mindsets. In summary, according to the respondents, these training programmes are adequate, but they are not enough to deal with dynamic challenges facing employees and the organisation as a whole.

7.6. Conceptual Skills

Conceptual skills are skills that provides an individual the capacity to proffer solution and coordination and the ability to make decisions in complex situations (Haq, 2011). These skills include the ability to analyse, provide insight to a given problem and make a final decision in a complex situation (Haq, 2011; Yukl, 2001). These skills are required by leaders to help solve

and deal with situations arising and strategies for the future. Ethical leaders are said to be more effective possessing these skills and utilising these set skills in the public sector. The conceptual skills that emerged from the findings are problem solving skills, analytical skills, idea-generation skills and envisioning skills. Respondents stressed the need for the adoption of these skills within the Nigerian public sector.

7.6.1. Problem-Solving Skills

All respondents (25) attributed the need for problem-solving skills as an ethical leader within the public sector. As an ethical leader, no matter the circumstances faced within the public sector, you should be able to provide solutions to problems facing the organisation. Furthermore, Respondent 007 emphasised that ethical leaders need to be innovative in proffering solution or involving followers (follower involvement) in decision-making even though most of the control within this sector is centralised and influenced from governmental or external factors. An ethical leader should foster problem-solving measures and innovative concept without deviation from moral and ethical values. This is seen in the quote below,

“See, even though one has attained several years of experience in this sector, you will be shocked that to tackle a problem an individual who is new in the sector can provide ideas or solution to a specific challenge. You need to be able to use your knowledge, share ideas in line with rules and regulation and allow your own subordinates to be innovative to help solve the problem (Respondent 009).

Furthermore, all respondents (25) clearly stated that they have had to adopt and utilise their experience in the field to solve given problems within their departments, be it ethical or conventional in nature.

7.6.2. Analytical Skills

Participants (19) stated that ethical leaders need the ability to analyse ethical situations and weigh these issues to affect their decision-making process. Respondent 001, 005, 017 all concur that as leaders when faced with issues during their experience they have had to adopt and analyse the issues facing them within the refinery. These leaders attributed the need to analyse ethical situations stemming from cultural, ethnic and ethical beliefs. Respondent 017 highlights the importance of using one's analytical skill to solve complex ethical situations such as allowing employees the opportunity to be autonomous in their specific assignment. Ethical leaders should be able to weigh their strengths and weakness, and delegate tasks based on their performance outcomes. Respondent 005:

“You also need to be able to involve them in planning and delegating task. Delegation and sorting of task appropriate to employee's speciality is also a necessary skill one must possess in the public sector (Respondent 005) “

This standpoint is also supported by Respondent 017 who iterates that a leader needs these skills to lead effectively and to influence their followers. An ethical leader must be able to observe the subordinate's strengths, assess their understanding of the rules and regulation, and proffer job specific tasks for employees who have strong standing within these roles. They should aid those in need of assistance guiding them according to the confines of the organisation's ethical structure and culture. Respondent 017 states:

“The needs of the subordinates are most times expected to be managed by the leader which would in return create a sense of belonging to the company they work for. You must be result driven even in our sector being a public sector. It is very essential to be driven to get the best result through your intelligence and directing people” (Respondent 017).

Furthermore, ethical leaders are tasked with balancing the performance output of the organisation and base this performance outcome from the employee perspective. They perform a risk analysis on the effect of these ethical issues on the positive and negative influence on all stakeholders involved. Respondent 001 states.

“To be instrumental in this service, you need to be able to assess your subordinates and know what they are very capable of doing and what they are not too good at doing. Also, you need to be able to think properly and balance their capabilities to the right activities and assignments they need to do in this institution. Because if you notice, most of the setbacks you can see is due to lack of desire, poor decisions taken and lack of ability to select the best candidates for the best task. This is also evident in promotions (Respondent 001).”

7.6.3. Idea-Generation skills

Five respondents suggested that ethical leaders should possess the ability to generate ideas to be effective within the public sector. Idea generation involves thinking outside the box and fostering team participation and inclusiveness while supporting employee voice (Respondent 015, 009, 004). While this is a skill necessary to thrive and foster organisational performance, the public sector environment in Nigeria do not foster innovation due to the slow process of idea formulation from the top executives and also the lack of voice for employees and ethical leaders alike (Respondent 001).

7.6.4. Envisioning skills

Envisioning skills also emerged as one of the outcomes from the research findings. Some respondents (4) suggested that ethical leaders require vision and goals when dealing with employees and fostering performance. Respondent 024 emphasized that as an effective leader, they need goals both in the short and long term when planning and strategizing for the organisation. Respondent 024 states:

“You cannot be a good ethical leader if you don't have the ability and capacity to look ahead and plan the right direction for the unit. You should be able to set targets and envision. Also know how to bring people along with your vision for the organisation, allow expression of talent from employees through decisive belief in employees ability and providing them thorough feedback on their performance (Respondent 024).”

7.7. Challenges

The purpose of this section is to investigate the ethical issues and challenges facing ethical leaders within the public sector. This section addresses research question four and explores current issues and antecedents to the ineffectiveness of the ethical leadership-based framework within Nigeria's oil and gas sector (which is a snapshot of the Nigerian public sector). Furthermore, the researcher tries to explore the prevalent ethic-based challenges facing leaders within the public sector and how these issues affect or influence their performance. This also addresses objective two of this research. The Nigerian public sector faces a growing number of concerns ranging from wide reports of mismanagement to ineffectiveness in various levels of the sector. This as seen in institutions such as the NNPC led to the decadence in productivity and has negatively affected performance from the employees and the organisation.

This research question explores the participants perspective on the perceived problems and brings to light the ethical dilemmas within this sector. Some studies have addressed the issues facing the effectiveness of ethical leaders in different sectors and from different demographics such as the western perspective. The researcher tries to investigate if these ethical issues are prevalent within the Nigerian public sector or are there other internal and external factors faced.

All participants within this research acknowledged that they have been saddled with ethical issues during their leadership roles. These participants provided various examples and

scenarios of ethical dilemmas they have faced and how these issues affect them as a leader and impacts the employees and the organisation as a whole. The following themes (factors) emerged during this research as the impediments or limitation that can affect the effectiveness of ethical leaders within the organisation. These include internal and external factors, inadequate level of ethical leadership skills, disregard for rules and regulation and cognitive dissonance & group prototypicality.

7.7.1. Internal and External Factors

There are instances highlighted by participants of interference from internal forces backed by employees with strong relationship with those in top management such as the executive management at the headquarters. Leaders within these subsidiaries are faced with the growing issue of effecting their leadership on employees who possess substantial backing, and this in turn leads to a breakdown in organisational structure. It also directly or indirectly creates a perception within employees in the organisation that any individual can get away with doing unethical acts or not adhering to the rules and regulation.

Some participants also attribute the structure of leadership within the public sector as a challenge. As a public organisation, decision-making process follows a hierarchical structure whereby most decisions pertaining to communicating information takes time to be analysed and executed in the organisation. Furthermore, some respondents were also of the opinion that due to the centralisation of power residing within the government or the appointed executives, implementing an individual based ethical leadership in their department might not be feasible. One must adhere strictly to all necessary guidelines provided from leaders at the top of the organisation. Respondent 009 iterates:

First problem facing this institution as any other within the Nigerian public sector is the issue of the span of people in control. As a public enterprise, there are so many people in authority

that so many things have to pass through them. So many leadership ladders to climb for things to be signed off or approved. This issue takes its toll on organisational performance and the growth too. There are many paper works that have not been signed off or approved due to the nonchalant nature of people at federal management to sign and this takes a lot of time, some maybe weeks or months.... While some, only the grace of God can help you if it sees the day of light. Not just time consuming, there are also ethical doctrines and beliefs of these leaders at the top. What one will consider ethically right and morally right might be different from another who has to approve a proposal. You also have some religious belief to some situations (Respondent 009).

External factors affecting the non-adherence to rules and regulation can be attributed to involvement and interference from government, community heads or politicians. Respondent 014 suggests an interference from government officials external to the organisation's management structure. From the respondent's viewpoint, leaders are faced with a growing influence from government officials and those within the ministries and corridors of power.

“There used to be a time whereby leaders who hold moral standards and are perceived with high ethical values provide support and help in carrying the fellow workers along in providing direction. But interference from top government officials in power have seen employees with connections disobey directives from managers or fail to turn up for work or carry orders that supersedes ours. This is detrimental to one's position as a manager and you do not want issues with powers from the political spectrum (Respondent 014)”.

Another key interference and obstruction to effective ethical leadership are the employee union bodies such as NUPENG and PENGASSAN within the Nigerian public sector. Employees or leaders within these bodies have sometimes flouted rules and regulations or used the excuse of going for union meetings or events and not turned up to work. Respondent 003 states:

“There are some cases where employees come late to work once a while or some cases where employees cut corners to get the job done. While we try to effect these rules, some are backed by external or higher forces. I have seen a scenario where some are contracted to work but because they are part of a union like NUPENG or PENGASSAN they fail to turn up to work for some days. When you take it up with management, you hear different stories or actions are not taken. Or you see individuals flouting rules of taking fuel products from the refinery because of their position. My son, there are many challenges that if we start to mention them, there won't be enough time or space to go through them. The Nigeria public sector lacks respect for ethic rules that's where you see various challenges coming to the NNPC and there is lack of productivity (Respondent 003).”

Another major ethical issue facing effectiveness of leadership within the Nigerian public sector can be ascribed to government involvement and community interference. Participants during this research in one way or the other suggest government involvement in literally almost every aspect of governance of the organisation. As an organisation within the public sector, government have full autonomy in terms of control, policy making, filling leadership positions and influencing promotion. Some respondents believe that there is a high level of influence from those in power such as senators, politicians and ministers and people who know them are favoured in the organisation.

Some of the respondents also attribute the issue of community involvement as an issue of ineffectiveness in the public sector from a leadership standpoint. As an organisation serving the public, there is an advocacy for the organisation to give back to the community through a form of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and community involvement. As Respondent 006 and Respondent 007 place it, the organisation is faced with employing individuals from the community from certain regions inside the organisation. This is a form of giving back to the people while disregarding merit as a criterion for employee recruitment and retention. Firstly,

this creates a competency and skills gap for those getting into the organisation and a sense of godfatherism within the organisation. In the long run, this creates a breakdown in terms of employing those who align with the organisational culture. Employment is based on ethnic or cultural lines, and community or religious doctrine as opposed to merit. Respondent 006 states:

“Challenges in the public sector... for instance from my personal experience and having worked most of the years within the Warri environment, I would say one of the prevalent issues affecting our institution is the issue of absorbing the community within the organisation. As a government body exploring and refining petroleum here, we are tasked to recruit some employees from the local community. Meeting this quota in recent years have had several effects on the organisation as a whole as local chiefs tend to sway people into the organisation especially people with no merits or qualification to fill these posts. I know as a public body we are meant to recruit and show community social responsibility, but this should be done based on criteria and merits and not favouritism or he or she is part of one chief family or is connected to the chief (Respondent 006)”

Respondent 007 also states that not only community involvement or government interference through employment create avenues for ethical issues, there is also the issue of policy making, strategic planning and innovation. Respondent 007 states:

“This is more of a public organisation and not really a commercial enterprise per say. As a government parastatal, it does not operate as a commercial organisation or commercial entity as compared to another organisation. Let us take for instance the private sector where practice, performance and culture are strictly driven by a well guided code of conduct or rules and regulation. This is directed and done by the government in every way. There is a limit to the performance output and the standards due to government policies or untimely response of attending to issues (Respondent 007).”

Participants concur that there are several ethical challenges facing them as leaders within the public sector that has over the years hindered their growth from a personal point of view and the organisation's performance. Following up from the previous question posed to these leaders, respondents all attribute the growing challenges to corruption related issues within the organisation and the Nigerian public sector. Respondent 010 suggests the disparity in terms of religious beliefs and ethnicity, or tribe influences the selection of the right leaders into position of authority. As stipulated by the respondent, these leaders who are selected based on favouritism tend to adopt their own understanding of the conception of values, morals and leadership styles which in the long run has negative consequences on employees. They govern employees with diverse religious or cultural beliefs within the organisation and this in turn affects the output in terms of productivity and performance. Respondent 010 states:

“Tribalism and religious beliefs create the problem and challenges facing leadership effectiveness in the Nigerian public sector. This is also supported with Godfatherism and discrimination over capable locals for preference to foreign expertise. Most of the managers lack leadership training and only utilise the cultural styles of leadership which are aggressive and direct to subordinates and to challenges they face within the organisation (Respondent 010)”.

Respondent 005 stated that a hinderance to the effectiveness of ethical leadership in the public sector also stems from the performance output of the refinery mechanisms and production. Most of the organisational facilities within most subsidiaries in the organisation are not running at full capacity. This is due to the negligence on the part of the government such as government non-involvement in providing the proper maintenance to most of their plant engines. This all stems back to government's lack of provision of the turnaround needed based on the recommendations put forward by the managers and the suggestions made by employees on the best possible solution to some of these problems. Turn-around maintenance are not given the

priority which they need and most executives in some parts of the organisation must be persuaded through shady methods. This supports Respondent 006 viewpoint that “who you know” gets the job done in the organisation.

7.7.2. Inadequate Level of Ethical Leadership Skills

Some respondents addressed the shortage of skills in navigating ethical situations as well as delivering organisational outcomes. This creates a growing problem for leaders trying to influence and impact their employees and also in the long run affects their personal and organisational performance. This can also be linked to favouritism and nepotism on the part of government incursion in these public organisations. This is seen in the quote below.

“There is the issue of nepotism, I think this is the major drawback for performance and growth within this institution. It is very rampant and glaring within this public institution. There aren’t any regards for employing or retaining people on merit and skills within the organisation. People are employed and promoted based on you knowing people or you’re from a specific ethnicity. That’s why you see some people within a certain position who do not know the nature of the job or what to do with regards to responsibility. It is really discouraging seeing this as the best people are not picked or employed. This has been the cause of the drawbacks in this organisation moving forward.” (Respondent 005).

Respondent 023 addresses the ethical concerns faced when dealing with employees who try to adopt unethical acts or behaviour in achieving the given tasks assigned to them by their leader within the organisation. There are dilemmas faced in the aspect of balancing work expectation and trying to adhere to one’s ethical principles or organisational rules and regulation. Respondent 023 states:

“We sometimes face issues or have to deal with followers (subordinates) that do not want to carry out the work, or are not ready to work within the confines of the rules of ethical conduct

because they want to meet the target, they don't want to put in the effort or they see some of those leaders within high position getting away with these conducts (Respondent 023)."

Some respondents recognised the issues facing ethical leader's skills with regards to trust, voice, integrity and prototypicality and how these affects performance from the leader's perspective, employee's perspective and of their respective organisation. Respondent 001 suggests:

"Now also, there is the case of lack of voice within the organisation. There isn't any room for employees to voice out issues or question higher authority. If you do, you will face query or different challenges due to you voicing out. There are times higher authority issues a directive to do some things and you know within you some of these things are unethical in terms of practice but to challenge or voice out such to the top management can be of harm to your career or progression as a whole. Also, there isn't any room for you to chip in some ideas or room to be innovative to solve problems due to the fear of being a target." (Respondent 001).

Respondent 005 statement concurs with Respondent's 001 concern of lack of voice within the organisation. They suggest that a lack of voice within the organisation leads to a disregard of employee's input and ideas to organisational performance and creates no room for idea generation and innovation. Respondent 005 states:

"There is limited room for voicing concerns or inputting ideas as there are from management and the challenge with this organisation, it is not a fully commercialised organisation. The challenge is that individual concept is difficult to formulate ideas and little room for innovation as most are directed and guided by government policies. Promoting and directing appointment, all this are directed by the government and that affects production and performance. This are not properly taken into account. These are all formulated from those above (Respondent 005)."

Respondent 007 suggests also that there is a shortage or lack of ethical competency, ethical skills needed to face the challenges surrounding nepotism within the organisation both with dealing with subordinates and managing ethical situations with those in executive management.

“We are not equipped with the skillset to deal with issues to tackle nepotism or the avenue to not only question ethical issues arising from subordinates but also people within higher authority (Respondent 007).”

7.7.3. Disregard for Rules and Regulation

Participants within this research all agreed that there exists a major concern and an ethical challenge in the aspect of disregard of laid down rules and regulations within each subsidiary of the institution. Leaders from each of these subsidiaries all stipulate that the disregard for rules and regulation can be attributed to several number of factors within the institution. Furthermore, the respondents also stated that this is not just from the employee/follower’s standpoint, leaders as well tend to flout these rules within the organisation or aid in the disregard of laid down guidelines. Most of the culprits of these acts tend to be the leaders themselves. Example of flouting of rules and regulations is highlighted by Respondent 009,

“People generally find it difficult to adhere strictly with the ethics of the organisation. So, whipping them on-line can be challenging at times. There are times whereby individuals ignore set guidelines and act unethically because they possess a different ethical belief to certain issues or there is support from top management at the headquarters (Respondent 009)”.

Respondent 001 provides a more detailed view on the major reason why employees or leaders within the public sector flout these laid down rules and regulation. Respondent 001 states:

“Like I said, due to the issue of nepotism and who you know within the organisation or in government, I have seen cases where one individual came in drunk to work and another did not even turn up for the shift because they know someone at the top who can vouch for them or squash their case. Also, the individuals can also write negative comments about you and can be negative in your progression appraisals. So, there are so many ethical problems currently facing us in this institution and if care is not taken there wouldn't be any point of return (Respondent 001).”

From this perspective, these participants during the interview process have all highlighted issues from the employee's viewpoint in the disregard of rule of law or non-adherence to these rules. This is based on certain interference from internal and external forces supporting the flouting of rules and regulations by employees within the organisation.

7.7.4. Cognitive Dissonance and Group Prototypicality

Another broad theme to emerge from the findings is cognitive dissonance and group prototypicality. Evidence from findings attribute the challenge to some issues arising from threat to a leader's integrity, perceived threat to a leader's career goals, pressure to deliver performance output and the differentiation in ethical beliefs and moral values within the organisation. Cognitive dissonance was identified as an outcome, as leaders within the organisation over a long period of time adopt these amoral behaviours during the course of their leadership. Furthermore, due to a distortion in leader ethicality and an overall organisational unethical culture within the public sector, leaders are more inclined to be indirectly influenced by the behaviours of the followers and their co-managers. In essence, ethical leaders become amoral or are perceived as likely to be less ethical in their behaviours to followers and in the execution of their roles.

Some participants highlighted a growing concern with regards to leaders meeting up with the demands of certain targets set by top-tier management with limited resources provided. This in turn affects the way leaders perform within the sector as they are faced with the challenge of keeping up an ethical identity while also tasked with the responsibility of meeting key performance requirement of the organisation. There are instances within the organisation where leaders are faced with the possibility of adopting amoral practices or encouraging amoral activities to meet up with the requirement while foregoing laid down rules and regulations. Some respondents suggest instances where these problems arise within subsidiaries with infrastructures needing maintenance and lack of resources to meet the demand of maintenance. Respondent 003, 004, 018 and 023 identify a dissonance in leader's ability to effect core ethical guidelines in order to meet performance. Respondent 023 states:

“Yeah well, in order to do one, the worker is supposed to do his or her job right. The management is supposed to provide the necessary equipment and environment to carry his duty effectively. But in a case where an operator is to carry out an operation within the plant with a hand glove and there isn't any hand glove. He is not required to go and do that thing with his bare hand it is the fault of management not providing the necessary safe equipment to work with and not the fault of the worker. But if there are hand gloves and the worker carries out his checks and duties without the required safety equipment's and there is an accident then he or she is liable to face disciplinary actions or sacked from the job as all have been provided for him” (Respondent 023).

Respondents 008, 012 and 013 suggest that the prevailing ethic problem facing them as leaders in the public sector ranges from a lack of core ethical attributes from the points of leadership and followership. As a leader, one must be able to imbibe and foster the culture of honesty, trust and avenue to report ethic-based incidences within the organisation. As Respondent 012 stipulate, there exist limited effective avenues and follow up mechanisms for reporting due to

fear of interference or the slow-paced approach to which these ethic incidences are tackled by the management. This creates a knock-on effect on both leader and employee who are unwilling to report these incidence and issues to the management. This also creates in the long term a cultural belief that an individual can get away with unethical issues.

Some respondents addressed the issues regarding effectively communicating ethical values towards employees and lack of skills addressing follower's ethical norms and beliefs.

“While communication is an integral aspect as a leader in any given institution, there are certain issues facing communicating ethics and values in a public institution as this. You need to understand we are in a society where to do the right thing to move to the top is scarce. Now, imagine communicating this to your team for example while individuals from other units are being promoted because they are cutting corners. It's very difficult. Also, there are individuals who have a different belief to what is right as opposed to one's own, how do you navigate this and effectively communicate this standard” (Respondent 011).

Participants also highlighted the challenges faced by ethical leaders within the organisation due to the inability to grow in position through promotion. Respondent 010 suggests while there are avenues for growth, there are some instances where leaders who do not possess the right qualification within a certain period do not progress after a period. While they do possess the qualities of an effective leader and have a strong influence on employees within the organisation, there are times these issues of no promotion or the fear of a mass recruitment create a sense of not being wanted within the organisation. This leads to instances where there is a loss of motivation within the leader. As a leader, when you lose drive to be effective due to lack of growth and development while others excel without meeting these requirements, it creates a feeling that being amoral within the organisation is beneficial. Subordinates also

observe these issues in the organisation when they sense an iota of demoralization within these ethical leaders. This is seen in the quote below.

“Does it involve ethic of the work or ethics as a statement? Well yes, it is something we face within the sector. Ermm... when we started at the beginning in NNPC, it was with national diploma in electrical engineering. There used to be a time when we were all promoted together because it was still in the beginning. But after a while it was not the same and have to do more degree programs to support our diploma and help in taking us further. So those issues are persistent and still there till this day just because there are people who have spent over 10 years because their qualification can no longer provide an avenue for progression within the refinery. So, most people are not promoted because they do not possess these degrees because I can still recall there was a mass retirement because people didn't possess these qualifications, so in essence if you cannot get further qualifications or degree, such individuals will remain in the position they are occupying till when they are due for retirement or there is a call for mass retirement (Respondent 010).”

While some addressed the presence of infrastructure to foster its effectiveness, these mechanisms are only attributed towards the human resources department and not the organisation as a whole. This is seen in the quote below.

“Ethical leadership is only existent within the human resource department, such as implementing rewards motivation systems for employees who perform but this does not exist at all within the operations side of the organisation. You might say it is only practised by the HR but no other departments as people do not regard ethics to the full extent “. (Respondent 001)

Respondent 009, 012 and 018 all state the issues faced over a period of time changes the way ethical leaders are perceived due to the unethical environment in which they find themselves. These pushes these leaders to adopt unethical means to get the job done due to job progression,

meeting organisational deadlines and the fear of being appraised badly. Leaders highlighted the stress this causes most of their peers which pushes them to put aside ethical standards and personal values for the benefit of becoming favoured. This is seen in the quote below;

“It affects them in such a way that if the number of unethical leaders is more than the ethical ones and if the unethical ones are superior in position to those who are ethical, the ethical leaders are forced to keep quiet and watch in order to preserve their source of livelihood (Respondent 018).”

Almost half the respondents did attribute there are times one had to adopt these measures due to the strain over time from the unethical culture within the organisation and this also affects the employees over a long period of time. This is seen in the quote below.

“Yes, it does, due to the competitive and extreme environment to get tasks done, some individuals resort to unethical means to get the job done. Furthermore, over the years this will become a norm for these individuals, both the leaders and followers (Respondent 012)”

In summary, the findings provided several impediments to the effectiveness of ethical leadership within the public sector. While some of the respondents did emphasise, these challenges are an upstream from the main issue within the Nigerian public context (corruption), there are ways to which they have been able to tackle or mitigate these growing problems.

7.8. Conclusion

This findings chapter has provided a better understanding of the concept of ethical leadership in the public sector via the participants. This research adopted a semi-structured interview to explore the operationalisation of ethical leadership in the sector. These interviews were carried out with 25 respondents consisting of managers, deputy managers and supervisors. From the outcome of these interviews, results obtained satisfied the following research questions.

Research question One: How do we define the concept of ethical leadership?

Research question Two: What are the required skills necessary for an effective ethical leader?

Research question Four: What are the hinderances and limitations to the implementation of an ethical leadership framework.

The primary definition of ethical leadership from the public sector can be defined from two key themes namely the ability and the process of the operationalisation of the concept. This involves inculcating rules and regulation of the organisation and influencing ethics on the subordinates to improve performance, drive employee commitment and foster ethical culture.

The following challenges were identified from the research namely, the internal & external factors, disregard for rules and regulation, inadequate level of ethical leadership skills and cognitive dissonance & group prototypicality.

The leadership skills to emerge from the research outcomes were interpersonal skills, conceptual skills, core ethical skills and the technical skills. Most respondents during the interviews stressed the need for ethical skills as the most vital skill needed and these skills set them apart from the other forms of leaders within the organisation. While technical and interpersonal skills are vital to the positive influence on organisational performance and employee performance, there is a need for the inculcation of ethical norms and values, to foster an environment for employee participation and voice. It is important to reward those who ethically perform well and punish those who are unethical in their acts and in the way they influence performance.

Several studies have suggested the positive influence ethical leaders have on employees and the organisation such as organisational citizenship behaviour, core job characteristics and corporate social responsibility. Furthermore, some scholars have highlighted the negative effects of ethical leadership on performance such as job stressors, threat to leader's integrity and perceived threat to career and social goal. Further evaluations will be done in the

discussion chapter to better understand the impediments and to explore these findings with regards to the influence of these impediments to ethical leadership on overall performance.

CHAPTER EIGHT: DISCUSSION

8.0. Introduction

This chapter aims to provide a critical and detailed analysis of research findings presented within the finding chapter, with existing literature in the field of ethical leadership. This chapter will provide a detailed correlation of findings to literature and analyse these findings and the effect of these skills to the challenges facing the implementation of an effective ethical leadership framework within the Nigerian public sector. Also, a detailed analysis of the influence of ethical leadership on performance will be provided from the findings and compared with existing literature in the field. To proffer an empirical framework for ethical leadership skills development within the public sector, core examination of the existing skills framework (Harrison et al., 2018; Katz, 1955; Kearns et al., 2015; Lord & Hall, 2005; Moore & Rudd, 2004; Mumford et al., 2000; Mumford et al., 2007; Bowman et al., 2004) within other approaches to leadership will be examined

The concept of leadership has over the years received critical assessment and exploration with scholars providing new insights to the definition of an effective leader, antecedents of influencing effective leadership and its impact on employee (task) and organisational performance. The skills perspective within leadership literature as an antecedent and a determinant for effective leadership is not new. Jago (1982) elucidated the concept of leadership as the application of a leader's skill and knowledge influenced by the traits, value and belief to achieve a desired goal. Studies have examined the positive relationship between leadership skills and employee performance and organisation's positive outcome.

The necessity for ethics as a critical aspect within the concept of leadership have been stressed by researchers in the field. While studies have emphasised the need for leaders to be ethical in their daily tasks and activities, there exists a gap within the body of literature that examines the

development of the skills required by an effective ethical leader. The systematic literature review process identified a shortcoming within the body of literature highlighting the identity perspective of an ethical leader with scholars suggesting the attributes and the behaviours needed to be considered. Furthermore, while studies have been able to provide a better understanding on the development process of an ethical leader, there is a missing link in the skills development process. Scholars also have mis-interpreted the understanding of different concepts of skills and portray these skills as behaviours of an ethical leader (please refer to the systematic literature review, SLR).

8.1. An Empirical Based Model for Ethical leadership within the Public Sector

Ethical leadership as an approach to leadership is not relatively new, having been around for over three decades. Heres & Lasthuizen (2013) suggests that the notion of ethical competence considerably overlaps with ethical leadership. This is based on an individual's ability to proffer sound ethical decisions and to act in accordance to normatively appropriate manner or behaviours. In essence, ethical leaders can influence followers in their actions such as through their decision-making process and the way they carry themselves. Ethical leadership adopts a more relational and reputational approach when dealing with employees and stakeholders, as leaders without the ability to inculcate ethics are perceived to be likely less ethical within any organisation (Heres & Lasthuizen, 2013; Brown et al., 2005; Brown & Trevino, 2006; Huberts et al., 2007).

Mendoca (2001) examines EL from two distinct perspectives namely, the behavioural perspective and the influence perspective. The behavioural aspect which is essential to the accomplishment of a given task and the influence process which can be described as a set of tactics, skills and strategies that are critical in influencing followers' beliefs, values, and behaviours. In this regard, skill implies an ability which can be developed, not necessarily

inborn, and which is manifested in performance. So, the principal criterion of skilfulness should be effective action under varying conditions (Katz, 1955).

Skills are effective tools adopted or developed over a period to focus on a potential change, plan, build and guide both personal and organisational systems to accomplish specific objectives (Aligahtani, 2014). Skills differ from traits of an individual, as skills are what leaders can achieve while traits are the characterization of who leaders are (Katz, 1955). While relatively grounded in the field, the concept is still undergoing a nascent state in terms of ethical leadership development. While core literature has provided a distinct understanding from the six perspectives emphasised in the review chapter, there exists a critical gap within the body of literature in understanding the essential skills necessary for effective ethical leadership.

Furthermore, while there are skills highlighted within the body of literature needed to effect positive performance from employees, there exists a fragmentation within the field on the essential skills needed to inculcate ethical values and norms in employees, foster employee performance, positive ethical climate and culture within these organisations. Ethical leaders require particular skillsets, actual knowledge and virtue to inculcate ethical competence, and foster inspiration through employee motivation. (Peng & Lin, 2017; Gallagher & Tschudin, 2010). Gallagher & Tschudin (2010) suggested the development of core ethical leader knowledge, virtue, skills for ethical leadership within organisation. Ethical leaders must possess the ability to handle ethical and moral issues satisfactorily. They require a very high level of competence and skill to deal with ethical and real-world issues. Most leaders require the capability of understanding moral problems as they arise and also the ability to perceive these issues and provide solutions to these problems (Kavathatzoupolos, 2012).

There exists a number of skills framework within the body of literature effecting positive employee output and performance (Bowman, et al., 2004; Katz, 1955; Lord & Hall, 2005;

Mumford, et al., 2007; Harrison, et al., 2018; Moore & Rudd, 2004; Katz, 1974). Furthermore, there exists a vast fragmentation of the required skillset in effecting ethical leadership. Some scholars have posited one or more skills necessary to effect employee commitment and influence implementing systems to effect ethics. Also, scholars as stipulated in the outcome of the systematic literature review have interchangeably adopted skills as a behaviour of an ethical leader. Evidently only one scholarly work has provided an ethic-based skill model for ethic-based leadership in the public service (Haq, 2011) but this research work lacks empirical evidence to support these skills.

This study presents an empirical model of ethical leadership skills within the Nigerian public sector. This skill framework is developed from the findings of this study and is built on the earlier contributions of the skills model within literature whilst aiming to address their limitations (See Table 2 in section 3.9.) The ethical leadership skills framework proposed for the Nigerian public sector identifies four skill categories required for its enactment: interpersonal skills, ethical skills, conceptual skills and technical skills. These skills are not relatively exclusive or adopted from a distinctive standpoint. These skills are interchangeably adopted and simultaneously utilised in fostering ethical leadership, influencing organisational growth and motivating employees to drive performance. Findings from this study has highlighted a number of critical skills from these core group of skills that evoke positive employee commitment and determination within the organisation.

While communication and listening skills can be perceived as an interpersonal skill within the literature, these skills work in tandem with other skills such as ethical awareness and motivation skills to influence ethical culture within the organisation. It also promotes an ethical climate where employees can perform effectively. Also, skills such as problem-solving skills and analytical skills are identified as a critical in fostering ethical decision-making within the organisation. Further findings from this research study also highlight the importance of

interpersonal skills which stood out as the highest mechanism of influence on subordinates within the public sector and works in unison with ethical skills. These are important to inculcate ethical leadership and foster employees positively.

A growing number of challenges facing the proper implementation of effective ethical leadership framework were identified and categorised into four key themes namely, the internal and external factors; the lack of skills to deal with moral challenges and influence performance; disregard for rules and regulation; ethical dissonance and group prototypicality. These challenges within the public sector have over the years inhibited the effectiveness of ethical leadership and has created an unethical culture and environment where unethical practices exist and thrive within the organisation. As a result, this has led to a series of bad leadership issues and affected performance as a whole within the organisation.

The internal and external factors were identified as the major challenge affecting the success of ethical leadership within the public sector. This can be attributed to the involvement of people both within and outside the organisation influencing the way things are delegated. Ethical leaders within this sector are faced with this interference from those above their chain of command, those within the community and those with political influence or in governance. They affect their leadership capability and also negatively influence employees within the organisation. This also makes leaders to embark on amoral and unethical behaviours which in the long run impact performance. Furthermore, these internal and external factors act as a prerequisite to the other major challenges facing the adoption of an effective ethical leadership framework.

While these challenges exist within the public sector, findings from the study highlights a missing link in addressing these challenges. A large majority of these challenges can be attributed to the limitation of skills needed by a leader to cultivate an ethical environment and

drive performance within the organisation. While some of these factors over time are persistent (the external factors), there is room for improvement through proper skills development of leaders within the organisation. Furthermore, while it is essential that a leader possesses the right ethical behaviour to foster ethical leadership, it is pivotal that a leader possesses the ability to impact these skills on the subordinates. A large percentage of leaders identified the need for proper skills development in handling moral problems within the organisation. In this regard, there is a need for skills development in solving ethical problems.

This ethical leadership skills framework also highlights the outcomes of ethical leadership namely, improving ethical culture and climate, employee performance and organisational performance. While ethical leaders addressed the importance of inculcating ethics, values and norms in employees and promoting these values and those of the organisation, performance of the organisation was identified as the most important factor to be considered. In actualising this performance, the need, motivation of employees and employee commitment are essential. The figure 17 below gives a detailed representation of the skills model for the Nigerian public sector.

Figure 17: Ethical Leadership Skills Framework in the Nigerian Public Sector

8.2.Challenges

Chapter four provided a detailed discussion on the Nigeria public sector, which included the challenges they encounter as reported within the literature. Furthermore, the systematic literature review section also addressed the impediments facing the effective implementation of an ethical leadership framework within literature. The challenges identified by scholars are: failure to communicate ethical expectations (Trevino et al., 2003; Greenbaum et al., 2015); perceived threat to career and social goals; threat to leader's integrity (Greenbaum et al., 2015); disregard and lack of moral influence and skills by moral leaders; absence of ethical culture and lack of recurrent ethic-based training of employees; induced stress by supervisors and job-related stress (Quade et al., 2017); doubt in ethical leader's behaviour and act; pressure to deliver performance output (Babalola et al., 2016); differentiation in ethical beliefs and moral values (Miao et al., 2013); organisational constraint and philosophy (Gok et al., 2017); organisational culture constraint (Backhordari-Sharifabad et al., 2017; Temple, 2012; Jones &

Lasthuzien, 2018); societal constraint; ethical distress for organisational policies; job autonomy (Stouten et al., 2013; Miao et al., 2013, Greenbaum et al., 2015). and organisational deviance (Kalshoven et al., 2016).

Several challenges were identified from the findings of the study. This can be grouped into four major themes namely; the internal and external factors, the disregard for rules and regulation, inadequate level of ethical leadership skills and cognitive dissonance and group prototypicality.

8.2.1. Internal and External Factors

8.2.1.1. Internal Factors

Internal challenges were suggested by ethical leaders within the public sector as a hinderance to their leadership capabilities. Leaders within the public sector are plagued with everyday internal issues ranging from an individual to the management within the organisation. These two perspectives are interrelated and go hand in hand. While this can be attributed as an internal challenge within the sector, this is mediated by processes of employee recruitment being influenced by external factors within the organisation. The influence of these external factors in key processes such as employee recruitment affects the ethical culture of the organisation.

A high number of respondents during the interview provided instances of lack of meritocracy within the sector. The developmental background to create an effective ethical culture for employees to thrive is negatively affected by the lack of merited staff and leaders who possess the right cultural doctrine. This was identified by Fulmer (2004) and states it as one of the main issues facing the establishment of ethical leadership. While Fulmer (2004) elucidates the growing concerns facing ethical leaders from an educational perspective, ethical leaders are also burdened with the challenges of developing an ethical climate due to a plethora of influences from individuals. The Nigerian public sector is reeled in politicization, with little or no regards for merit-based quota systems in recruiting and promotion of employees and leaders

(Anyim & Ufodiama, 2013; Opara, 2014) and the non-utilization of job specialisation and job description (Briggs, 2007; Anyim & Ufodiama, 2013; Akinyele, 2010; Imhonopi & Ugochukwu, 2013).

This study also highlighted that the challenges facing the implementation of ethical leadership can also be attributed to top management influence within the organisation. Respondents elucidated the concerns and issues facing leaders through interference from top management. Ethical leaders within the public sector are hindered by influence from top management in the execution of their capacity. There are instances where these leaders face issues in punishing employees who go against the rules or carry out unethical practices in the organisation. Interference from top level management in dealing with cases from unethical employees may lead to threat of the leader's integrity in proffering fair judgement to employees. Greenbaum et al. (2015) suggest a major concern facing ethical leaders within organisations can be attributed to threat to their integrity. Leaders feel threatened by management interference to proffer the right punishment to unethical subordinates. They feel threatened to punish and in turn this leads to ineffectiveness on the part of the leader.

8.1.1.2. External Factors

External factors were identified during this research from the Nigerian public sector. Themes emerging from the study identified three major factors affecting the effectiveness of ethical leadership namely government & political intervention, community intervention and workers (labour force) group intervention.

Public sector leaders are faced with issues and challenges within the sector from external factors such as government. While few studies on ethical leadership have iterated some understanding of some negative effects of government intervention on public institutions

(Khuntia et al., 2004), organisational leaders within the Nigerian public sector are faced with developing ethical morals within the organisation.

Fatile (2013) posits that a broad range of public sector organisations adopt a single code of ethics applied within all areas. The ineptitude of these codes of conduct adopted within most public sector organisations is as a result of widespread corruption. The influence from government tends to be rather self-seeking and nepotistic in nature (Fatile, 2013). This is identified in literature by Babalola et al. (2016) and Greenbaum et al. (2015) who elucidate the threat to an ethical leader's career goal by external factors or environment

External influences from government stems from a lack of accountability and ethics-based structure. This can be attributed to difference in cultural, religious and moral beliefs within Nigeria. All respondents in this study emphasised that challenges facing leaders stem from a diverse difference in culture, and tribes. This in turn has created a room for nepotism and tribalism to thrive within the organisation. While the public sector can be considered a melting pot for various cultures and religion, differences in moral beliefs and culture creates avenue for cultural societal constraints for ethical leaders (Temple, 2012; Backhordari-Sharifabad et al., 2017; Fulmer, 2004; Brown and Mitchell, 2010; Obicci, 2014). Furthermore, interference from government officials has led to a deficit in the required skill and competence of ethical leaders and employees. This has led to a drop in employee effectiveness and performance output. Ethical leaders are faced with a shortage of skilful subordinates and are left to deal with the effects of a corrupt system.

Furthermore, respondents emphasised that the influence from government have negatively affected growth on the part of the employees. Employees and ethical leaders alike are left with the option of following stipulated code of conducts, which in the long run affects employee commitment and performance. This is further strained by a very weak and large hierarchical

structure of authority to take actions on unethical conducts in the organisation. Some respondents highlight the delay in the administration of punishment due to the large hierarchical structure, leaving room for unwanted practices and a widespread belief within the organisation that unethical behaviours can go unpunished. This supports Imhonopi & Ugochukwu (2013) assertion on the challenges facing the Nigerian public sector leadership structure which faces severe problems as a result of the rot and corruption. Efficiency and effectiveness in providing decisions and punishment to defaulters are not carried out in a timely manner or are disregarded.

Few respondents (5) attributed the direct and indirect involvement of the community through the process of community development and fostering a positive image of the organisation in the Niger Delta as one of the issues facing the organisation. As a public facing organisation, public sector institutions are tasked with fostering corporate social responsibility (CSR). To foster cohesiveness and community development, public sector organisations such as NNPC are tasked with adopting measures for the absorption of individuals to roles (contract or permanent) within the organisation. While community development initiatives are core ethical elements provided by the public sector to boost their presence and moral, the initiative has produced some negative effect in the acquisition of qualified personnel. This supports Ojodu (2017) that asserts that most CSR initiatives by public sector organisations for development in the Niger-Delta region have been plagued by several problems such as legitimacy and transparency. High-level corruption is predominant, with very little to justify the huge resource allocations received in terms of actual delivery and employment of skilled employees (Ojodu, 2017).

In summary, public sector organisations (NNPC) are faced with ethic-based challenges from internal and external forces. The bane of corruption is prominent at different levels of the organisation. Corruption and lack of accountability in NNPC stems from influences within the

government and other political actors. This has over the years affected the ability and capacity for leaders to influence employees effectively according to moral values and principles (Ofuani et al., 2018; Anyim & Ufodiama, 2013). This in turn has impacted negatively on ethical culture within the organisation, led to a disregard of laid down rules and regulation, and created a high employee turnover within the organisation.

Ethical leaders are left with a shortage of skilled workers and leaders alike with the right knowledge, skill and attitude to carry out their tasks. Furthermore, due to an ineffective hierarchical structure of leadership affected by incessant influences from government and community elements in the organisation. Also, leaders are left with minimal ability to impact efficiently as regards ethical behaviours in the organisation, inculcate and influence an ethical culture of reporting unethical behaviours from amoral employees or managers. This is due to threats from authorities above to take decisive steps to foster effective reward management systems to motivate ethical acts, threats to social and career goals of these leaders and their leadership integrity from these internal and external forces (Akinyele, 2010; Chiamogu & Chiamogu, 2019; Fatile, 2013; Greenbaum, 2015).

A large portion of these issues can be attributed to unqualified leaders filling roles in each subsidiary based on influence they got from these factors. These leaders who fill these positions in the long run lack the skills necessary to foster ethical behaviours, influence effective change and motivate employees to be ethical in every act and tasks they carry out. This creates a belief and a norm within the organisation that being amoral or unethical can be profitable. In essence, while ethical leaders within these organisations exist and possess the necessary ability to foster ethical behaviours in subordinates, there exists a number of followers who have varying beliefs and moral values not in accordance with the ethical norms of the organisation (Ijewereme, 2020; Opara, 2014). This individual possesses ethical norms and beliefs based on different

factors that are detrimental to the organisation. These issues impact employee and organisation performance.

8.2.2. Disregard for Rules and Regulation

Another theme to emerge from the findings is the disregard for rules and regulations by employees and leaders alike in the sector. Respondents stressed the challenges facing the organisation is due to the lack of adherence to ethical guidelines in carrying out tasks and assignments by workers within the organisation. The disregard for rules, code of conduct and regulations stem from the deep-rooted corruption and external factors within the public sector. These nonchalant attitudes to work by employees can be attributed to unethical practices from amoral managers and supervisors within the organisation. Furthermore, the issues arise from other varying factors within the organisation such as the lack of trust, confidence and reputation (Gundu, 2011; Ogbeidi, 2012).

Several scholarly works have identified the positive effects of ethical leadership in reducing organisational deviant behaviours such as disregard for rules and regulation (Mayer et al., 2009; Babalola, et al., 2016). Findings from this study elucidate a mixed effect with mitigating the disregard for rules and regulations. Ethical leaders within public sector organisations are left to deal with the decay in the social value system created as a result of a trickledown effect of nationalised and institutionalised corruption which has fostered unethical and corrupt practices (Ogbeidi, 2012; Opara, 2014; Nwokorie, 2016).

In summary, ethical leaders are faced with a culture within the Nigerian public sector that thrives from corruption at an external and an institutionalised level. Due to this rampant corruption, there exist a trickledown effect towards the way things are done within the organisation and the way employees perceive laid down rules and regulation. While there exist structures to counteract the effects and mitigate the issues of corruption within the public sector,

the mechanism in charge to enforce these codes of conduct within the organisation do not enforce these standards.

8.2.3. Inadequate Skill Level of Ethical leadership

The study showed that there is a deficiency in the skills needed in tackling issues within the Nigerian public sector. These leaders attributed the lack of skills within the public sector, a main problem in dealing with these moral dilemmas, and inculcating an ethical culture in the organisation. Respondents suggests that there are avenues through which one can mitigate the risks of these challenges and inspire ethics and confidence from employees and foster performance.

Skills within literature have been suggested to improve leadership effectiveness and also employee performance in organisations (Mumford et al., 2000; Katz, 2009; Harrison et al., 2018). This study elucidates that most leaders and employees do not possess the skills to accomplish this task. There are instances within the institution whereby leaders do not possess the proper channel of communication, do not have the ability to foster employee cohesion or participation (employee voice) in critical processes such as decision-making, fostering innovation and envisioning the way forward for the organisation. There are instances where leaders adopt the same set of skills to different ethical problems or scenarios in the organisation. Some of these leaders employed into the institution are limited in their ability to handle situations based on their employment and promotion into their positions as a result of these internal and external factors. This is supported by prior studies. Ejimabo (2013) states the prevalence of leaders in the public sector in Nigeria lack the effective leadership skills needed in executing the roles to which they are assigned or promoted.

Some respondents suggest there are situations where leaders do not possess the required skills in dealing with some dilemmas influenced by external factors. Scholars in literature have

highlighted the curvilinear effects of ethical leadership on employee effectiveness and performance (Miao et al., 2013; Stouten et al., 2013). There are cases where leaders are faced with balancing the performance output and effecting ethical conducts and behaviours. But with the existence of limited resources to deal with some requirement, an ethical leader must be able to sense these situations and apply the right ability in terms of analysing the situation (Greenbaum, 2015; Fatile, 2013; Nwokorie, 2018; Opara, 2014).

8.2.4. Cognitive Dissonance and Group Prototypicality

This research identified varying forms of cognitive (ethical) dissonance in the execution of their tasks and objectives in their organisation. Ethical leaders within the public sector have experienced different forms of unethical behaviours from employees or they have been in a position where they are in a dilemma to partake in unethical acts to foster productivity, effectiveness and performance. Festinger (1957) cognitive dissonance theory ascertain and suggests that two thoughts can either be associated or unrelated to each other. According to Festinger, cognitions are beliefs, opinions, knowledge and perceptions that individuals have about their behaviours, attitudes and environment. Every ethical leader in the study attributed to variations of cognitive dissonance in the process of carrying out task or in dealing with issues arising that goes against their beliefs and values

While Price (2017) have emphasised a volition by leaders to adopt unethical practices within organisations, findings from this research disputes this notion. Respondents within this research highlight a growing concern in working within unethical environments such as the public sector. Ethical leaders in the Nigerian public sector are faced with the challenge of maintaining a moral self-image as a role model while influencing their employees to be moral and effective in the execution of their daily objectives. Within public sector organisations, leaders and employees are constantly exposed to, or made to tolerate moral values and to

execute tasks and objectives which conflict with their beliefs and their core values. Respondents stipulate that they are faced with a situation of balancing between going against the norm of their belief and that of the organisation. This challenge was identified by Babalola et al. (2016) and Greenbaum et al. (2015). Leaders who are perceived as ethical within organisations are faced with the challenge of proffering a solution to this problem. Evidently, leaders are at a dissonance to set examples to their followers and influence subordinate to make ethical decisions.

In essence, majority of respondents (18) highlighted a growing concern in influencing ethical norms in the organisation and the impact of these challenges to their moral values. Leaders are faced with issues of balancing performance, acting as ethical role models to subordinates and concerned with their career growth within the organisation. In the long run, most leaders become amoral or unethical in their behaviours, actions and this affects the employees within the organisation

8.3. Skills

The necessity of skills as a critical element for effective leadership is not new within the literature (Katz, 1955; Katz, 1974; Mumford, 1986; Mumford et al., 2000; Mumford et al., 2007). Some studies posit that the effectiveness of leadership behaviours is fundamentally dependent on the ability of a leader to solve complex problems (Mumford et al., 2000).

For this study, the adaptation of skills is defined as a leader's function-related knowledge and the skills that contribute to the accomplishment of a goal through a display of ethics (Pettigrew, 1988; Crosby, 1997; Winstons & Patterson, 2006). Skills are effective tools developed over a period to build and guide both personal and organisational systems to accomplish specific objectives (Aligahtani, 2014).

As explained in the beginning of this chapter, the skills approach to leadership development have provided different leadership skills models tailored to improving organisational performance and solving complex problems. There exists no skills model for inculcating ethics in leadership, hence three key models from general leadership informed this study namely, Katz (1955; 1974); Mumford et al. (2000) and Kavathatzopoulos & Rigas (1998).

8.4. Ethical skills

While the concept of ethical skills has been adopted by scholars within literature and is not relatively new, a detailed understanding to what these skills entail and what can be considered as ethical leadership skills are relatively scarce. While majority of studies have proffered a better understanding of ethical competence as a critical element within organisation, these works only provide a detailed insight into what constitute an ethically competent individual within an organisation and not an ethically competent leader (Kavathatzopoulos & Rigas, 1998; Menzel & Cooper, 2013; Bowman et al., 2004; Heres & Lasthuizen, 2013). Heres & Lasthuizen (2013) posit ethical competence considerably overlaps with ethical leadership as this is based on an individual's ability to proffer sound ethical decisions and to act in accordance to normatively appropriate behaviours. While this defines ethical competence, it does not equate to effective leadership or the ability of a leader to influence ethical leadership on subordinates (Heres & Lasthuizen, 2013).

In essence, ethical skill as a psychological construct, and in accordance to the philosophical position, can be described as the basis of ethical competence of leaders at personal and organisational levels (Kavathatzopoulos, 2012).

8.4.1. Ethical Awareness

Few participants highlighted the necessity of having ethical awareness within the organisation. The concept of ethical awareness in literature is not relatively new. Some school of thought have interchangeably used the term moral awareness and ethical awareness. Furthermore, studies have iterated the concept of ethical awareness as ethical perception. While few works have elucidated some aspect of awareness from a self-perspective, leaders need to be ethically aware of situations surrounding them and be able to perceive these ethical problems before they arise. Ethical awareness was first identified in literature as a key component of ethical leadership by Trevino et al. (2003). Trevino et al. (2003) elucidate the importance of ethical awareness for an ethical leader within any given organisation.

An ethical leader must be able to view, analyse and consider situations from an ethical standpoint irrespective of the given situation (Reynolds, 2006), possess the ability to anticipate an ethical problem in real life and perceive them at the right time (Kavathatzopoulos & Rigas, 1998). In essence, this is a distinctive skill that sets them apart from other forms of leaders within the organisation.

8.4.2. Ethical Decision Making

While decision-making skills within literature can be classified as a conceptual skill (Harrison, 2018), decision making have been considered as an important aspect in the conceptualisation and the operationalisation of ethical leadership. A good number of respondents in the Nigerian public sector confirmed adopting ethical decision-making skills in solving ethical issues in their various subsidiaries.

As stipulated by most respondents (17), a leader is faced with ethical issues in the organisation, and as such one must be skilled to make such ethical decisions. Furthermore, one must be able to perceive, be attentive and always consider the ethical point of view as this will impact the

organisation. The concept of ethical decision making as a critical aspect of ethical leadership was identified and inculcated into the conceptualisation and the operationalisation by Brown et al. (2005) and Huppenbauer & Tanner (2014). Whilst decision making is conceptual in nature, ethical decision-making skills is distinct in nature and involves the ability to combine ethical awareness to perceive these issues and adopt a core number of skills to effect decisions within the organisation. Whilst Brown et al. (2005) and Huppenbauer & Tanner (2014) infer to the ability to make ethical decisions when faced, this fosters teambuilding and role modelling in carrying along employees in the decision-making process (Christensen & Kohls, 2003; Firsch & Huppenbauer, 2014).

8.4.3. Integrity

Respondents stipulated the positive influence of a leader's integrity on subordinates. Employees are more inclined to trust, discuss, report and emulate ethical leaders with integrity because they are honest, fair and have strong values (Kavathatzopoulos & Rigas, 1998; Kavathatzopoulos, 2014; Engelrecht, et al., 2015).

Scholars have considered integrity as an attribute to effective leadership. Some school of thought have argued integrity can be considered as a behaviour (Keating, et al., 2007; Den Hartog & De Hoogh, 2009; Lawton & Paez, 2015). Furthermore, some studies have attributed the benefit of integrity as a mediator in the creation of a positive ethical climate within the organisation (Enwereuzor, et al., 2020).

8.5. Interpersonal Skills

Interpersonal skills can be defined as an individual's ability to understand the attitudes, feelings and intentions of others (Haq, 2011). This skill can be interchangeably identified as human skills (Katz, 1974; Katz, 2009) and involves a leader's capacity to work effectively as a group member and to foster cooperative efforts amongst followers. This involves working with

people and the establishment of mutually satisfying relationships (Haq, 2011; Mahoney, et al., 1963; Mahoney, et al., 1965; Mintzberg, 1973). Some school of thought posit interpersonal skills can be defined as one's ability to influence followers' actions through persuasion to achieve a given objective or organisational outcome (Yukl, 1989; Haq, 2011; Mintzberg, 1973). These can be considered as people's skills and this is demonstrated in how a leader is perceived and behaves towards those around him/her including followers, stakeholders, directors, peers and superiors (Moore & Rudd, 2004).

These set of skills are highly important and cannot be a "some-time skill", but must be utilised, demonstrated and adopted in every action of a leader (Moore & Rudd, 2004; Katz, 2009). Leaders adopt these skills when they motivate individuals and groups (Moore & Rudd, 2004). In essence, these set of skills are essential throughout all levels of management (Katz, 1955; Hicks & Gullet, 1975; Moore & Rudd, 2004).

The following interpersonal skills that emerged from the research outcome are discussed below. These include communication and listening skills; empathy; team-building skills; motivation skills; employee development skills and political skills.

8.5.1. Communication and Listening Skills

Communication and listening skills have been asserted by literature as a leadership skill for effectiveness (Harrison et al., 2018; Katz, 2009; Mumford et al., 2000). This view is pertinent among 22 respondents of the research. Respondents stressed the need and the impact of communication in instilling ethical norms and providing avenues for subordinates to understand the benefits and consequences of their actions in the organisation.

A vast majority also stressed that one must not just be able to verbally or non-verbally communicate the positive aspect of ethics, they need to pay attention, encourage and listen carefully to their ideas. Communication was identified as a key mechanism for inculcating

ethics in subordinates by most studies on ethical leadership. While most studies have mentioned the need for this mechanism, they did not attribute it as a skill within the ethical leadership context. Katz (2009) have addressed the importance of communication for effectiveness as a leader. However, findings from this study also attribute interpersonal skills for effecting ethical values and instructions on subordinates. Ethical leaders must be skilled in delivering and effecting rule-based leadership on the organisational standards.

First identified by Trevino et al. (2000) and Trevino et al. (2003) highlighting communication of ethics as an important category in creating a positive perception of ethical leadership to followers. This is supported by Peng & Lin (2017) and Brown et al. (2005) who assert that through the communication of a leader's ethical vision, ethical leaders can positively affect the way employees perceive themselves.

In taking into consideration their moral values and attributes of altruism, ethical leaders should be able to communicate clearly to employees how their actions at work contribute to the main goals of the organisation and foster performance (Zhu, 2014). They utilise inclusive communication patterns such as listening to employee's concern and what they have to contribute and also share power in the process of decision-making (Piccolo et al., 2010; Brown et al., 2005; Zhu, 2014). Lack of communication was shown in this study to negatively affect the objectives and the performance of the organisation.

While most scholars within literature address the need for effective communication, this has not been highlighted as a skill in the development of an ethical leader. Peng & Julian (2017) elucidate the importance of communication and emphasise that this goes in tandem with the transactional aspect of dispensing rewards and the enhancement of follower's performance. Effective communication skills promote group value congruence, thereby further improving group in-role and contextual performance (Alshammari et al., 2015; Peng & Lin, 2017).

8.5.2. Empathy

Kellett et al. (2006) elucidate empathy as the ability to understand other's emotions. Empathy is the ability to experience vicariously the feelings of other persons (De Schrijver & Maesschaik, 2013). The respondents articulated the need for this skill in dealing with subordinate's concerns and also building a bond or working relationship within the organisation. While some scholarly works have emphasised empathy as a mediator or a behaviour of ethical leadership (Mahsud et al., 2010), empathy from the findings can be described as a skill essential in fostering employee commitment and performance (Sadri et al., 2011; Harrison et al., 2018). Some school of thought have linked empathy to effective leadership in organisational settings (Kellett et al., 2002).

Works in leadership literature have asserted that leaders who display empathy are able to understand others and as such these understanding helps strengthen relationship with subordinates. Furthermore, subordinates look up to their leaders for ethical cues and empathy as an example to embody which in turn stimulates positively their behaviours to help other followers within the organisation (Kalshoven et al., 2013).

8.5.3. Team Building Skills

Team-building skills is essential for effective leadership. It involves a leader's ability to build teams and foster teamwork within any given organisation (Harrison, 2018). This involves a leader's ability to foster cohesiveness and participation in organisational activities to accomplish goals through participation in decision-making processes. Respondents in the study confirmed that they have fostered employee participation during the course of their leadership journey. As an effective leader within the public sector, one must be able to involve subordinates in team processes such as decision-making and in the delegation of tasks within the organisation. Some scholarly works have attributed the positive effect of team building

skills on employees' performance and leader effectiveness in mainstream leadership literature (Harrison, 2018).

Respondents emphasized the need for collaboration with the clear goal of accomplishing a task. Some scholars have stipulated the positive influence of ethical leadership in fostering and creating a cohesive ethical environment to foster employee voice, employee commitment and power sharing (De Hoogh & Den Hartog, 2008).

Ethical leaders influence ethical behaviours in subordinates through their ability to give followers the opportunity to express themselves (Piccolo et al., 2010; Brown et al., 2005). While these studies highlight a positive effect on fostering ethical climates, findings from this study elucidate this is possible through team-building skills. This supports literature on the positive impact of team-building skills in influencing employees. While Harrison (2018) emphasized its importance from an entrepreneurial leader's perspective, this skillset is also vital in fostering employees to act ethically and inculcate ethical norms and values of the organisation. Through the inculcation of team building skills and employee participation within organisation, ethical leaders foster employee identification with the organisation which leads to organisation citizenship behaviour (OCB). Ethical leaders foster employee trust and motivate their followers to identify as team players within the organisation (Peng & Julian, 2017; De Hoogh & Den Hartog, 2008).

8.5.4. Motivation Skills

Motivation skills can be defined as the ability to inspire confidence and motivate followers and it is considered a vital aspect of effective leadership (Harrison et al., 2018). Baldwin & Grayson (2004) highlight the benefits of motivation skills and the effects on employees and overall organisational performance. Leaders with the ability to influence followers within

organisations produces three distinct outcomes from their followers namely: compliance, commitment and resistance within an organisation.

This study highlighted the importance of fostering motivation of subordinates within the Nigerian public sector. As the Nigerian public sector is riddled with unethical culture and corruption, these leaders ascribe the need to motivate employees ethically through their behaviours and actions. Ethical leaders within the public sector adopt various strategies to influence employee commitment, mitigate employee resistance and deviance within the organisation. While motivation within the literature is related to transformational leadership theory (Bass & Avolio, 1993; Bass & Bass, 2008) and as a skill in entrepreneurial leadership (Harrison et al., 2018), ethical leaders within this study have suggested its importance for developing ethical values in followers and influencing performance in the organisation.

Ethical leaders should possess the ability to influence and encourage their subordinates to behave ethically, act in accordance with the values and norms of the organisation (Huppenbauer & Tanner, 2014). As stipulated by Peng & Lin (2017), effective ethical leaders motivate employee devotion to a shared goal by building ethical norms, communicating with members, implementing, dispensing rewards and punishment fairly within the organisation. Ethical leader's ability to motivate employees enhance trust among employees and fosters team building within the organisation. (Peng & Lin, 2017).

8.5.5. Employee Development Skills

The findings showed that ethical leaders require the skillset of fostering employee development within the organisation. Several scholarly works within literature have identified the positive effect of ethical leadership behaviours on fostering employee development within organisations (Yidong & Xinxin, 2016; Piccolo et al., 2010; Zhu et al., 2004; Kalshoven et al., 2013). The display of affection by leaders drive employees to have a sense of belonging, and

form positive self-views based on social interaction and persuasion (Yidong & Xinxin, 2016; Piccolo et al., 2010; Zhu et al., 2004). Leaders are to foster employee growth and development through interpersonal relationships, communicating and influencing ethical norms and culture. Yidong & Xinxin (2016) posit that ethical leaders help drive employee self-development through the process of delivering empowerment and placing them in the right position to develop, acquire and master their skills and knowledge. While these studies have asserted the positive relationship between ethical leaders and various facets of employee mastery and job autonomy, findings from this study suggests leaders employ this skill in assigning and delegating tasks and ensuring employees improve their ability and develop ethical behaviours. Ethical leaders create opportunities and avenues for driving employee development. They do this through their ability to evoke an ethical climate for followers to learn (Yidong & Xinxin, 2016; Zhu et al., 2004). While studies refer to employee development as a behaviour, this study stipulates it as a skill. As ethical leaders, they foster employee development through the provision of job autonomy and creating a sense of responsibility in the organisation.

8.5.6. Political Skills

Findings show that political skills are instrumental in driving employees from different backgrounds and moral beliefs to work together to achieve organisational outcomes. Political skills were identified in the literature by Harvey et al. (2013) and Kacmar et al. (2013) as an interpersonal skill of an ethical leader. Some studies have identified the benefits and the positive effect of political skills on employees, stimulating and fostering organisational citizenship behaviour and its influence on success within organisation (Gill et al., 2014; Pfeffer, 1981).

Organisations are inherently political in nature (Mintzberg, 1985), this can be seen in the Nigerian Public sector (NNPC). Leaders in these institutions require the ability to politically

navigate to be successful (Pfeffer, 1981). Leaders with political skills are perceived as ethical by followers and have positive influence on their psychological reactions by giving employees the impression of conformity to these ethical norms (Harvey et al., 2013; Kacmar et al., 2013).

8.6. Technical Skills

Respondents all attributed that they possessed varying forms of specialised knowledge as a requirement to taking up employment positions within the organisation. A good number of respondents (18) were educated to the bachelor's degree level. A few numbers of leaders (2) acknowledged they were educated to a master's degree level. Furthermore, training programmes are provided to help in the development of their competency and provide them some of the adequate knowledge necessary such as in the aspect of business ethics to navigate the institution.

The emphasis of technical skills as a requirement for leadership cannot be far-fetched. Technical skills can be classified as the expertise and proficiency in a specific area of work or activity (Katz, 1974). This involves having subject matter knowledge, the required skillset or procedures about the specific subject or field (Katz, 2009; Haq, 2011). Some school of thought have attributed technical skills to task effectiveness (Katz, 1974) and organisational performance (Haq, 2011; Mumford et al., 2000), or have considered technical skills as task-oriented skills (Lord & Hall, 2005) within an organisation. These skills can be described as the prerequisite to the provision of problem solving in situations. Gallagher & Tschudin (2010) elucidate the importance of technical skills, most especially education and training in the development of ethical leaders. Education and training in ethics within organisation are essential to ethical leaders. It is a critical aspect and aids these leaders with the skills and experience (Gallagher & Tschudin, 2010).

8.7. Conceptual Skills

Harrison (2018) defines conceptual skills as the ability of a leader to develop concepts and ideas. This skillset involves the capacity to foster good judgement, envision, analyse situations and proffer solution to problems within any given situation (Haq, 2011; Harrison, 2018). Several studies have emphasised the need for conceptual skills in fostering effective management within organisation. Some school of thought have classified conceptual skills as cognitive skills within literature and have iterated the capability of leaders with this skillset to analyse and solve complex problems (Mumford et al., 2000; Harrison, 2018; Katz, 1955; Katz, 1974; Katz, 2009).

The following conceptual skills that emerged from the research are discussed below. These include problem solving skills; analytical skills; idea-generation skills and envisioning skills.

8.7.1. Problem-Solving Skills

Problem solving skills have been identified as a core skill for leadership effectiveness and fostering performance within mainstream leadership literature (Mumford et al., 2000; Harrison et al., 2018). The findings from this research have elucidated its importance in ethical leadership effectiveness. All respondents (25) asserted that they adopted problem-solving skills within the public sector. Effective leaders possess the capability to proffer solution to complex problems through the adoption of logical and analytical approaches despite a limitation in resources (Harrison, 2018).

Mumford et al. (2000) elucidates problem solving skills as one of the three skills necessary to foster performance, a leader must be able to define significant problems, gather information required, formulate ideas and construct alternative plans for resolving these problems. Huppenbauer & Tanner (2014) identified the need for complex solving components in the facilitation of ethical leadership. A leader must be able to adopt their cognitive ability and work

simultaneously with other skills such as ethical awareness and ethical decision-making. This study supports prior literature in the domain.

8.7.2. Analytical Skills

This study showed analytical skills as a prerequisite to proffering ethical solutions to situations within organisation. As such, leaders need to be analytical in making ethical decisions (Harrison, 2018; Kavathatzopoulos & Rigas, 1998). Leaders within the public sector demonstrated analytical prowess in assessing employees and situations and is key in solving ethical situations. This relates to Cam Caldwell et al. (2002) stipulation that ethical leaders must possess the capability to think logically, understanding the strengths and weaknesses of a given problem. Kavathatzopoulos & Rigas (1998) further expatiate on the requirement of analytical skills in the development of an ethically skilled individual within an organisation. Leaders are required to be analytical in their thinking and solving problems to proffer ethically sound decisions and impact performance in the organisation.

8.7.3. Idea-Generation Skills

Respondents iterated the importance of this skill set in influencing organisational performance. Idea-generation skills have been attributed to effective leadership and improves performance within an organisation. This is evident in extant literature on the influence of leadership in organisations (Harrison, 2018). While this can be considered effective within literature, ethical leaders foster an environment for idea generation through the skill of fostering collective employee participation and employee voice to problems. In essence, ethical leaders provide environments whereby employees feel psychologically safe to speak about their new ideas and challenge the norm within the organisation (Yidong & Xinxin, 2013; Yidong & Xinxin, 2016). Findings from this study support leadership scholarship (Harrison, 2018) on idea generating skills in fostering performance.

8.7.4. Envisioning Skills

Respondents suggested that ethical leaders require vision and goals when dealing with employees and fostering performance. Envisioning involves the ability of a leader to create and visualise the future for an organisation to create added value (Harrison et al., 2018; Harrison, 2018). Envisioning or vision creation has been identified in the literature as a key element of ethical leadership (Yidong & Xinxin, 2013; Lawton & Paez, 2015; Alshammari et al., 2015). Ethical leaders are equipped with task and the skillset of developing and creating a clear vision of an ethically sound environment for employees to thrive and instil performance (Lawton & Paez, 2015).

8.8. Relationship between Skills, Challenges and Performance

The findings and the analysis have identified the challenges facing the Nigerian public sector and the skills adopted by these leaders to mitigate these challenges and improve performance within the organisation. Furthermore, the review and findings identified the growing ethical issue facing the Nigerian public sector can be traced to the ingrained corruption facing most public sector organisations in the country. Also, leaders have attributed the internal and external factors as the most pertinent concern negatively affecting the effectiveness of ethical leaders in the organisation. This involves interference from individuals, government, top management and employees alike.

While there exist frameworks to foster and promote ethical guidelines within the organisation, leaders are faced with challenges stemming from poor hierarchical structure in dealing with ethical situations. As respondents suggest, leaders are placed in positions based on the people they know rather than on meritocracy, skills and the knowledge these individuals possess.

As stipulated by most respondents, recruitment and retention is motivated by external influences such as the government, politicians and highly influential individuals within society.

Due to these external involvement in the recruitment process of the organisation, employees and leaders are employed based on nepotistic, ethnic and religious tendencies. Individuals are employed into both subordinate positions and core leadership positions without regards to core job specifications, ethical values and culture of the organisation. In this regard, some leaders are less equipped with the skills and knowledge to take up these leadership roles in the public sector organisation. This in turn leads to trickledown effect on employees and negatively affects the ethical culture of the organisation. Employees within the organisation will perceive unethical or amoral behaviours as the norm of the day.

Most skill taxonomies within the literature have emphasised the benefit of core skills requirement for effectiveness of a leader (Katz, 2009; Mumford et al., 2000). Leaders not equipped with the right skillset are at a disadvantage and are not able to lead effectively and negatively influence employees to disregard rules and regulations (organisational deviance) of the organisation.

The impact of internal and external influence on the organisation creates a deficiency in the required work force needed and the necessary leadership skills needed to create an ethical climate. Furthermore, while there exist ethical leaders within the public sector organisation, respondents further attributed challenges facing the sector as regards leaders not possessing the ability to perceive ethical situations or challenges in the organisation. This can be attributed to the lack of ethical awareness to identify these situations, the ability to make ethical decisions and the integrity to know and stand by these actions. While some leaders within the institution possess these abilities, there is a growing concern of the dissonance caused by balancing the required course of action and fostering organisational performance.

The empirical ethical skills model presented addresses the ethical situations and problems facing the public sector. Several studies within leadership have stipulated the core skills critical

for leaders to influence performance within organisation (Connelly et al., 2000; Mumford et al., 2000; Katz, 2009). The skills taxonomies have addressed the need and the impact of interpersonal skills, technical and conceptual skills as a mechanism for driving performance in different organisational levels of management (Mumford et al., 2000; Katz, 2009).

Extant literature in the studies of ethical leadership have emphasised the positive influence of ethical leadership on promotion of voice, firm performance, promotability, organisational citizenship behaviour which drives employee commitment and participation. Findings from this study highlight the key skills required for effective ethical leadership. From the study, interpersonal skills and the conceptual skills were the two major skills attributed by respondents as a key criterion for influencing employees to adopt ethical values, and norms. While these skills are core to the development and operationalisation of ethical leadership in the sector, ethical skills emerged from findings as the skill which differentiates ethical leaders from all other types of leaders.

In essence, ethical skills help followers identify and emulate ethical leaders within the organisation. Furthermore, interpersonal skills such as empathy, communication & listening skills and motivation was shown to influence employee commitment and in the long run leads to organisational citizenship behaviour. In this regard, employees are eager, committed and are willing to proffer their best when leaders create an ethical atmosphere and climate for employees to voice their concerns.

8.9. Conceptualisation and Definition of Ethical Leadership

Ethical leadership has been conceptualised by scholars as the demonstration of normative appropriate behaviours or conduct through their actions by ethical leaders, their interpersonal relationship with their followers, and the promotion of these normatively appropriate behaviours and conducts through two-way communication, reinforcement and decision-

making. The main objective of this research was to explore the necessity and the credibility of these widely accepted definition within literature and to proffer a better and more detailed definition from a skill standpoint.

While literature have emphasised the importance of normative behaviours and attributes an ethical leader must possess in influencing ethical values on followers, there is a necessity to further explore and provide a clearer understanding of how these behaviours can be influenced through the ethical leader's action (skills). Several studies have addressed the need for a detailed definition of ethical leadership (Voegtlin, 2016; Price, 2017; Eisenbeiss, 2012). While these authors have addressed the need for a clarification on the behavioural aspect of normative appropriate behaviours, this study takes a different approach and proffers a skills perspective to the definition of ethical leadership. This work further expatiates on the definition of ethical leadership by inculcating skills as a core requirement to the operationalisation and the development of ethical leadership.

Findings from the respondents attributed their understanding and definition of ethical leadership from two key emergent themes namely, ethical leadership as a process and as an ability. Respondents emphasised their understanding of ethical leadership as the process of being an ethical leader, possessing the right behaviours, having a clear understanding of the rules and regulation of the organisation. In essence, as identified by Brown et al. (2005); Trevino et al. (2000); Trevino et al. (2003) and Yukl (2013), leaders perceived to be ethical possess the behaviours and attributes to be morally right, are considered moral individuals while being role models to their employees. This aspect of ethical leadership has been the focal point of majority of ethical leadership literature as identified in the identity perspective (refer to identity perspective).

A high number of respondents emphasised ethical leadership as the ability of a leader to influence these behaviours on their followers. Mumford et al. (2000) and Hall & Lord (1995) stipulate that while these behaviours are critical to effective leadership, a leader must be equipped with the skills to demonstrate these behaviours and influence subordinates. Ethical leaders must possess the capability to decide when to adopt and influence these ethical behaviours on followers to attain organisational goals (Mumford et al., 2000; Bass, 1990; Fleishman, 1998; Fleishman, 1973; Yukl, 1994; Mumford, 1986; Howell & House, 1992; Winter, 1991; Heres & Lasthuizen, 2013; Kavathatzopoulos, 2014).

Drawing on Heres & Lasthuizen (2013) notion on the definition and the development of an ethical leader from a skills point of view, findings from the study identify the utilisation of skills as a key tool for fostering ethical leadership behaviours in followers.

In summary, this study proffers and allows for skills inclination on ethical leadership and satisfies research question one. The definition is provided below:

“Ethical leadership is the process of being an ethical leader and involves the demonstration of normatively appropriate behaviours through a leader’s ability to foster interpersonal relationship through core skills to influence positive employee commitment and organisation objectives. Ethical leaders utilise their fundamental skills: ethical skills, interpersonal skills, conceptual skills and technical skills to mitigate and resolve ethical situations and dilemma while positively influencing ethical climate, employee performance to effect organisational performance.”

8.10. Conclusion

This chapter has provided a conceptual ethical leadership skills framework and has addressed the ethic-based challenges facing leaders from the findings of this study, which is contextualised within existing literature. This has addressed research objectives three and four.

Research objective Three: To provide a skill-based ethical leadership framework within the Nigerian public sector.

Research objective Four: To investigate the influence of ethical leadership skills on performance in the Nigerian public sector.

Two core themes emerged from findings proffering a better understanding of ethical leadership from the Nigerian public sector and influence on performance: the ethic-based challenges facing its effectiveness and the skills critical to the success and the positive influence of performance. The challenges facing ethical leaders in the Nigerian public sector were found to include internal & external factors; disregard for rules and regulations (organisation deviance); inadequate level of ethical leadership skills; cognitive dissonance and group prototypicality. The Nigerian public sector is faced with challenges stemming from corruption which has over the years negatively impacted the structure, firm reputation and the performance of the organisation. Due to this effect, internal and external influences on core mechanisms for recruitment and retention of highly ethical and qualified staff has created a shortage both in terms of ethically-skilled leaders and employees and has negatively influenced the sector fostering a breakdown in laid down rules and regulations and affecting performance.

This study identified four broad skills needed by ethical leaders in the Nigerian public sector: ethical, interpersonal, conceptual and technical skills. These skills were identified as a key determinant in influencing performance within the organisation. Whilst all skills are important at every aspect of leadership within the public sector, interpersonal skills were identified as the

most important skill for influencing ethical values and norms within subordinates. Furthermore, ethical skills emerged as a determinant factor in separating all other forms of leadership to ethical leaders. Ethical leaders develop and adopt ethical skills as an added layer to help perceive ethical situations and aid in their problem solving and decision-making process. Ethical leaders adopt interpersonal skills to build interpersonal relationship with subordinates, foster team building, employee building and commitment from followers which positively influence performance within the public sector. Whilst there exists a number of skills frameworks in literature, this skills framework identifies ethical skills as an important skill mediating all other forms of skills within existing skill taxonomies. Ethical skills possess the ability of integrity, ethical decision making and ethical awareness as the core foundation which influences the three major skills categories essential for influencing employees and fostering performance. Furthermore, leaders with these core ethical skills are highly valued, promote trust and work simultaneously with other skills such as interpersonal skills to influence subordinates to behave ethical and in the long term develop the ethical leadership skills.

Finally, findings from this study have provided a basis and inculcation of the skills perspective to the definition of ethical leadership in literature. While the Brown et al. (2005) definition addresses the demonstration of normative appropriate behaviours through a leader's action, interpersonal relationship, adopting a two-way communication and the aspect of decision making, this study provides a mechanism through skills to influence these appropriate behaviours on employees within the public sector.

The final chapter will give a detailed summary of the entire study and the key milestones presented in this thesis.

CHAPTER NINE: CONCLUSION

9.1. Introduction

This chapter provides a conclusion to this thesis and presents an overview of the study and the actualisation of its research aim, objectives and research questions. The findings from this study and its contribution to knowledge are highlighted. Implications for practice and limitations are also provided. Furthermore, this chapter concludes by suggesting further research opportunities.

9.2. Summary of Thesis

This study examined the concept of ethical leadership and contributed to the body of knowledge.

9.2.1. Research Aim

The purpose of this doctoral research was to examine the concept of ethical leadership from the context of the Nigerian public sector. There was a detailed investigation into the ethic-based challenges facing ethical leaders in the public sector and the skills they require for influencing performance.

The research aim was actualised by fulfilling four research objectives:

Objective One: To examine the current conceptualisation of ethical leadership

Ethical leadership from findings in literature is not relatively new. Several studies from this doctoral study, thorough and detailed critique of literature have provided various conceptualisation of ethical leadership. To proffer a better understanding and a critical examination, research question (1) and research question (2) were adopted to provide a guide to current examination. From findings, some studies have provided several variation to the definition of ethical leadership in literature (please refer to Section 5.4.1.).

From findings, majority of scholars have adopted Brown et al., (2005) definition of ethical leadership providing the understanding of ethical leadership from a behavioural point of view highlighting the concept as the demonstration of normatively appropriate behaviours and the influence of followers. Furthermore, several scholars have asserted the vagueness and impracticality to the conceptualisation of ethical leadership (Voegtlin, 2016; Toor & Ofori, 2009; Eisenbeiss, 2012; Price, 2017). Findings from literature in this study also identified the different perspectives to the conceptualisation of ethical leadership namely identity, followers, performance, sectors, behavioural and demographical perspective (please refer to Section 5.4.2). Whilst major studies have provided pivotal advancement in literature within these perspective, gaps highlighted in the SLR identified limited empirical works on the skills perspective to the conceptualisation of ethical leadership. The findings from this study provided a skills perspective on the definition and conceptualisation from the public sector. The primary definition of ethical leadership from the public sector can be defined from two key themes namely the ability and the process of the operationalisation of the concept. This involves inculcating rules and regulation of the organisation and influencing ethics on the subordinates to improve performance, drive employee commitment and foster ethical culture. From findings, the definition of ethical leadership can be defined as process of being an ethical leader and involves the demonstration of normatively appropriate behaviours through a leader's ability to foster interpersonal relationship through core skills to influence positive employee commitment and organisation objectives. Ethical leaders utilise their fundamental skills: ethical skills, interpersonal skills, conceptual skills and technical skills to mitigate and resolve ethical situations and dilemma while positively influencing ethical climate, employee performance to effect organisational performance.

Objective Two: To identify the ethic-based challenges facing leaders within the Nigerian public sector.

This study identified several ethic-based challenges facing the Nigeria sector. To examine and identify these challenges, a thorough review of literature identified four key factoring facing the public sector namely economic, socio-cultural social-political and the leadership factors (please refer to section 4.4.). Whilst these challenges affect the performance of leaders in the public sector, scholars within the body of literature have identified ethic-based issues facing leaders in the Nigeria public sector stem from the absence or lack of effective skills to foster ethical based leadership (Orazi et al., 2013; Van Wart, 2003), a direct result of leadership failure and the unwillingness or incapability of individuals in power to rise to the responsibility (Eliogu-Anenih, 2017; Iheduru, 2016) and lack of responsible and ethical leaders with integrity, vision, high moral values (Ogbewere, 2015; Opara, 2014). The outcome from the systematic literature review (section 5.6.) identified several hinderance to the implementation of ethical leadership. Empirical findings from this doctoral study identified four challenges from the Nigeria public sector namely (1) internal & external factors, (2) inadequate level of ethical leadership, (3) disregard for rules and regulation (4) Cognitive dissonance and group prototypicality (See section 8.2.).

Objective Three: To provide a skill-based ethical leadership framework within the Nigerian public sector.

This research objective was actualized through the satisfaction of research question four. A detailed review of leadership within the body of literature identified an ethical gap within the skills perspective of leadership development (section 3.9). Furthermore, findings from the systematic literature review identified the limitation of empirical works in the skills development of ethical leadership and highlighted the misconception and misuse of behaviours as skills in the body of ethical leadership literature (Section 5.5). Findings from this study identified four major skills essential for ethical leadership effectiveness in the public sector namely the interpersonal skills, ethical skills, technical skills and conceptual skills. While

interpersonal, conceptual and technical skills play key roles in leadership effectiveness, ethical skills identified in this study differentiates ethical leadership from other leadership approaches.

Objective four: To investigate the influence of ethical leadership skills on performance in the Nigerian public sector.

This research objective was actualized through the satisfaction of research question five. Findings from the systematic literature review identified the influence of ethical leadership on performance within literature in organisation (section 5.7). Whilst several scholars have identified the positive influence on performance, few scholars have identified the curvilinear and some negative effect to employee and organisational performance (see section 5.6). Empirical findings from this study identified the positive influence of skills in influencing ethical leadership, fostering employee commitment and organisational performance.

The research aim of this thesis was actualised through the satisfaction of the research objectives and questions. A traditional narrative literature review was conducted within the field of ethics, leadership and the Nigerian context. A detailed systematic literature review was done to proffer a comprehensive understanding of ethical leadership within the literature. Semi-structured interviews were used in the exploration of the experience of leaders in the public sector. The outcome from the findings of these interviews allowed for the development of an empirical skills framework within the Nigerian public sector.

9.2.2. Narrative Literature Review

During the course of this study, three reviews were conducted. These reviews explored ethics, leadership and the Nigerian context. These reviews provided a detailed background for examining ethical leadership within the Nigerian public sector perspective.

The review of ethics within this study provided an understanding of the definition of ethics. Ethics can be regarded as an individual or a group way of life guided by the principles of what

can be considered good or bad, morally right or wrong and what we ought to do (Kamlesh, 1999; Thiroux & Krasemann, 1980; Copp, 2006; Banerjee & Ercetin, 2012; Inal, 1996; Kamlesh, 1999). From the review, several theoretical variations were found to proffer a better understanding of ethics namely, deontological, teleological theory, virtue, contractarianism and pluralism. Some scholarly works have attributed a link between ethical theories and ethical leadership (Knights & Majella, 2006; Whetstone, 2001; Arjoon, 2000; Knights & Majella, 2005; Morrison, 2001; Molyneaux, 2003) namely, the deontological theory and the virtue ethics theory. This study adopted the standpoint of virtue ethics (Anna, 1995; Stichter, 2007; Dougherty, 2020).

A narrative review of literature on leadership was also presented in this study. From findings, leadership is a process (Harrison, 2018; Stogdill, 1974; Jago, 1982; Northhouse, 2007; Kotter, 1988; Bennis & Townsend, 1995) which involves influencing individuals or group of individuals (Bass & Bass, 2008; Jago, 1982; Northhouse, 2007), through interaction (Tannenbaum, et al., 1961) for the purpose of attaining a goal (Stogdill, 1974; Bennis & Townsend, 1995; Chemers, 1997; Bass & Bass, 2008; Banerjee & Ercetin, 2012). Several theories of leadership were examined, and findings showed that there is a limited examination of ethical leadership skills (Kavathatzopoulos and Rigas, 1998; Heres and Lasthuizen, 2013).

The review of the Nigerian context was conducted within this study. From findings, the public sector plays an important part within the Nigerian economy through the provision of employment and avenues for economic growth and development (Edo & Ikelegbe, 2014; Orukpe & Omoruyi, 2017). The Nigerian public sector was found to face several challenges due to four factors namely, the economic factor, socio-cultural factor, socio-political factor and the leadership factor (Ogbeidi, 2012; Opara, 2014; Nwokorie, 2016; Gundu, 2011; Ehiyamen, et al., 2009). Findings from the narrative review provided deficits in leadership within the public sector in Nigeria namely, the lack of skills and the issues of unethical behaviours.

9.2.3. Systematic Literature Review

A systematic review of literature on ethical leadership was conducted. This method proffers a critical exploration of ethical leadership literature as this process provides an unbiased, rigorous and evidence-based approach to analyse fragmented literature (Nightingale, 2009; Piper, 2013; Wright et al., 2007; Harrison et al., 2016; Denyer & Tranfield, 2003). The SLR presented quantitative and qualitative analysis of its outcome. The quantitative analysis provided a detailed exploration and scope of papers identifying the research type and demography. From findings, there exists no empirical research within the Nigerian public sector context that examines ethical leadership. Findings also elucidated the qualitative approach to the exploration of ethical leadership. Findings from the SLR identified several gaps within the literature with emphasis on the development of an ethical leadership skills framework. Whilst there exists one conceptual paper on ethic-based leadership skill (Haq, 2011), no empirical study focused on ethical leadership skills.

9.2.4. Research Methodology

The methodological choice of this study was justified and informed by its research aim, objectives and questions. An inductive approach was adopted. It finds solutions to a problem by beginning from the area of study (specific focus) and creates a theory from the collated data acquired (Jebreen, 2012; Thomas, 2006; Elo & Kyngas, 2007). This was based on the provision of a better understanding of the concept of ethical leadership and the ethical leadership skills required to foster effective performance within public sector organisations. The research adopted an interpretivist philosophy to proffer a better understanding in relation to the social and human context of leaders in the Nigerian public sector (Chowdhury, 2014; Lin, 1998; Walsham, 1995).

This research study employed a qualitative method using semi-structured interviews to acquire rich data from participants in the Nigerian public sector (Bryman, 2004; Neumann, 2006; Looi,

2014). The interview guide was developed through prior understanding of literature in the field of ethical leadership, ethics and leadership. Interviews were conducted with 25 participants who were identified through a purposive sampling strategy.

Thematic analysis was utilised to proffer a clearer insight using King et al. (2019) three step coding framework. Findings from the study provided major themes: the conceptualisation of ethical leadership, challenges and the skills. From a conceptualisation perspective, a revised definition of ethical leadership was provided which was influenced by findings from the study. Four main challenges were identified namely: internal and external factors, disregard for rules and regulation, inadequate level of ethical leadership skills and cognitive dissonance & group prototypicality. Four categories of skills were also identified namely, interpersonal, technical, conceptual and ethical skills.

9.3. Contribution to Knowledge

9.3.1. Methodological Contribution

This study provides a methodological contribution to the field of ethical leadership through the use of a systematic literature review. This study adopted a systematic approach to leadership emphasizing the quantitative and qualitative analysis and providing a detailed description of the field. From literature findings, works in the field have not adopted this method in exploring ethical leadership. The adoption of an SLR provided an unbiased exploration of the field and utilised a thematic approach to the literature.

The study also provides a methodological contribution to the field of ethical leadership through the use of a qualitative research method and the focus on the public sector. Whilst most empirical studies in the field have adopted a quantitative approach in examining leadership and ethical leadership, the systematic literature review conducted elucidated a limitation of its adoption. It therefore adds to the body of knowledge in providing a qualitative approach to

ethical leadership. Furthermore, this study contributes to knowledge through the exploration of ethical leadership within the public sector. From the outcome of the SLR, there exists a limited number of studies that have examined ethical leadership from the public sector. This study provides an empirical contribution to the public sector.

9.3.2. Demographical Contribution

This study provides a demographical contribution to the field of ethical leadership through the exploration of a developing country perspective. Few studies have examined ethical leadership from several geographical perspectives (Resick et al, 2006; Eisenbiess, 2012; Eisenbiess & Brodbeck, 2014). Furthermore, most empirical work on ethical leadership provides a Western, Eastern and Asian perspective with limited empirical studies from the African perspective. This study provides an empirical research addressing a developing country from Africa (Nigeria).

9.3.3. Empirical Contribution

This study presents an empirical contribution to the understanding of ethical leadership through the context of the Nigerian public sector. Whilst few studies have provided conceptual understanding of ethical leadership from the Nigerian perspective from the private sector, the context of the Nigerian public sector has not been previously examined. This study facilitates further insight from the Nigerian public sector. The systematic literature review highlighted some gaps with regards to empirical evidence in relation to the development of ethical leadership. Findings elucidated the lack of development in the skills perspective of an ethical leader. Most scholarly works have explored the identity, behavioural and performance perspective of ethical leadership. One conceptual work in the field proposed an ethic-based skills model but lacked the empirical evidence to support their study.

This study adds to the body of literature by providing a skills-based framework for ethical leadership development to foster performance from a developing country context. Whilst there

exist several skills model within mainstream leadership literature, this study provides an empirical skills framework to foster ethical leadership. Furthermore, findings from the study shows a positive influence of skills on performance.

Few studies have identified challenges in the implementation of ethical leadership (linear and curvilinear effect) on employee behaviour, employee performance and stakeholders (please refer to works by Gok et al., 2017; Stouten et al., 2013; Greenbaum et al., 2015; Brown & Mitchell, 2010; Evans et al., 2016, Quade et al., 2017; Babalola et al., 2016; Miao et al., 2013). This study has explored the ethic-based challenges facing ethical leaders in the public sector and identified four key themes namely, internal and external factors, the lack of skills, disregard for rules and regulation and cognitive dissonance/group prototypicality. While some studies have elucidated some factors affecting ethical leaders, this study highlight a key factor can be attributed to cognitive dissonance. Price (2017) proposes a choice by ethical leaders to be amoral. Findings from this study asserts cognitive dissonance as a major factor for leaders becoming amoral over a long period of time. While there exist some negative effects of ethical leadership implementation, these study addresses the utilisation of skills in mitigating these challenges.

9.3.4. Theoretical Contribution

This study presents a theoretical contribution to the body of knowledge. Studies in the field of ethical leadership have addressed challenges facing the definition of ethical leadership (Voegtlin, 2016; Price, 2017; Eisenbeiss, 2012). While these studies have conceptualised ethical leadership from a behaviour perspective, this study presents a skills-based definition to the concept of ethical leadership from the Nigerian public sector context.

9.3.5. Implications for Practice

There are several implications for practice from the outcome of this doctoral study. This study provides a practical basis for the development of ethical leadership within the body of literature and provides an operationalised framework for managers and leaders within various sectors of industries. Whilst this study is focused on the public sector industry, organisational leaders in private and hybrid institutions can inculcate developmental programs on the acquisition and the awareness to the necessity of ethical leadership skills. Another implication to practice for leaders from the outcome of this research is the ability to develop ethical skills mostly critical to identifying and tackling ethical based challenges within the industry. Whilst this study was focused on public sector, organisational leaders can face similar challenges within private and hybrid sectors. This study provides the practical instruments to understand, mitigate and develop to ensure a more effective outcome, employee commitment and in the long run improve organisational performance.

The Nigerian public sector can be considered as one of the major driving sectors within the Nigerian economy in terms of employment, economic growth and development (Imhonopi & Ugochukwu, 2013). While this sector is a major driver, it has been reeled by a growing number of challenges most especially the leadership factor. Most leaders in the sector lack the skillset to foster ethical culture and improve performance. Findings from this research could bridge the leadership skills gap within the sector and help in the mitigation of unethical behaviour and practices in the Nigerian public sector. This skills framework could proffer a basis for the development of ethical leaders in the public sector.

9.4. Limitations

9.4.1. Sample Limitation

From the sample perspective, there exist some limitation to this study. As stated, within this thesis, the study focused on one major public sector organisation in Nigeria namely, NNPC.

Whilst the NNPC provides an avenue to explore the social and human context of leaders from various subsidiaries within the organisation at different locations, there exists a limitation of exploring the concept of ethical leadership from one organisation. Findings within this study might be limited to the understanding of leaders within this organisation. Furthermore, a limitation within this study is the sample size (25). However as stated earlier in the thesis, theoretical saturation was reached at the 18th interview and a larger sample would not have provided richer information to the study.

9.5. Future Research

Whilst this study's contribution to knowledge focused on the skills framework for ethical leadership and the challenges facing the inculcation of this framework in the sector. There are various avenues for future research and development in the field.

9.5.1. Cognitive Dissonance (Ethical Dissonance)

Cognitive dissonance (ethical) was a major theme from the challenges facing ethical leaders from this study. Whilst cognitive dissonance within the body of literature is not relatively new, there exists limited literature exploring the phenomenon in ethical leadership literature. Ethical leaders from the findings are faced with ethical situations which may lead to them being amoral or unethical in the long run. There is a need for the exploration of the behavioural impact of cognitive dissonance on ethical leadership development and the mechanisms to perceive and mitigate dissonance. Furthermore, there is a necessity to explore the skills in mitigating the effects of dissonance within other organisations.

9.5.2. Ethical Theories in Ethical Leadership

Whilst ethical leadership literature has emphasised the understanding of ethics as the integral pillar in its development, there is a need for the exploration of ethical theories in the development of an ethical leader. Some works in literature have asserted variation in the theory

definition of ethical leaders namely, deontological and virtue ethics (Knights & Majella, 2006; Whetstone, 2001; Arjoon, 2000; Knights & Majella, 2005; Morrison, 2001; Molyneaux, 2003). There exist limited empirical studies to assert these understanding. Whilst this study adopted a virtue ethics approach to understanding ethical leadership, there is a need for further exploration of ethics as a constituent of ethical leadership in terms of virtue or duty.

9.6. Conclusion

This research study has explored the concept of ethical leadership in the Nigerian public sector, with the purpose of identifying the ethic-based challenges facing ethical leaders and the required skills needed for their effectiveness. Respondents from the study provided insightful data through semi-structured interviews. These interviews were analysed thematically. The outcome from the Nigerian public sector identified three main themes namely the conceptualisation, the challenges and the skills.

An empirical ethical leadership framework was developed and presented from the findings of this thesis. Ethical leaders in the Nigerian public sector encountered several ethic-based challenges namely, internal and external factors, inadequate level of skills, disregard for rules and regulation and cognitive dissonance. The employment of skills within the sector have mitigated the ethical issues faced in the organisation and has fostered employee commitment and organisational performance. This study provides the first empirical exploration of the skills perspective of ethical leadership in the public sector in a developing country context in literature.

This study presents a contribution to knowledge methodologically, demographically, empirically and theoretically.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Interview Schedule

SECOND SECTION: ROLES, ETHICS AND LEADERSHIP SKILLS

1. What are your roles and responsibilities within the organisation?
2. What do you understand by leadership?
3. What are the attributes of an effective leader?
4. What type of leadership style do you adopt within the public sector?
5. What are the required skills needed to meet these responsibilities?
6. Are leadership skill development programs provided to meet these responsibilities?
7. What do you understand by ethics and how does it influence your perception of leadership?
8. As a leader within the public sector, what ethical challenges have you encountered?

THIRD SECTION: DEVELOPING SPECIFICITY: ETHICAL CHALLENGES, ETHICAL LEADERSHIP SKILLS AND PERFORMANCE

1. What are the prevalent ethic problems and challenges facing leaders in the public sector in terms of performance and organisational growth?
2. Are there adequate training facilities and ethic skill acquisition programs to help tackle these challenges?
3. Do these required skills meet the ethical challenges within the public sector?
4. How can these challenges be eliminated within the public sector?

5. What do you understand by ethical leadership?
6. How do you influence ethics to subordinates within the sector (skills)?
7. Do ethics influence performance within the public sector?
8. Do ethical skills play critical roles in influencing performance (Decision-making, communicating and empathy).
9. Do ethics play a role in decision making in the public sector?
10. How does unethical environment influence ethical leaders within the public sector, and can this affect a leader's ethicality?
11. How do leaders mitigate these issues?
12. Do ethics inhibit organisational performance?
13. Does ethical leader skills foster (employee engagement, organisational citizen behaviour)
14. Does effective leadership provide competitive advantage?

Appendix 2: Information Sheets for Potential Participants

Effective Ethical Leadership Framework within the Nigerian Public Sector: The Need for skills as an integral aspect of fostering performance.

My name is Adeshipo Adebawale Samuel and I am a post graduate student from the School of Business and enterprise at University of the West of Scotland. As part of my degree course, I am undertaking a research project for my doctoral dissertation. The title of my project is: Effective Ethical Leadership Framework within the Nigerian Public Sector: The Need for skills as an integral aspect of fostering performance.

This study will investigate the concept of ethical leadership within the Nigerian public sector and provide a better understanding of the concept of ethical leadership and explores the need for skills as a mechanism for improving performance within the public sector.

The findings of this study will be useful/applicable to both the academic community and public service management as it highlights the necessary skills and recommendations for improving performance and provision of solutions to the challenges facing existing leadership framework within the Nigerian public sector.

I am looking for volunteers to participate in this project. There are no criteria (e.g. gender, age, or health) for being included or excluded – everyone is welcome to take part. This research is focused towards individuals within management roles, supervisor roles and employees working within the public sphere of business.

If you agree to participate in the study, you will be asked to fill a consent form. The researcher is not aware of any risks associated with filling the consent form. The whole procedure should take no longer than 30-60 minutes. You will be free to withdraw from the study at any stage, you would not have to give a reason, and it will not affect your treatment (if applicable). This

project will also mean that I will have to read your recording or transcript (documents or other forms of information)

All data will be anonymised as much as possible. Your name will be replaced with a participant number or a pseudonym, and it will not be possible for you to be identified in any reporting of the data gathered. All data collected will be kept in a secure place (specify e.g. locked cabinet in locked room/stored on a pc that is password protected) to which only the investigator has sole access. These will be kept till the end of the examination process, following which all data that could identify you will be destroyed.

The results may be published in a journal or presented at a conference / *or* final doctoral thesis.

If you would like to contact an independent person, who knows about this project but is not involved in it, you are welcome to contact Dr Christian Harrison. His contact details are given below.

Email- [REDACTED]

If you have read and understood this information sheet, any questions you had have been answered, and you would like to be a participant in the study, please now see the consent form.

Appendix 3: Publication List

Adeshipo, A.S. and Harrison, C (2021) The need for the development of a skills perspective to Ethical leadership: A systematic review. European Management Review. Manuscript under review.

Adeshipo, A. S. and Harrison, C. (2020). “Ethical leadership in the Public sector: An African perspective”. In *British Academy of Management 2020 Conference in the Cloud*: British Academy of Management.

Adeshipo, A. S. and Harrison, C. (2018). “Ethical leadership: the way forward”. In *British Academy of Management 2018 Conference Proceedings [565]* Bristol: British Academy of Management.

Adeshipo, A. S. and Harrison, C. (2018). “Ethical leadership: an effective and efficient leadership approach for the Nigeria public sector”. In *British Academy of Management 2018 Conference Proceedings (Vol. 2018). [567]* Bristol: British Academy of Management

Appendix 4: Ethical Approval Letter

31/01/2019

Dear Adebowale Adeshipo,

Your application 7790: Effective Ethical Leadership Framework within the Nigerian Public Sector: The Need for skills as an integral aspect of fostering performance, submission 6163, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean
